

**Investigating the level of financial performance analysis in
franchising and managerial ownership within the
restaurant industry in the areas of Taiwan.**

SHU-PEI HUANG

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor Business Administration (DBA)

September 2023

Declaration of Authorship

I declare that the work in this thesis was carried out in accordance with the regulations of the University of the West of Scotland and is original except where indicated by specific reference in the text. No part of the thesis has been submitted as part of any other academic award. The thesis has not been presented to any other education institution in the United Kingdom or overseas.

Any views expressed in the thesis are those of the author and in no way represent those of the University.

Signed Date.....

(Shu-Pei Huang)

Abstract

This research examines the correlation between the shareholding structure and the corporate performance of public catering companies. As the share of insiders' shareholding increases, the company's agency problems can be reduced and the company's value increased; while the investment of legal entities can monitor the performance of the company's management together with the market investors, reducing agency problems and increasing the company's value. However, few studies have examined if and how ownership and performance and Degree of Franchise in Asia are related. In most studies when Return on Assets is used as the performance variable, the non-direct relationship between insider shareholding ratio and company performance is particularly evident. In terms of knowledge contribution, this study adds Operating Margin Rate to the existing MO model and adds Director hold degree to the existing DOF model. Manager's relative hold degree and corporation hold degree are analysed because most chain restaurants in Taiwan are family businesses, their manager is a shareholder or a relative, these will affect the performance of the franchise business. Consequently, add these factors to analyse the Degree of Franchise.

This study aims to explore the relationship between the governance of franchise companies and the operating performance of Taiwan restaurants. Therefore, by studying the characteristics of the composition of the board of directors, this research will discuss how to set up internal controls to reduce the company's agency problems. In this study, a sample of Taiwanese restaurant franchise listed companies from 2016 to 2020 and excluding companies with insufficient data and non-compliant sampling standards. A total of 466 firm-quarter-year samples were collected from 28 companies, the least square method is used to explore the possible impact of equity structure and financial factors including ROA and EPS on the operation of the company.

Based on undertaking multiple regression analysis, the study's findings show in terms of multiple regression analysis, that there is a positive relationship between corporate shareholding ratio and company performance. In particular, the shareholding of directors and supervisors is negatively correlated with operating performance. On the one hand, it is revealed that the company's directors and supervisors do not seem to perform their due management and supervision functions to affect operating performance. On the other hand, this research article also supports the importance of institutional investors' shareholdings.

The correlation between stock or shareholding preference and business performance is also analysed and only the manager with director status shareholding degree is negative correlation, others are positive correlation.

This study's findings are useful for restaurants which are run with franchise systems. It could provide directors with the basis for corporate governance on developing the franchise system and whether hiring managers requires investment in shares. Lastly, the regression results also show the important relationship the roles of shareholding degree between financial ratios, such as return on assets (ROA), and earnings per share (EPS). The findings also indirectly provide evidence that the Taiwan restaurant industry's operating performance is reflected in increased levels of assets in recent years.

Acknowledgements

Firstly, I must thank my Lead Supervisor Dr Allison Wylde and Dr Javad Izad, Second Supervisor Dr Mandana, Assessor Dr Matin Ghanam Boushra and Oliver Witkin who is a librarian academic skills adviser from UWS for my careful guidance and continuous encouragement and training of thinking and reasoning skills. In addition, I also want to thank the oral examination committee members. Their corrections and many valuable suggestions have made this paper infinitely more complete. I am sincerely grateful.

After 20 years of a working life, I returned to a campus life, which is full of expectation and joy. The three years of your interesting graduate school experience was full and compact. During this period, under the pressure of both schoolwork and daily work, thanks to my company's chief John Rickard, I have been given a lot of encouragement, and the former colleagues, Dr. Sylvia Wang, assisted me to increase my professional knowledge and inspire my ability to think logically during my studies. Thanks a lot for helping me to bring this paper to a completion, I am full of infinite gratitude.

Most importantly, I want to thank my family, my parents, and my siblings, because of your constant support, you allowed me to complete my studies without any worries.

During the research period, especial between 2020 and 2021, I encountered difficulties in my livelihood and studies. The covid-19 epidemic made study and the gathering of research difficult for us all and the illness of my Taiwanese family members forced me to interrupt my studies and return to Taiwan to take care of them. Unfortunately, my sister passed away in February 2022. I will miss her forever and thank her for her support and the care she showed me throughout her life.

Finally, I would like to thank all my tutors and friends, because having you with me is the greatest happiness of my life. I offer my sincerest blessings and gratitude here and wish you every success in your lives, thanks all of you.

Table of Contents

Declaration of Authorship	1
Abstract	2
Acknowledgements.....	4
Chapter 1 - Introduction	14
1.1 Background of the Study	14
1.2 The Problem Statement	17
1.3 Research Aim.....	19
1.4 Research Question, Objectives, and Hypothesis	20
1.4.1 Research Question.....	20
1.4.2 Research Objectives	21
1.4.3 Research Hypothesis:	21
1.5 Research scope	22
1.6 Research Motivation	23
1.6.1 Motivation 1	24
1.6.2 Motivation 2	27
1.7 Expected Contributions	29
1.7.1 Academic Contributions.....	30
1.7.2 Professional Practice	30
1.8 The structure of this thesis	32
1.9 The research framework flow chart.....	36
1.10 Chapter Summary	37
Chapter 2- Literature Review.....	38
2.1 Introduction	38
2.2 Historical Review of Franchise	40
2.3 Definitions of Franchise.....	42
2.4 Theories Discussion of Franchise	49

2.4.1 Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee	49
2.4.2 Agency theory.....	51
2.4.3 Brand resonance	54
2.4.4 The theories associated with both sides of the franchise.	59
2.5 Chapter Summary	67
Chapter 3 –Related Research on the Performance of the Catering Industry.....	69
3.1 Introduction	69
3.2 The studies involving the company's operating performance.....	71
3.2.1 Performance Appraisal	71
3.2.2 Key success factors.....	73
3.2.3 Review of the dynamics of family businesses	75
3.2.4 The correlation of ownership structure and company performance	77
3.3 Taiwan development of franchise chain business.....	79
3.3.1 The development of Taiwan's catering industry.....	81
3.3.2 Future environment forecast.....	85
3.4 Franchise system of catering	93
3.4.1Catering management functions.....	93
3.4.2 Service operation side	95
3.4.3 Diversified consumption	99
3.4.4 Overseas expansion.....	103
3.4.5 Social participation and policy communication	105
3.4.6 The type of American franchise system.....	107
3.4.7 The experience of promoting franchise chain business in North American countries.....	108
3.4.8 Experience in promoting franchise chain business in Asian countries.....	110
3.4.9 East Asian countries' policies and promote.....	115
3.4.10 The type of Japanese franchise system	116
3.4.11 Pros and Cons of chain types.....	120
3.5 Global current catering status of franchise & development.....	121
3.5.1 The benefits of the franchise system	122
3.5.2 The weaknesses of the franchise system.....	123
3.5.3 Impact of franchise operation on industry, society, and economy	124
3.6 Crisis management capabilities.....	125

3.6.1 Coronavirus disease crisis.....	125
3.6.2 Redesign of business strategies.....	126
3.7 Key points of theories of franchise	127
3.7.1 Main statements of theories	127
3.7.2 Firm performance approach strategy.....	129
3.8 Chapter Summary	130
Chapter 4- Research Methodology.....	132
4.1 Introduction	132
4.2 Research Design.....	134
4.2.1 Research Design Flow Structure	134
4.2.2 The benefits of the quantitative approach.....	136
4.3 Hypothesis Development	137
4.3.1 Introduction.....	137
4.3.2 Research Hypotheses	137
4.3.3 Conceptual Framework of Hypothesis.....	143
4.4 Variables Definition	145
4.4.1 Research variable definition	145
4.4.2 The sign of variables.....	154
4.5 Data Collection & Sample Selection.....	154
4.5.1 Research period and research samples	154
4.5.2 Data source	155
4.5.3 About the IFRSs	161
4.5.4 Data procedures	164
4.6 Research Approach	168
4.6.1 The descriptive analysis	168
4.6.2 The multiple regression model.....	168
4.6.3 Validation of Regression models	174
Chapter 5 Empirical analysis and results.....	175
5.1 Introduction	175
5.2 Descriptive statistics.....	175
5.3 Multicollinearity Analysis	179

5.3.1 Correlation coefficient Analysis.....	179
5.3.2 VIF (variance inflation factor) Analysis	182
5.3.3 Independence Test of Residuals	183
5.4 Empirical Results-Regression Analysis.....	184
5.4.1 Analysis of the correlation coefficient between the ownership structure and ROA and EPS	185
5.4.2 Analysis of the correlation coefficient between ownership structure and DOF ..	187
5.4.3 Regression analysis of ROA performance under MO model.....	188
5.4.4 Regression analysis of EPS performance under MO model.....	188
5.4.5 Regression analysis of DOF performance under the DOF model.....	189
5.5 Regression Analysis with different business code and model summary	190
5.5.1 The four catering Type on ROA.....	190
5.5.2 The catering industries on EPS	191
5.5.3 The catering industries on DOF.....	193
5.6 Research Findings and Discussion	194
Chapter 6- Conclusion	197
6.1 Introduction	197
6.2 Analysis conclusion.....	197
6.3 Managerial Implications	199
6.4 Recommendation	200
6.4.1 Catering industry owner.....	200
6.4.2 Government agencies	201
6.4.3 Future investors of franchise business	202
6.5 Research limitations.....	203
6.6 Suggestions for future research directions.....	204
Appendix.....	205
Reference	213

List of Tables

Table 1 Franchise operations historical period	41
Table 2 Definition of franchise business-based on management characteristics.....	44
Table 3 The definition of chain industry based on the number of franchisees.	47
Table 4 Definition of various categories of catering industry of Taiwan	84
Table 5 Frequently Questions in the Typical Chain and Catering Companies.....	97
Table 6 Consolidation of opinions from industry and academia.....	106
Table 7 The largest franchise chain brand in the U.S.	109
Table 8 East Asian countries' policies to promote franchise chain industry.....	115
Table 9 Chain franchise types	118
Table 10 Advantages and disadvantages of chain types.....	120
Table 11 A summary table of empirical research issue`s and hypotheses	143
Table 12 Definition of Variables.....	153
Table 13 The sign of variables.....	154
Table 14 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria of research.....	155
Table 15 Sample companies Market capitalisation and number of branches	158
Table 16 IFRSs historical name and abbreviation	161
Table 17 Other countries practice with IFRSs.	162
Table 18 Data definitions and code -IFRSs	163
Table 19 Business Code.....	164
Table 20 Data collection from Goodinfo.....	165
Table 21 Data filtering after in total	166
Table 22 Descriptive statistics of sample variables	176
Table 23 Pearson's Correlation Matrix.....	181
Table 24 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 1	182
Table 25 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 2	182
Table 26 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 3	183
Table 27 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 4	183
Table 28 Regression DW statistics on Model 3	184
Table 29 Regression DW statistics on Model 4	184
Table 30 Hypothesis 1 result	185
Table 31 Hypothesis 2 result	186
Table 32 Hypothesis 3 result	186
Table 33 Hypothesis 4 result	186
Table 34 Regression Analysis of Ownership structure and ROA.....	187
Table 35 Regression Analysis of Ownership structure and EPS	187
Table 36 Regression Analysis of Ownership Structure and DOF	188
Table 37 Regression analysis with ROA as the performance measure on MO	188
Table 38 Regression analysis with EPS on MO model.....	189
Table 39 Regression analysis with DOF on DOF model.....	189
Table 40 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on ROA	191
Table 41 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on ROA	191
Table 42 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on EPS.....	192
Table 43 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on EPS.....	193
Table 44 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on DOF.....	193
Table 45 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on DOF.....	194

List of Figures

Figure 1 Hypothesis and questions correspondence	16
Figure 2 The research framework flow chart	36
Figure 3 Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee	50
Figure 4 Average franchise cost in the U.S.	109
Figure 5 The average cost of investing in franchised businesses in the U.S.	110
Figure 6 Research Design Flow Structure	135
Figure 7 Conceptual Framework of Hypothesis	144
Figure 8 The process of collecting data from different sources.	156
Figure 9 Managerial Ownership from 2016-2020.	177
Figure 10 Degree of Franchise from 2016-2020	178

List of Appendix

Appendix 1 Definition of Key Terms	205
Appendix 2 Theories authors, method and finding list from 1996 to 2020.	206
Appendix 3 The sample companies and stock code	212

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full name
AC	Assign Chain
ACFPT	ASSOCIATION OF CHAIN AND FRANCHISE PROMOTION, TAIWAN
AEC	ASEAN Economic Community
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMA	American Marketing Association
APEC	Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation
AR	Augmented Reality
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
C/P	Cost-effectiveness
CapEx	Capital Expenditures.
CapInt	Capital intensity
CC	Cooperate chain
CEO	Chief Executive officer
CFI	Corporate Finance Institute
CFO	Cash from Operations
CHD	Corporate shareholding Degree
CIS	Corporate identity
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
CRSP	Centre for Research in Security Prices
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CV	Control variables
CX	Customer Experience
DGBAS	Directorate-General of Budget, Accounting and Statistics, Executive Yun, R.O.C. (Taiwan)
DHD	Director shareholding degree
DOF	Degree of Franchise
DV	Dependent variables
DW value	Durbin Watson statistics
E2E	Employers to Employee
EBIT	Earnings Before Interest and Tax
ECFA	Cross-Straits Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement

EPS	Earing per share
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FC	Franchise chain
FCF	Free Cash Flow
FSR	Franchisor Social Responsibility
FTC	FAIR TRADE COMMISSION
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
Growth	Sales Growth
IASs	International Accounting Standards
IFA	International Franchise Association (IFA)
IFRICs	International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee
IFRSs	International Financial Reporting Standards
InvRate	Investment Rate
IoT	Internet of Things
IV	Independent variables
JFA	Japanese Franchise Association
KSF	key success factor
Lev	Leverage, Debt ratio
log	Natural logarithm
MO	Managerial Ownership
MOEA	Ministry of Economic Affairs, R.O.C.
MOTC	Ministry of Transportation and Communications. R.O.C.
MP	Market Capitalization
MRHD	Manager relative shareholding degree
MTB	Market-to-book
NI	Net Income
NOI	Net operating income
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares Method
OMRate	Operating Margin Rate
OTC	Over-the-counter
PPE	property, plant, and equipment
QSR	Quick-Service-Restaurant systems
RC	Regular chain

ROA	Return on Assets
ROC	Republic Of China
ROE	Return of Equity
Sale	Net Revenues
SIC	Standard Industrial Classification
SICs	Standing Interpretations Committee
Size	Firm Size
SMEs	Small and medium enterprises
SPSS	Statistical Product and Service Solutions
TA	Total Assets
TD	Total Debt
TEJ	Taiwan Economic Journal
TFTC	Taiwan Fair Trade Commission
TS	Total number of shares
TTR	Taiwan Trend Research
TWSE	Taiwan Stock Exchange Corporation
VC	Voluntary chain
VIF	Variance Inflation Factor
VR	Virtual Reality

Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

The entrepreneurial model in Taiwan today is different from decades ago, and companies are run around the world with new technologies and advanced methods. Arora and Sharma (2022) explored that qualitative and theoretical perspectives, emphasizing the importance of artificial intelligence and big data applications in multi-sectoral scenarios of global enterprises. Taiwan's economy has been on the rise over the years and people's consumption has increased as the population has grown, and the population has moved to the cities. Because of its increasing demand for labour supply and food service, most people prefer to dine out, rather than buying and cooking their own meals and it is an easy option for them to find meals they like. Most consumers are looking for a balanced diet, quality food, cheap and fast service on busy workdays, and they spend very little time on lunch and dinner. According to the Ministry of Economic Affairs, since the 2020 pandemic (COVID-19), dine-in restaurants have fallen by 30%, while fast-food restaurants, mainly American brands, have increased by 5.4% because they already have strong technology in reaching customers. with There is extra value in getting services like takeout, drive-thru and food delivery providers (Jha, 2022).

The scale of modern enterprises is getting larger and larger. To raise enough working capital for enterprises, business owners often raise their equity to facilitate the raising of capital, which increases the shareholding ratio of external shareholders and diversifies the company's equity, resulting in the gradual separation of ownership and management rights. Yao, et al. (2018) research results show that management ownership has a positive impact on performance. Good corporate governance is essential for all organisations and must be encouraged for the benefit of all stakeholders (Alabdullah, 2018). Because managers may only have a minority stake in the company, only employees may receive bonus, or even do not hold shares, resulting in managers' self-interest motives, sacrificing the overall interests of the company personal gains, resulting in conflicts between shareholders and managers. This is the so-called agency problem (Hao, 2022).

One of the solutions is that managers are given partial shares in the company, so that the interests of managers are consistent with the shareholders of the company, to reduce the

occurrence of agency problems. Another solution is to invite managers to join the board of directors, and for the directors to also serve as managers. Bencomo (2021) linked those independent non-executive directors are key corporate governance personnel. In view of their multiple beneficial attributes, they should play a prominent role in the corporate form (Bencomo, 2021). For this reason, mediation can be an effective method for resolving corporate governance disputes. Independent non-executive directors can act as mediators and make appropriate judgements on disputes related to corporate governance. A working knowledge would improve the effectiveness of decision-making, and directors who do not have the status of company managers can be more objective and better able to evaluate company decisions. Because of this, company directors and supervisors can play a professional and independent supervisory role in company decisions to ensure the interests of shareholders (Byrd and Hickman, 1992).

In my point of view, it is precisely because of these characteristics that independent non-executive directors can play a prominent role in the company's response to shareholders, stakeholders and internal disputes related to corporate governance and board disputes.

This article focuses on eight points for franchise restaurants in Taiwan. The hypothesis and the questions correspondence show below. Starting Research Question 1 and 2 to reasoning Research Hypothesis 1, Research Hypothesis 2 and Research Hypothesis 3. Analyse whether managers holding company shares, including relatives of managers, have positive or negative performance how it effects on the company's financial performance, especially managers who with director status, it may have a negative performance. As of Research Question 1 set assumptions Research Hypothesis 4, the institutional shareholding ratio reaches supervisory role. After Research Question 3 set assumptions from Research Hypothesis 5 to Hypothesis 8, here this research mainly analyses the impact of equity structure on the franchise rate.

Figure 1 Hypothesis and questions correspondence

Since the service industry accounts for about 70% of Taiwan's GDP, the government has drafted several guidance and promotion measures in recent years to promote the export of various key service industries. Taiwan franchise businesses also have great potential to enter the international markets (Xu, 2023). In terms of assisting Taiwanese enterprises to participate in distribution services such as wholesale and retail, Taiwan has become an important model for enterprises to engage in distribution services due to the vigorous and diversified development of franchise businesses. According to statistics, the annual output value of Taiwan's franchise businesses is about 1.7 trillion yuan, with 180 types of industry categories, which can be called another "trillion yuan" industry in Taiwan; the total number of chain stores is close to 1,500, and the total number of stores is nearly 90,000 (Huang, 2021). In terms of land area and total population, Taiwan can be said to have the highest density of franchise headquarters in the world, and it has strong overseas development capabilities. However, if the service industry is classified according to the competent authority, the areas

covered by the Ministry of Economic Affairs in the service industry classification include wholesale and retail, catering, warehousing and logistics, leasing, professional scientific and technical services industry, leisure service industry, and other service industries, a total of seven categories (National-Statistics, 2011).

According to Fox's research on the formation process of gourmet identity (Fox, 2007), a unique and memorable gourmet identity is essential to the success of a destination. Discuss the formation process of the destination's gourmet identity from five aspects: differentiation, beautification, authentication, symbolism, and vitality. Differentiation refers to the argument that each culture is marked with unique food, meals, and menu choices. Çalışkan (2013) found that aestheticization is the use of unique national aesthetic values, such as tastes, blends, and the presentation of local dishes. In addition, the identity verification symbolises the characteristic that the food identity truly belongs to the region and cannot be imitated. Symbolization refers to the preservation of food heritage attributes through various signs and symbols, and to increase the value of food logos (Lin & Mao, 2015). Rejuvenation refers to reviving old customs and traditions and applying them to target destinations.

In addition, a common situation in companies in Asian countries is that the family business within the company has a strong influence, and at the same time family members are the heads or management of the company resulting in the characteristics of ownership and management (Shen, 2018). Broccardo, Truant & Zicari (2019) claim that family businesses have certain characteristics that are different from non-family businesses, so it is valuable to analyse whether these characteristics are also reflected in their attitudes towards sustainability. Specifically, the determinants of the concept of family business sustainability are unclear (Broccardo, Truant & Zicari, 2019). Although this characteristic makes the authority of the management more concentrated within the company, it helps to implement the order (Shen, 2018). However, it is easy to cause the person in charge to dictate and make inappropriate decisions for their own interests, which in turn endangers the rights of generally disadvantaged shareholders. The understanding of agency problems and the way to deal with them are the topics that the investing public must study before they decide to invest.

1.2 The Problem Statement

The catering industry is an industry formed to meet the basic needs of people's physiological

functions. It has the characteristics of low entry threshold, high labour intensiveness and easy imitation of products or services. Because of its low technical threshold and low operating costs, there are many operators in the industry (TTR, 2020). It is a highly competitive industry. In recent years, with the economic growth and the increase in national income, people's living standards have been greatly improved. The consumption pattern of consumers' catering needs has changed, and the food culture that enhances life enjoyment has become more pursued, resulting in the existence of diverse and often competing food standards. Considering the importance of certain dietary claims to a person's integrity, personal evaluation standards and cultural habits, legal regulations related to this are often inextricably intertwined (Ceva, Testino and Zuolo, 2015).

In addition, in recent years, the rise of exotic cuisine, such as South Korea and Japanese, the United States and other well-known catering brands have successively joined the industry, increasing the degree of industrial competition. The catering industry also has the characteristics of a short shelf life of raw materials, inability to store products and services, and high turnover rate of personnel, so that cost control is an important issue for the industry (TTR, 2020). Therefore, how operators use operating resources to continuously innovate products and services to meet consumer demand, create competitive advantages under severe competitive pressure and cost control, and stand firm in industrial competition currently pose a major challenge (TTR, 2020).

Firstly, there are many conflicts and issues of recognition of rights and responsibilities between the franchiser and the franchisees if the franchising system is not comprehensive. Before investing into the franchise, the problems of the franchise management system may not be visible; only when it is in operation, the problem of the real franchise system is known (Hsu, 2013). For example, the franchiser fails to supply materials in time, or increases in the purchase price of goods to franchisees, resulting in a decrease in profits of franchisees. If these problems are not well communicated between franchiser and franchisees, it will cause damaging disputes between them (Frazer, et al., 2012). This could jeopardise the renewal of the franchise for the next year within the business.

Secondly, many relative factors affect the company's performance between managerial ownership and franchising system in the catering business. In any catering industry that directly faces their customers, the operator who is manager, carries a very important role

within the corporation. Some businesses are run by members of the family, some hire professional managers, and some are operated by those with partial shares (Stewart & Hitt, 2012). Whatever the case, their purposes are to help the firm make a maximum profit. The managers with share ownership, may direct the company's business performance to be better than managers without shares (Bhaumik & Gregoriou, 2010). In addition to giving higher incentive bonuses to managers, what other factors may affect the performance of the company.

The current operational difficulties in the catering industry are mainly due to high personnel costs, high staff turnover rates and large fluctuations in the cost of food ingredients, all of which account for more than 50% of their turnover (Chen, 2020). The catering industry has the characteristics of low barriers to entry and labour-intensive. In recent years, well-known foreign catering companies have joined the market one after another, making the competition very fierce. "Sequence of high staff turnover" (71.8%), "intensive competition among peers" (63.6%), "large fluctuations in the cost of food ingredients" and "difficulty in passing on rising costs" (56.4% each), of which "cost-increasing transfer difficulties" increased the most by 12.7 percentage points from the previous year. The beverage store industry ranked "high rent costs" (59.3%), "fighting competition among peers" (57.6%), "high staff turnover" and "food ingredients" and "cost volatility" (each 50.9%), of which "intensive competition among peers" increased by 3.5 percentage points from the previous year ().

1.3 Research Aim

This study aims to investigate and assess the level of franchising and managerial ownership within the catering industry in Taiwan. Understand whether the different shareholding ratios under the shareholding structure in Taiwan's chain restaurant industry affect the company's performance and the degree of franchise. For example, the high shareholding ratio of managers may affect the company's ROA or EPS. In this study, the family shareholding ratio of the manager is included, because these shareholding numbers may have a greater impact on the ratio. In addition, the manager's shareholding ratio is also with director status, to explore whether the company's performance and the degree of franchise are positive. In adding the MO model and the DOF model dimension this thesis addresses the current lack of understanding in performance for the role of equity structure.

1.4 Research Question, Objectives, and Hypothesis

1.4.1 Research Question

The main research question formulated are:

RQ1: Analysis of the role of equity structure on financial performance

The relationship contract theory is well suited to support behaviour between franchisers and franchisees as they seek to strike a balance between governance and performance. In franchise relationships, relationship contracts are more trustworthy and valuable for relationships based on trust and commitment. Relationship contracts are more conducive to more stable franchise cooperation, thus promoting the expansion of international franchise and group performance (Rosado-Serrano & Paul, 2018).

RQ2: Analysis of the role of the managerial ownership model affect the performance of the company.

Kurniati (2019) found that a good corporate governance has a significant negative impact on stock earnings; good corporate governance has no significant impact on financial performance and company value; stock earnings have a significant positive impact on financial performance and company value, and that financial performance has a significant impact on stock earnings and company value (Kurniati, 2019). Relatively, where there is a lack of good corporate governance mechanisms, their companies are easily manipulated by a few people and can cause fraud, which reduces the company's own potential growth space and its investment value. It may even lead to negative results such as the failure of the company's operations and vicious bankruptcy.

RQ3: Analysis of the role of the level of franchising and managerial ownership compare.

Jensen and Meckling (2019) believe that managers have potential incentives to allocate company resources in a place that is beneficial to themselves, but does not necessarily create benefits for shareholders, thus creating agency problems. Many supervision mechanisms are derived to solve these agency problems. Internal mechanisms include board supervision, ownership by managers and incentive or dismissal of managers. External mechanisms include capital market, managerial labour market and the supervision of institutional

investors. The management power is delegated to professional managers, and the shareholders elect the board of directors to supervise the professional managers and protect the interests of shareholders. In theory, the board of directors have the power to review the managers decisions and to replace the managers. Stouten, et. al. (2018) mentioned that contemporary organisations often strive to create meaningful and sustainable change. At the same time, relevant organisational research lacks easily obtained consensus on basic change management processes and principles (Stouten, Rousseau and Cremer, 2018). Therefore, to assess managers competence directors need to establish clear lines of managerial supervision. (Alabdullah, 2018) .

1.4.2 Research Objectives

Since most of the public shares held by insiders of listed companies only consider the number of shares under the manager's name, the number of shares under their family's name and the number of shares owned by their controlled subsidiaries (or investment companies) are not taken into consideration (Broccardo, Truant & Zicari, 2019). To fully clarify the impact of insider shareholding on company performance, it is necessary to consider the number of shares under the names of all family members (third-class direct blood relatives, second-class in-laws) and subsidiaries (representatives or major shareholders) (Bettinelli, 2012).

The objectives of this study that would be expected to be achieved are:

- Clarifying the role of insider shareholding and company performance (through the Nonlinear model) and identifying the relationship between insider shareholding rate and company performance.
- Interpreting the role of internal managers that also have director status, to evaluate if this is negatively related to company performance.
- Evaluating the role of corporation shareholding ratio to determine if this is positively correlated with company performance.
- Evaluating the relationship between insider shareholding ratio and franchise degree positive apart from managers with director status shareholder.

1.4.3 Research Hypothesis:

RH1: Under different managerial family levels of shareholding with a Nonlinear relationship,

that the increase in shareholding ratio has significantly different impacts on company performance.

RH2: There is a negative relationship between the director status of a manager and the company's operating performance.

RH3 : The manager's ratio of shareholding has a positive impact on company performance.

RH4 : The corporation's shareholding ratio has a positive impact on company performance.

RH5: Under different managerial family shareholding degrees, with a Nonlinear relationship, an increase in the shareholding ratio has significant differences in the impact of the company's franchise degree.

RH6: There is a positive relationship between manager (including director status) and franchise degree.

RH7 : Manager's shareholding ratio has a positive impact on the degree of franchise.

RH8 : The corporation' shareholding ratio of has a positive impact on the company's franchise degree.

1.5 Research scope

The scope of the data is for Taiwan from 2016 to 2020. There are 28 domestic listed catering companies as a sample, and they are chain catering companies and companies with more than two branches.

1.6 Research Motivation

My previous work experience was as the General Manager of a multi-site language school in Taiwan for over 10 years. To conduct this position efficiently I studied the Manager's business model and turnover performance of each branch. At that time, I was constantly looking at ways to improve the operation and management models in operation to achieve the company's expected operating performance goals. It turned out that if dividends were given to shareholders, the branch manager would consider him personally a shareholder of the company so motivated would devote himself to the company's operation and management which naturally increasing turnover. I first came to the UK to explore what opportunities were available in the Western educational system and like a lot of new arrivals I took work in the hospitality industry to earn living expenses. This was my first exposure to work in the demanding and fast-moving hospitality business and I was fascinated to see how rapid the growth and expansion of brands has occurred in the UK and how high incomes can be achieved. This aroused my interest in how multi-site chain stores can be grown and established in this industry.

The restaurant industry faces many time pressures, such as the timeliness of ingredients and the speed of meal delivery. The service attitude of the waiter, the emotional management of the chef, etc. will also affect the performance and evaluation of the product and the business. I could clearly see one needs an in-depth understanding of the hospitality franchise model to fast grow a business in this sector. I decided if I was to be a successful entrepreneur to create and develop a brand-new restaurant franchise business here or in my home country of Taiwan, I needed to deeply study the whole principle of franchising and the West was the place to do it. This is my prime motivation to study this subject to the depth of this DBA. There are two insights to learn for my research to be successful. The first is to understand what kind of franchise model is suitable for the catering industry, and to make the relationship between franchisees and headquarters successful. There has been no such research before, and it is to fill the gap in this perspective and lack of past research. If I want to successfully invest in the catering industry in the future, I need to identify what are the markers of success that I can apply from my research and ensure the successful employment and retainment of workers into the industry. The second insight I wanted was to learn was how the impact of

branch manager shareholding ratio on the company's operating performance can be provided to investors as a reference for future management decisions.

Dietary requirements and habits can be seen as economic activities carried out daily. As a result of the growth of Taiwan economic strength, the improvement of national income, and the improvement of living standards, changes in social patterns and family structure; eating out being seen as no longer a luxury expense, and the busy life of double-income families has created a growth in eating out. With the development of the Internet, many different types of catering are constantly innovating, and the overall catering market is developing steadily and rapidly. Because the catering industry has a lower threshold for entrepreneurship, it is easy to become the first choice for entrepreneurs. And the traditional foods and flavours of various countries from around the world have become a major feature of the catering economy, moreover, it has the ability to provide good services while price can remain reasonable, attracting entrepreneurs to compete. When the business volume of the industry increases and the self-created brand succeeds, it is easy to develop a franchise channel on its own, to develop transferable technologies, and to create greater business opportunities.

1.6.1 Motivation 1

Rummage a franchise model suitable for Taiwan's catering industry.

The current business model of enterprises has shifted from competition to cooperation. Based on reasons such as resource sharing and reducing competition, companies have developed a variety of cooperation modes. Franchising is one of the most popular cooperation modes (Shevchuk, 2021). From a theoretical point of view, the operation of the franchise system is a win-win business between the franchise headquarters and the franchisee. In practice, not all franchise systems are profitable without losing money (Jang & Park, 2019)..

Franchising and entrepreneurship are a partnership of benefit-sharing. The franchisee quickly obtains the operating know-how from the franchise headquarters, replicates its business model in a short time, and quickly enters the market with the product management technical support of the franchise headquarters, saving a lot of time for learning and exploring. The franchise headquarters can use the public's funds and manpower to quickly exhibit stores and collect the most real-time market information from franchisees. However, due to the

imperfect domestic franchise market, coupled with the laws and regulations related to franchising, which are scattered in different fields such as civil law, fair trade law, and trademark law, there is no special bill that can completely regulate it. Therefore, some immature chain systems began to quickly join in based on the successful experience of operating one or two companies. When the organisation is too large to control, the headquarters will allow the logistics supply to be out of balance. It is easy to produce the domino effect of malignant bankruptcy (Johnson, 2009).

According to a survey conducted by the Franchise Promotion Association, franchisees are generally dissatisfied with the support and guidance of the parent company. They either complain that the parent company provides too little guidance or complain that the parent company interferes too much. On the contrary, the parent company IS often dissatisfied with the results of the cooperation and implementation of the franchise's policies, that is, there are many problems in franchising that affect the franchise relationship (Matthes, et al., 2021). Therefore, how to strengthen the franchise relationship so that the franchisee generates trust, and then agrees with the cooperative relationship and is willing to continue cooperation. It is an important subject. In terms of academic aspects, although the past research on franchise industry management often focused on the perspective of alliance performance (Gassenheimer, Baucus and Baucus, 1996 cited in Colla, et al., 2020), it was less comprehensive than the key success of the franchise system. Factors to explore the research that affects the performance of the chain system. For this reason, it is one of the motivations for this research to fill in the gaps in this perspective in the past research.

In addition, due to the rapid development of the franchise industry, the management of franchise enterprises is one of the most important issues in modern business management. There are few franchise systems, and the headquarters and franchise stores are developing at the same time. Both sides are still beginners. The headquarters cannot provide mature market management techniques to franchisees, and the management-related knowledge is relatively insufficient compared with large-scale foreign chain businesses. Li (2001) pointed out that the management technology of the franchise system is becoming more mature, and the Know-how franchise is gradually established. However, compared with the United States and Japan, the franchise business in Taiwan has many creative ideas, but most of them lack systemic management Know-how. Therefore, proposing that the relevant research on improving the performance of chain operations should have improved practical value for the

practitioners, and it is also the second motivation for this research.

With the change of history, Taiwan's diet has absorbed foreign cuisines, including, Japanese and Western, etc., and has evolved into its own characteristics through continuous absorption and fusion. Zhang (2018) shows that there is a rapid growth of chain restaurants and exotic cuisine has also made Taiwan 's food culture more diverse and become a republic of world cuisine. In addition to domestic consumers, Taiwanese cuisine is well-known internationally. According to the "Report on the Investigation and Consumption of Tourists Coming to Taiwan by the Tourism Bureau of the Ministry of Transport in 2019", the main factors that have attracted tourists to Taiwan in recent years are gourmet food or speciality snacks, showing gourmet tourism. The development of Taiwan is also one of the factors influencing the number of restaurants and revenue growth in Taiwan's catering industry. In terms of the difficulties faced by the catering industry, it has experienced a slowdown in the number of employees. The number of employees and sales in recent years, indicates that the catering market has gradually entered a saturated state (TTR, 2020).

According to the results of the actual survey of the restaurant industry operation conducted by the Ministry of Economic Affairs in 2019, the current difficulties faced by the restaurant industry include "too high personnel costs", "high staff turnover" and "large fluctuations in food costs". Understanding how the restaurant industry controls cost and avoiding staff turnover are important keys to management. In recent years, basic wages have increased year by year, which has increased the operating pressure of the catering industry. The catering industry is a high labour-intensive and low-tech threshold industry. It is difficult to avoid the problem of personnel loss. In addition, due to the fluctuation of raw material prices, the cost of food ingredients has increased. How to control internal costs and reduce operating pressure is a problem faced by the industry. In addition to the need for restaurants to reduce internal operating pressure, the external competition pressure they face cannot be ignored (TTR, 2020).

In the food and beverage section, smaller food and beverage companies include lunch, snacks, etc. In addition to the price cut competition of the same industry, in recent years, there have been cross-border joint cooperation between different industry players and well-known food and beverage brands to share the opportunities in the affordable food and beverage market. For example, 7-11 and CoCo (ICHIBANYA) jointly launched a curry series

of meals; in addition, in the competition of large chain catering brands, due to the high acceptance of foreign cuisines by domestic people and the continuous increase in the number of tourists visiting Taiwan, the well-known foreign catering brands have since the beginning of the year, been competing to exhibit at the Taiwan Exhibition Store to drive the domestic catering business opportunities. Foreign traders have also acted as agents of catering brands. For example, Tailong Industrial Group has introduced Japanese famous pork chops brand Jijiwu to enter the domestic catering market, which has intensified domestic catering industry competition (TTR, 2020).

1.6.2 Motivation 2

Understand the performance management model of managers in the catering industry.

Based on the principle of separation of corporate ownership and management, and in the face of an increasingly competitive international environment, professional managers are appointed to improve corporate performance and competitiveness (Ilmi, Kustono & Sayekti, 2017). However, professional high-level managers can do their best to increase the value of the company; but they may also abuse the company's resources by using their powers, causing the company and its weak shareholders to suffer, resulting in the so-called agency problem (Tsai, Huang, Kuo and Kuo, 2006).

As for how to reduce agency problems, companies generally do so in two ways. One is to establish different types of corporate governance, such as directors and supervisors, independent directors and supervisors and shareholder meetings to supervise the exercise of managerial powers (Adnan, Hay & Staden, 2018). Whether it is appropriate or not; the other way is to give the manager the company's equity to incentivise the manager's to better perform his duties in the company, thereby creating the value of the company and achieving a win-win situation (Ceasar, 2021). Directors, shareholder meetings and other external supervision mechanisms are closely related to the company's operating performance, and the concentration of the manager's shareholding ratio is also closely related to the company's performance. Scholars at home and abroad have continuously conducted research on this related topic to understand the relationship between the ownership structure and operating performance (Alabdullah, 2018).

As far as the interest convergence theory is concerned (Lee, 2007), the manager's shareholding ratio has a positive relationship with company performance (Shan, Tang and Zhang, 2021). When the manager's shareholding ratio is higher, the goal is more consistent with the expectations of the company's shareholders, and there will be no self-interest and waste of company resources. This way, the company's value can be enhanced, and the shareholders' wishes can be achieved (Khan, Kaleem, He, Akram, Akram & Chen, 2017).

Jensen and Meckling (2019) first proposed that when the manager's shareholding ratio is very low, it is possible to use their power to improve their own utility, carry out unnecessary personal privileged consumption or choose the next best investment plan, while ignoring the interests of shareholders. Leland and Pyle (1977) proposed that when the company's performance is good and the future cash flow is expected to be large, managers may be the first to have this internal information and increase their shareholding ratio, but generally, investors cannot know the future cash flow with certainty (Hu, Du, and Zhang, 2020). Therefore, the manager's shareholding ratio represents information about the amount of future cash flow and is positively correlated with the company's expected value.

The Consolidation of Position Hypothesis points out that when the manager's shareholding ratio reaches a certain level, the shareholding ratio will have a negative relationship with company performance (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019). When the manager's shareholding ratio exceeds a certain ratio, the manager will only increase the shareholding ratio purely to consolidate his own management rights to fight against malicious mergers (Yin, Tung and Shen, 2014). Therefore, the self-interest situation will worsen with the concentration of ownership, meaning the value of the company has been damaged, and shareholder funds have been misappropriated in disguised form.

Ruback (1983) believes that when equity is concentrated in managers, to consolidate their powers and private interests, managers may choose solutions that are unfavourable to shareholders and reduce the value of the company. In addition, from the perspective of hostile takeover, Stulz (1988) believes that when managers hold a high proportion of shares, to protect their own rights and interests, they often oppose equity acquisitions that are beneficial to the company. Generally, the stock price of the acquired company will rise, but managers with a high proportion of shares oppose the acquisition, resulting in a low completion rate of acquisitions, which in turn reduces the value of the company (Ray, 2020).

As for the increase in manager's shareholding ratio, the most direct impact on the benefit of managers is the increase in dividend income, which encourages them to be more committed to improving the value of the company and reducing their private expenses, reducing the manager's and agency issues between shareholders (Panda and Leepsa, 2017). However, the increase in dividend payments will have a negative impact on the company's future investment funds budget, which may reduce the company's growth ability and future potential value. Once the ownership is concentrated, there will be potential incentives to increase the distribution of dividends (Feng, Chen and Tang, 2018).

Franchising has become a popular form of global business in many industries. Franchising is a form of permission by the main office of the company, franchisers (franchisees) to grant independent entity, the franchiser prescribed way of doing business right (Czinkota, et al., 2003 cited in Katsikeas, 2003)). This form of business has received widespread attention in academia, and SMEs have used this approach to expand their business for more than 100 years. Franchising has become a popular way of selling products internationally in Australia, Spain and newly industrialised countries, while international franchising remains one of the most popular distribution channels for US export products (Rosado-Serrano, et al., 2018). In the catering industry, what significant factors show how managerial ownership is related to the performance of the business are, as well as how the level relationship between franchising and managerial ownership influences success.

1.7 Expected Contributions

It is recommended to follow up the research of the catering franchise industry, especially the internal management of ownership enterprises, to have a deeper understanding of the research, provide different perspectives, and allow operators to consider management strategies. This research can make up for the deficiencies in this field. When understanding the shareholding structure of Taiwan's catering industry, whether the manager's shareholding ratio affects the company's actual operating performance.

In addition, identifying whether the level of directors' shareholding affects the company's business decisions has a profound impact on the company's future development. When a corporation holds a high proportion of shares, it will affect investors' judgement on the company's stock price. For example, a company with a good image and a high stock price

has shares in this catering company; the general public investors would expect the performance of this catering company to improve. This is a factor that belongs to the expected psychology of investors and can be explored in future research. This researcher expects that the high proportion of managerial family shareholdings will directly affect the company's operating performance. In addition, the high shareholding ratio of the director is positively correlated with ROA or franchise degree.

1.7.1 Academic Contributions

In the academic contributions part, it has complementary effect toward Rhou, et. al (2019) research "Does managerial ownership influence franchising in restaurant companies?". The franchise level related to management ownership has reached the optimal level, which means that the management shareholder can improve the company's operating performance by setting company goals and designing effective incentive contracts or bonus. According to (Wang & Chiang, 2020) research pointed out the influence of shareholding ratio on the company's operating performance. The shareholder structure is measured by foreign capital shareholdings, ROC government agencies shareholdings, ROC financial institutions shareholdings, major shareholdings, and directors' shareholdings. Company performance is measured by ROA and ROE (Merendino and Melville, 2019).

The results show that the proportion of foreign shares, the proportion of shares held by financial institutions in the Republic of China, and the proportion of shares held by directors are positively correlated with the company's performance, and all have reached a significant level. The main shareholding ratio is positively correlated with ROA and ROE (Wang & Chiang, 2020). This research is to explore the empirical model of the level of franchising and managerial ownership in the catering industry, which helps to strengthen the connotation of the theory.

1.7.2 Professional Practice

In industry aspect and government aspect, some suggestions and contributions respectively will be provided, which will help the future operation of the catering industry. To provide to investors currently operating or about to invest into the catering industry, the relevant statistics on the catering industry and management ownership. Additionally, providing to

relevant government agencies for the duty advice of the chain industry and labour regulations to protect the basic rights of both sides.

Industry aspect

- Provide advice for the catering industry about the strategies of managerial ownership.
- Advise the contract of franchising business development.

In 2018, the catering industry entered an era of huge profits, and the profit-making model of the catering industry is undergoing changes, the Internet innovation has changed the catering industry in particular. "Big data", "smart dining" and "black technology" have become industry keywords (KKnews, 2018). Consumers will no longer only value "convenience" but also "quality". "Many consumers who are busy and frequent eat out actually want to eat at home. This research predict that this group of people will rise, and therefore improve the high-quality speed scratch program¹, as well as ready-to-eat meals with restaurant standards demanded (MintelPressTeam, 2018).

Government aspect

- Based on social responsibility, the government could offer a policy of co-work with the companies, such as Tax deduction and so on. It would be good for the community.

Overall, the distribution of Taiwan retailers and catering companies in the global market, chain and brand are the two keys. In the future, Taiwan companies must think about how to further optimize their competitiveness under the basic strategy of chain brands, and successfully enter the huge global market. In terms of franchise chain system, in addition to unilateral evaluation, whether a complete and sound chain system is also one of the reasons that affects the franchise performance of franchisees, Clarkin & Swavely (2006) pointed out that research has confirmed that the cooperative relationship plays a very important role in the chain system, and the relationship between the franchise headquarters and franchisees has an impact on the franchise performance (Clarkin & Swavely, 2006).

1.8 The structure of this thesis

This article is divided into seven chapters. These are outlined in the following paragraphs.

In Chapter one, it mainly explains the research background, the problem statement, research topic, research focus. With the change of history and goals, research motivation, research limitations and expected contributions. Taiwan's diet has absorbed foreign cuisines, including, Japanese and Western, etc., and has evolved into its own characteristics through continuous absorption and fusion. Zhang (2018) shows that there is a rapid growth of chain restaurants and exotic cuisine has also made Taiwan's food culture more diverse and become a republic of world cuisine. In addition to domestic consumers, Taiwanese cuisine is well-known internationally. According to the "Report on the Investigation and Consumption of Tourists Coming to Taiwan by the Tourism Bureau of the Ministry of Transport in 2019", the main factors that have attracted tourists to Taiwan in recent years are gourmet food or speciality snacks, showing gourmet tourism. The development of Taiwan is also one of the factors influencing the number of restaurants and revenue growth in Taiwan's catering industry. In terms of the difficulties faced by the catering industry, it has experienced a slowdown in the number of employees. The number of employees and sales in recent years, indicates that the catering market has gradually entered a saturated state (TTR, 2020).

Chapter Two is the literature review. It first mentions the historical evolution and then explains the definitions of franchise. Different countries and different scholars have different definitions of franchise. Then I draw the correlation diagram flow based on the related theories of franchise and explain the correlation between different theories. There is also mention of social responsibility, which is divided into franchisee social responsibility and corporate social responsibility. The most relevant theory to franchise is agency theory and transaction costs theory. Many research reports and papers mention these two theories at the same time. Performance appraisal can find out the level of the company's operations. Employees or branches with shares or dividends (or bonus) will have a higher and vice versa. In a franchise enterprise, it is difficult for the enterprise to judge whether the actual behaviour of the franchisee meets the expectations of the franchise enterprise (Bercovit, 2004). In Chapter 2 especially is discussed the theory related to franchising, the relevant theoretical relationship diagram is shown with Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee. First,

agency theory and brand resonance perform an important role in this study and are discussed separately in separate sections. Second, other related theories are discussed from the perspective of franchiser, franchisee and both sides, and finally a summary is made.

Chapter three, franchise system of catering, classification of chain franchise system, such as American franchise system, and Japanese franchise system, as well as find out the advantages and disadvantages of chain types (Siebert, 2015). The United States is the first way to join in the world. It uses replication to replicate the successful operating mechanism to another city, and the head office provides management systems, raw materials, etc. Because Taiwan has just started to adopt the Japanese franchise system, it gradually understands the different franchise-related systems and operating modes, and then improves it. Correspondingly, in this chapter pinpoints the benefits and weaknesses of the franchise system. Also, it has been learned about the global current catering status of franchise and development discussing Chain franchise management mechanism, and explain about brand authorisation, franchise's trust, and loyalty to franchise system. The relationship between brand authorisation and franchisee commitment and loyalty. The company's performance achievement strategy method. The operation of the relevant franchise has an impact on the industry, society, and economy. However, Chapter 3 will continue to discuss the system and functions of franchising. According to the rules and regulations of franchising in different countries, the responsibilities and obligations that need to be borne are different. This research was conducted during the covid-19 period. Although the data was before the epidemic period, there were slight changes from the current situation, and there were also substantial changes in operation and management. Therefore, crisis management was specially added to the third chapter for discussion and explained it. Moreover, this chapter will deliberate the current situation after the epidemic and re-planning the company's development strategy, and finally a summary of all franchise theories.

Chapter four, explains the research methodology, including the research design, hypotheses development, variables definition (dependent variables in detection models, measurement of independent variables, and the sign of variables), data collection, sample selection, research approach, statistical analysis, and chapter summary. This paper mainly discusses the correlation between corporate governance and operating performance in Taiwan's catering industry. Taking 28 domestic listed catering companies from 2016 to 2020 as a sample, the least squares method was used to explore the possible impact of ownership structure and

financial factors on the company. The analysis process is divided into four parts. The first part is to examine the narrative statistics of each variable to observe the distribution characteristics; manager (including director status) shareholding ratio, manager (including relatives) shareholding ratio, director shareholding ratio and company shareholding ratio are used as explanatory variables. The second part is size (company size), Lev (debt ratio), MTB (market to book price), growth (sales growth rate), InvRate (investment rate), FCF (free cash flow), CapInt (capital intensity) and OMRate (operating profitability ratio) as control variables in the regression equation to observe the relationship between different performance variables and explanatory variables. The third part is to convert the performance variables in the regression into the DOF variable of the connection rate and explore whether the DOF will be affected by the explanatory variables. The fourth part is to explore whether the level of insider ownership will interfere with the results of the regression analysis and implement the above two parts of the regression analysis.

Chapter five, empirical analysis, includes the constructs used in the analysis, data analysis and summary. This section is mainly divided into two parts. The first part first analyses the distribution of insider ownership ratios during the sampling period, and then briefly introduces the characteristics of each variable in this study. Variables will be used for initial statistical analysis. Use SPSS statistical software to conduct model verification analysis, such as collinearity verification, autocorrelation verification, regression analysis, etc. on the sample data, understand the characteristics and distribution of the data, and obtain the statistical relationship between various variables and business performance. The second part is to conduct collinearity test and independence test on the residual project in Chapter 4 mentioned in the explanatory variables. When the independent variables in a regression model overlap linearly, it is difficult to distinguish the impact of each variable on the variable because the changes in these variables are highly correlated. This research used correlation coefficient analysis and variance inflation factor (VIF) as criteria to determine whether the independent variables have collinearity. To prevent the results produced by the regression model from being biased, the residual terms in the regression model are required to be non-autocorrelated and randomly distributed. This study uses the DW value as the criterion for judging whether there is autocorrelation between variables.

Chapter six, the conclusion, the level of investigations in catering industry, summary of main findings practical and theoretical implications of findings, significance of contributions, study

limitations, suggestions for future research and summary. Using ROA and earnings per share (EPS) as performance indicators, this research explore the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms, including the shareholding ratio of internal managers (with director status), manager shareholding ratio and company operating performance. Manager ownership level (MHD), empirical results show that the level of manager ownership does have a certain impact on company performance. Under managers with relative holdings (MRHD), there is a collinearity problem with MRHD. The regression analysis results have a significant impact on ROA and DOF but have no significant impact on earnings per share. Managers (MO) with director status, empirical results show that the shareholding ratio of managers with shareholder status has a specific and obvious impact on company performance, because the catering sector is a service industry, and the contribution of shareholders with director status to the company, there has also been an increase. Corporate shareholding degree (CHD), CHD is positively related to company operating performance. Institutional investors can monitor companies more professionally and effectively than small investors and increase company value.

1.9 The research framework flow chart

The figure 2 shows the progress of this research framework, from research background and motivation to conclusions.

Figure 2 The research framework flow chart

Source from: author

1.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter explains the background of the study, the problem statement and research aim and objectives. Taiwan's franchise system is very complete and in line with the local culture in the world. Many franchisees want to enter the industry but do not know how to. They can choose to enter a franchise system and save a lot of cost and time. Almost all the brands developed can be directly profitable. Of course, choosing a franchiser is very important, and location and operator's philosophy are also very important considerations. The motivation for the research is that the author is engaged in the catering industry, hoping to develop their own franchise brand through this research, and achieve the integration of academic and practice.

In terms of research limitations, much data cannot be directly obtained. It is necessary to purchase the database through different agencies, the Census and Statistics Department or China Credit Information Service Ltd., cross-comparative analysis, and obtain secondary data before they can be directly used in SPSS software analysis. In addition, there are contributions, providing academic and practical contributions. In terms of academic contributions, it can be understood the status of the franchise industry development and performance and provide innovative management models and feasible suggestions in management. In terms of practical contribution, first, for franchisee that will join the franchise industry, this research can provide them with reference materials when choosing franchise brands; second, provide the existing franchiser effective management model to provide best corporate performance.

Chapter 2- Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter evaluates the following theories, 1. Agency theory and 2. Brand resonance. In the franchise business, Agency theory is one of the theories frequently mentioned in many literatures. The reason wherefore the theory of Brand Resonance is used is that when the brand is outstanding and well-known, franchisees will be attracted to join the brand because they believe that investing in the company's brand can rapidly grow the turnover and reduce the uncertainty in the start-up period. Both theories will be explained in detail in chapter 2.4.2 and chapter 2.4.3, in figure 4 theoretical underpinning between franchise and franchisee, shows their relationship with how the correspond theories to be linked. Therefore, between both side of franchiser and franchisee, in chapter 2.4.4 also be discussed the following theories, 1. Transaction cost theory, 2. Social responsibility, 3. Resource dependence theory and Resource Scarcity theory, 4. Stewardship theory and Stakeholder theory, 5. Relational contract theory. The reason these theories have been selected is that all of theories related to franchise business, such as transaction cost, resource dependence and scarcity, if the products on the market are so popular, but the material of products might have patented or specialized sales channels which are not easily to get. Moreover, the social responsibility will affect brand image. Managerial ownership part included that the theories are stewardship theory and stakeholder theory, For the reason that this research need to more understand the connection between the shareholdings of managers and directors in the franchise business and bring in relational contract theory to control the responsibilities of the two parties, these will be discussed in this chapter. Those theories all are important to consider in the context of this study, not only Taiwan catering business, but also it can apply to other industries. The aim of this chapter is to review franchise history and its relative theories.

The manager responsible for the operation of the enterprise and the shareholders who provide the source of corporate funds have different levels of access to relevant information within the enterprise and the difficulty of obtaining information, resulting in information asymmetry. One of the main problems in the relationship between managers or directors as agents is also the focus of corporate governance. Therefore, this chapter first briefly discusses the agency problem, and then conducts in-depth research on the related literature on the relationship between internal manager stock ownership and performance. (Hao, 2022)

The company's governance issues have a certain degree of relationship between whether the manager is a major shareholder of the company, and the composition of the board of directors. The soundness of the accounting system also has a significant impact on the company's operations. Therefore, the company's internal board of directors' supervision mechanism has a significant impact on the company's operating performance. The impact of this research is a matter of great concern to this study, and the relevant literature has also been sorted out. Finally, this chapter discusses the related literature on agency issues and the shareholding of legal entities.

Nowadays, chain restaurants and exotic cuisines are growing rapidly, creating differentiated market expansion. Food is the easiest way for ordinary people to accept foreign cultures. Taiwan, which was famous for its food culture in the past, has also gradually integrated into the food culture around the world. The degree of internationalisation is quite high, and exotic dishes such as Japanese, Spanish or Italian cuisine. are already acceptable to ordinary people. At first, the main force of Taiwanese restaurants was mainly based on high-cost performance.

From the foundry and trade society to the management and replication capabilities of restaurant operators, through purchasing technology and systematic management, the original foreign chain catering menu has been improved again, resulting in many successful chain catering brands such as Wowprime, Wacheng, etc. However, the vigorous growth of Taiwan's restaurant chain has also caused a lot of replication and high homogeneity. The immediate problem for enterprises is how to create unique and special experiences. The restaurant industry, like the clothing industry, must add more diversity. Only popular elements can emerge in the fiercely competitive catering market (Zheng, 2018).

2.2 Historical Review of Franchise

The United States is the birthplace of franchise operations worldwide. After the Second World War, the US government provided employment for veterans who had no skills and no funds, so they jointly created a business model of authorisation to join the enterprise (IFA, 2019). The company headquarters provides the know-how, permits trademark use rights and gives the business guidance, the franchise owner receives technical compensation, and the government provides entrepreneurship financing to promote the rapid growth of franchise chains.

Chain stores refer to many small-scale, decentralised retail stores of the same brand operating with similar products and services. Under the organisational leadership of the headquarters, they adopt a common operating policy and consistent marketing actions and implement an organic combination of centralised procurement and decentralised sales. It is a consortium that achieves economies of scale through standardised operations. In the early stage, it was an organisation composed of some stores with the same attributes because of price competition. With unified procurement reducing costs, this achieved the purpose of bulk purchase cost savings.

Gillis et al, (2020) believe that the study of alliance management capabilities is expected to determine the performance enhancement capabilities of franchisees and franchisees in effective collation (Gillis, et al., 2020). Franchisees are also often responsible for selecting other franchisees, providing training, coordinating activities with local franchisees, monitoring performance, and implementing franchisee strategies (Shane, 1998).

Franchising is an inimitable business with a unique history. There were hundreds of famines in the Middle Ages, especially in Europe, where the plague of the Black Death on the continent killed more than a third of the population in the region. Working class people often stage violent uprisings, when they do not feel that their wages are reasonable. Serious religious conflicts have caused dissatisfaction (Libava, 2020). Franchise operations developed during this period, and some local governments granted senior church officials licenses to maintain order and assess taxation. Medieval courts granted these people the right to control the market and carry out business-related activities. In the colonial period, local sovereigns / lords would authorise individuals to hold markets, operate local ferries, host

fairs, and even hunt on their land. This concept extended to the king, who would grant franchise rights for different types of business activities. In the 1880s, Isaac Singer who was the first to obtain a practical and versatile sewing machine patent also asked the licensee to teach consumers how to use the machine they just bought. This arrangement is a win-win situation. It meant, partners benefited from licensing fees, which allowed them to fund more manufacturing. At the turn of the century, from 1896, one of these new distribution methods was in automobile distribution. After this saw the creation of the food franchise business. In the 1960s, McDonald's had 5000 restaurants up and running. Today, they have 34,000 restaurants open. (Libava, 2020)

Table 1 Franchise operations historical period

Period	Franchise Model	Companies
The Middle Ages	These initial franchisees paid royalties to the lord in exchange for "protection", which was essentially considered a monopoly on commercial enterprises.	Some local governments granted senior church officials licenses to maintain order and assess taxes. Over time, the regulations governing these first franchisees have become part of European common law.
The Colonial Period	Once a colony was established, the founders could obtain the protection of the "crown" in exchange for taxes or royalties.	Local sovereigns / lords would authorise individuals to hold markets, operate local ferries, host fairs, and even hunt on their land. This concept extends to the king, who will grant franchise rights for different types of business activities.
The 1840s	Franchisees needed to pay for the right to use the trade name	SPATEN was a beer brewery in Germany. He granted certain local taverns the right to sell beer. Interestingly, the pub owner must use the brand name of the beer brewer. .
The 1880s	Licensing Arrangements	Isaac Singer was the founder of IM Singer & Company, and his partners would find merchants interested in having the right to sell Singer sewing machines in specific geographic areas. Once they found out that they wanted to become a party to the licensee, they would charge them a pre-sale fee- a license fee to sell the machine. The licensee had his own business and sold the products most families want.
The 1896	One of those new distribution methods was the automobile dealership.	William Metzger established and opened the first independent car dealership in Detroit, Michigan. HO Kohler. He opened the first car dealership in Pennsylvania. He sold Winton cars. Henry Ford and other businessmen who make cars now had distribution systems. Restaurants began to pop up all over the place, especially near all newly paved roads. Eventually, the food franchise began to open
The 1960s	Contribution to franchise is related to uniformity and cleanliness	The McDonald's franchise store in Beaufort, South Carolina would have basically the same menu items and might be as clean as the McDonald's franchise store in Portland, Oregon.

Source from: MARIO L. HERMAN- *The Franchisee's Lawyer* (Mherman, 2021)

2.3 Definitions of Franchise

Franchise refers to a chain operation method in which many individual store operators operate the same brand chain stores under the guidance of the headquarters; through this operation method, individual operators can quickly acquire operating knowledge and reduce the time for doing own research, and, in this way, corporate headquarters can quickly expand their business territory.

The English word "Franchise" originated from the old French word "franc", meaning free from servitude. Later, the explanation in English contained the meaning of privileges granted by the king. Since its evolution, it can be interpreted as a right granted by the head office to franchisees, exempting them from the status of salaried employees and providing opportunities for self-employment. The so-called franchise is defined by the Japan Franchise Association (JFA) as: "The head office and the franchisee have signed a franchise agreement, and have their own trade names, trademarks, and other signs that symbolise business and Know-how. Authorise the other party to sell uniform products or provide the same service under a unified corporate image; after the franchisee obtains the above full support, the same must pay a certain amount of remuneration to the franchise head office and provide guidance and assistance in the head office a kind of continuity relationship for operating its business under the circumstances."

In addition, the International Franchise Association (IFA) pointed out that franchising refers to the contractual relationship between the headquarters and the franchisee. According to the contract, the headquarters must have two or more similar stores. The headquarters of the chain system can provide warehousing and procurement., Advertising and marketing strategies, and reduce costs with a high degree of bargaining power to form economies of scale. At the same time, it also helps each chain store's promotional activities Promotion, Product, Pricing, Channel Place, etc., and follows a consistent business strategy.

In addition, scholars emphasise the relationship between headquarters and franchisees from the perspective of management characteristics. Schewe and Smith (1983) defined franchise as a retail organisation composed of two or more units that belong to the same owner. All units have the same or similar goods or services, similar designs and decorations, and unified procurement in their operations. Justis and Judd (1989 cited in Ramírez-Hurtado, et al., 2022)

believes that chain operation is a kind of headquarters with patented brands, services, and technology, authorised to individual franchisees to operate in various regions, provide services or products, and return royalties to the headquarters, abide by rules, and ensure service quality. Type of business. Lin (1990) advocated that franchise refers to two or more stores with the same business nature, adopting the same store name, signboard, and decoration, and having a central unit to direct their actions.

Kotler (1991) defines franchise as a retail store that owns or controls two or more sales locations, and these retail stores sell the same products as much as possible, purchase and sell uniformly, and create consistent characteristics in store decoration. Hallak, et al. (1992) define franchise as: many retail units under the same ownership, at the same time centralised purchasing and decision-making behaviour.

Li (1998) believes that franchising should have the following four requirements: (1) Consistent business philosophy: customer service, work values, and the company's spiritual culture are carefully selected and educated to ensure that all business concepts are consistent. Connected to the heart. (2) Corporate identity (CIS) is consistent: the chain's business philosophy is the same, coupled with the appearance of packaging, such as signs, decorations, shopping bags, business cards and other identification objects, slogans, ceremonies, inside and outside everything can be seen, and feel is consistent. (3) Commodity and service consistency: The merchandise display, price, promotion, etc. of the store are consistent with the services provided; no matter which store is the same, consumers will have the same feeling when they go to anyone. (4) Consistent management system: The chain industry emphasises standardisation, consistency, and management systems are the main tools to maintain standardisation. Therefore, a standardised operation management system must be established; the entire chain system is managed by the organisation, the rule of law, rather than the rule of individuals and people.

Different organizations have similar definitions of franchise. According to the definition of management characteristics views, their differences can be clearly distinguished from Table 2. The American International Chain Association and the Japan Franchise Association believe that the headquarters provides franchisees with licensing privileges and assistance in organizing training, procurement, management, etc.; in contrast, the franchisee should pay fees to the headquarters, a continuing relationship between the chain headquarters and

franchisees. The U.S. Bureau of Industry and Commerce supposes that the definition of franchise refers to operating two or more stores with the same business nature and belonging to the same capital, managing their merchandise policies, and forming a corporate organization.

Consequently, in the light of some scholars' definitions of franchising, Schewe and Smith (1983), Kotler (1991) and Lin (1990) mentioned that own or control two or more stores, sell the same products, purchase goods uniformly, and store the same storefronts., the decoration is consistent and distinctive. Justis and Judd (1989 cited in Ramírez-Hurtado, et al., 2022) reputed that franchisees are the type of enterprise that operates in various regions, provides services or products, and returns royalties to the headquarters, abides by rules, and ensures service quality.

Hallak, et al. (1992) deemed that many retail units under the same ownership conduct centralized purchasing and decision-making activities simultaneously. Justis and Judd (1989 cited in Ramírez-Hurtado, et al., 2022) and Li (1998) both accounted that consistent business philosophy, consistent corporate identity, consistent products and services, and consistent management systems. The type of enterprise that provides services or products and returns royalties to the headquarters, abides by rules, and ensures service quality. Lumen dialogued the franchise definition in *Boundless Business*. Table 2 shows the academics and organisations of vary countries about definition in franchise (Lumen, 2020).

Table 2 Definition of franchise business-based on management characteristics

Year	Academics and Organisations	Definition in Franchise
1959	International Franchise Association (IFA)	The chain system is an ongoing relationship between the head office and franchisees. The head office grants the other party a license, privileges to enable it to operate; and assists in its organisation, training, procurement, and management
1972	Japanese Franchise Association (JFA)	Franchise stores are a kind of contract between Franchiser and Franchisee. The head office and the franchisee enter a contract to grant their own shop number, trademark, and other things that are sufficient to symbolise business and know-how for business, so that they can sell their products under the same corporate image. At the same time, it is relatively necessary to pay a certain price (amount) to the head office. Under the guidance and assistance of the head office, it is a continuous relationship for operating the business.

1973	Carman	A chain refers to two or more stores with the same operating nature, using the same store name, signboard, and decoration, and having a central unit to command its operations, such as unified advertising and unified purchase.
1983	Schewe & Smit	A chain store is made up of two or more units, which belong to the same owner and own a retail organisation. Each unit has the same or similar goods or services, similar design and decoration, and unified procurement
1986	U.S. Bureau of Industry and Commerce	Operating two or more retail stores, with the same business nature, belong to the same capital, and manage their commodity policies and form a corporate organisation. (Bureau , 1986)
1988	Stern & ElAnsary	A chain is two or more retail bases, with centralised ownership, control, and management, and must have store similarity. They also believe that the chain system must have the following four characteristics: (1) centralised ownership or control; (2) centralised management; (3) similarity of stores; (4) two or more retail bases.
1989	Berman & Evans	Chain stores are numerous retail units under the same ownership, and they have centralised purchasing and decision-making behaviours.
1989	Justis and Judd	The franchisee is a type of enterprise that operates in various regions, provides services or products, and repays royalties to the headquarters, abides by rules, and ensures service quality.
1990	Lin Juanjuan	Two or more stores with the same business nature adopt the same store name, signboard and decoration, and the central unit will uniformly direct their actions.
1991	Kotler	Retail stores that own or control two or more sales locations, and these retail stores sell the same products as much as possible, purchase and sell uniformly, and create consistent characteristics in store decoration.
1992	Hallak, et al.	Many retail units under the same ownership have centralised purchasing and decision-making activities at the same time.
1998	Li Xingmo	Consistent business philosophy, consistent corporate identification, consistent commodity services, and consistent management systems.
2000	Kotler	A chain store is a retail store that owns or controls two or more retail bases, and these retail stores sell the same product line, uniform purchase and sales, and try to create consistent features in store decoration
2004	Combs, J. G., Michael, S. C., & Castrogiovanni, G. J.	A franchise is a form of business in which a company (i.e. the franchisee) enters into a long-term contractual agreement with another company (i.e. the franchiser) to sell products or services in a brand name and business practice specific to the franchiser. In exchange for income, royalties and/or expenses.

2004	Deontological European Code of Honour	A franchise is a system for selling goods, selling and/or applying technology. It is based on an independent and financially autonomous corporate body, a close and continuous cooperation between franchisers and their individual franchisees.
2005	Watson et al.	Franchising is a business system in which franchisers allow franchisee to use pre-established successful brands and business resources in exchange for franchisees paying royalties to franchisers.
2008	Verbieren, S., Cools, M., & Van den Abbeele, A.	The franchiser grants him the right and gives them the obligation to develop the business according to the business philosophy. Therefore, the franchisee pays the franchiser an initial franchise fee, periodic royalties and/or advertising fees. In return the franchiser grants the right for the use of their brand names, trademarks, know-how, commercial and technical methods, operating procedures and other industrial or intellectual property rights. In addition, the franchisee receives support from the franchiser for commercial and technical assistance. All of this occurred during the written franchise contract between the parties for this purpose
2011	Barthélemy Combs, et al.	In many service and retail industries, franchising is one of the important corporate growth strategies because of the way in which two very different types of entrepreneurs work together.
2019	Jang & Park	Franchising is defined as an arrangement in which the ownership of a good, process or service permits others (franchisee) to use it to exchange certain payments.
2021	Sisca Ferawati Burhanuddin	Franchising is an agreement involving two or more individuals, which forms an agreement involving the law as the legal basis, and the franchising activities provide significant benefits to the actual operator. (Burhanuddin, 2021)
2022	Sashi, C. M., & Brynildsen, G.	In Franchise network aspect, franchising is an effort to increase brand value by connecting and interacting with existing and potential customers on social media platforms, benefiting franchisors as well as franchisees in the franchise network, and enhancing customer-to-customer interaction by stimulating customer-to-customer, word-of-mouth communication WOM), to build franchisee relationships, communication and co-creation of value in social media networks (Sashi & Brynildsen, 2022).

Source from: *LumenBoundless Business (Lumen, 2020)*.

The definition of chain industry based on the number of franchisees. Table 3 shows the difference in definition of a franchise operation based on minimum number of chain stores.

Table 3 The definition of chain industry based on the number of franchisees.

Academy or scholar	Minimum of chain stores
Kotler (1991)	Over 2
Carman & Keneth	2
Stern & E1-Anary (1998)	2
U.S. Department of Commerce Business Census Bureau	2
Chief Accounting Office of the Executive council	2
Statistics Canada	7
Taiwan Chain and Franchise Association	7
American International Franchise Association	10
International Franchise Association	10
Japan Franchise Chain Association (JFA)	10
Japan Distribution Economy Research Institute	10

Source from: Kainan University (CHUANG, 2009)

A franchise is a form of business in which a company (i.e. the franchisee) enters into a long-term contractual agreement with another company (i.e. the franchiser) to sell products or services in a brand name and business practice specific to the franchiser. In exchange for income, royalties and/or expenses (Combs, Michael and Castrogiovanni, 2004). Oxenfeldt and Kelly (1968) claimed that the main factor behind franchising is the availability of resources needed to expand the system, such as financial, HR, and IT that franchisees may have difficulty controlling. Once the franchise company has grown to a certain extent, firstly, it has sufficient cash; secondly, it has the ability to recruit and train enough managers; thirdly, it has developed sufficient assets and local market expertise. However, franchise is a growth strategy for the franchiser. Hence, franchising is seen as a temporary phenomenon in the life cycle of the franchiser organisation (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996).

Watson et al. (2005) stated that franchising is a business system in which franchisers allow franchisee to use pre-established successful brands and business resources in exchange for franchisees paying royalties to franchisers. Academically, franchising is defined as an arrangement in which the owner of a goods, process, or service permits others (franchisee) to use it to exchange certain payments" (Jang & Park, 2019). For the owner it is a growth strategy, while for the franchisee it is a risk mitigation strategy. Indeed, franchising is a form of business designed to create mutual benefits (Jang & Park, 2019). Usually through franchising, initial economic support can be obtained and designed as a way of obtaining funds (Caves & Murphy, 1976 cited in Scott, 1995). Though, for this proposition, Rubin (1978)

subsequently challenged this position as inconsistent with portfolio theory for the reason that of the greater risk is associated with owning one outlet rather than shares in a portfolio of outlets (Rubin, 1978). Under the Deontological European Code of Honour (2004), a franchise is a system for selling goods, and selling and/or applying technology. It is based on an independent and financially autonomous corporate body, a close and continuous cooperation between franchisers and their separate franchisees. Therefore, the franchiser permits them the right and gives them the responsibility to develop the business according to the business philosophy.

Therefore, the franchisee pays the franchiser an initial franchise fee, periodic royalties and/or advertising fees. In return, the franchiser grants the right to use its brand name, trademark, know-how, commercial and technical methods, operating procedures, and other industrial or intellectual property rights (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019). In addition, the franchisee receives support from the franchiser for commercial and technical assistance. All of this is agreed in the written franchise contract between the parties for this purpose (Verbieren, et al., 2008). Barthélemy (2011) and Combs, et al. (2011) also declared that in many service and retail industries, franchising is one of the important corporate growth strategies because of the way in which two very different types of entrepreneurs work together (Gills, Combs, and Yin, 2018).

One is the franchiser, who has developed a new business model and opportunity and has negated the risks to take advantage of it. The second is the entrepreneur/ franchisee who buys the franchiser's right to copy the franchiser business model and take advantage of opportunities in the new geographic market. The franchiser typically provides a full range of services, such as training, product offerings, and marketing programs. In return, the franchisee pays prepaid fees, continues royalties, and agrees to comply with the franchiser's guidelines. One of the papers proposes a sustainable franchiser-franchisee relationship model (SFFR) that supports the "franchise win-win" theory (Jang, et al., 2019). Under some conditions, relationship quality is an important part of a healthy relationship, including sustainable franchisers and licenses. The three core components of a person's relationship (i.e., satisfaction, trust, and commitment), and the antecedents and consequences of the relationship. Studies have shown that franchisees are willing to continue their current franchise business only if they are satisfied with the franchiser's fairness, autonomy, formality, and support (Jang & Park, 2019).

The business of franchising is a type of company strategy, the branch might have few percentages of stock or share, some might not. Many theories of franchising are relevant with managerial ownership, especially, this study will focus on the brand resonance within the restaurant industry. Agency theory is the main theory in franchising research, as it is about the authorisation system for new franchisee. Managerial ownership is relevant with the performance management, if the manager of franchisee has managerial ownership, the branch performance usually is better than without. Resource scarcity theory is often due to franchisers maintaining knowledge and business secrecy making it difficult to find alternatives. The cost control is very important for business profit, so the transaction costs theory shows bulk purchases to reduce costs. The relational contract theory is supporting behaviour between franchisers and franchisees.

The brand resonance will attractive the franchisee but still needs both sides of them (franchiser and franchisees) to maintain the brand, as name brand citizenship behaviour, it will create a brand community. FSR (Franchiser Social Responsibility) and CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) are similar for social responsibility work. Finally, the performance measurement can investigate the level of franchising and managerial ownership within the restaurant industry.

2.4 Theories Discussion of Franchise

2.4.1 Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee

This chapter shows that Agency theory and Brand resonance theory is one of the most important theories. this figure 3 shows the theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee. In the Franchiser side, Brand resonance theory is their main theories base discussion, also they have a right to authorized use and cost advantage, with lower purchasing price advantage. In the franchisee side, Agency theory is their main theories base discussion. because they have a lack of resources knowledge, so they join the franchise system. Moreover, franchisee may consider the knowledge about employee dividend and performance management. Within both side of theories base are transaction cost, social responsibility, resource dependence and scarcity, stewardship and stakeholder theory, and relational contact. Co-marketing can create a win-win situation for both.

Figure 3 Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee

Source from: author

2.4.2 Agency theory

The agency problem arises from the inconsistency in the interests pursued by the managers and shareholders, or between shareholders and creditors. In the absence of agency problems, the main purpose of the company owner is to pursue profit to maximise the market value of the company, or to pursue cost minimization. In these situations, the company's operating performance is consistent with the shareholders' interests, so there is no dispute at all. Therefore, to measure agency costs, it must be started from the face-to-face discussion of the ownership form and management structure. In the original agency theory of Jensen and Meckling (2019), the definition of zero agency cost is that the ownership and management rights of a company belong to only one person. After Jensen and Meckling (2019) put forward the agency theory, many scholars began to devote themselves to the discussion of agency problems and related solutions. But when managers hold less than 100% of the equity, shareholders will incur agency costs due to manager laziness or privileged consumption. Because managers will transfer this loss to other small shareholders who have no right to operate.

Since the ownership of non-public listed companies with zero agency costs is entirely owned by managers, Jensen and Meckling's example of zero agency costs cannot be applied to these publicly listed companies. However, the management style of contemporary enterprises is mainly the separation of the company's ownership and management. Therefore, the agency problem has arisen. At the same time, Jensen and Meckling believe that the agency relationship is a kind of contract, which includes the power to give the agent certain decisions, and the agent can get a certain amount of remuneration in performing these activities, but in a market with incomplete information, the contract is drawn up. The information and information possessed by the two parties are asymmetrical. Each party seeks to maximise utility. Therefore, the agent does not necessarily take the principal's best interests as the criterion for his actions. This applies to the company's shareholders and managers.

Agency theorists believe that franchising reflects the tendency to hand over positions to store managers when monitoring costs are high so that the interests of franchisees are consistent with the interests of franchisers (Brickley & Dark, 1987 cited in O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996). According to this view, it is not expected to turn to the wholly owned company chain but has

always been a preference for franchise stores. Therefore, in the development of this theory, whether the franchise is temporary or not temporary evidence becomes a key empirical fact (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996). Meams (2017) first proposed that after the separation of management rights and ownership, corporate behaviour will deviate from the trajectory of profit maximisation (Means, 2017).

Jensen and Meckling (2019) proposed agency theory and defined agency relationship as: "One or more principals to hire and authorise another agent to exercise certain specific actions have a contractual relationship between each other." They believe that the agent has a potential self-interested motive, and this self-interested motive prompts managers to no longer make company decisions or management with the goal of maximising shareholder wealth. Those who abuse the company's resources for privileged consumption will reduce the company's value. They divide the costs incurred by agency problems into the following three items: 1. Monitoring cost: refers to the cost incurred by the principal to ensure that the agent will act in accordance with the contract. 2. Bounding cost: refers to the cost incurred by the agent to make the principal believe that it will act in accordance with the contract. 3. Residual cost: refers to the loss incurred by the agent's decision-making deviating from the decision that maximises the benefit of the principal after using various methods of supervision and restraint. The above-mentioned costs will lead to a decrease in the value of the company. Therefore, the agency theory aims to seek the best contractual relationship to reconcile the effectiveness of the stakeholders of all parties and promote the increase of the company's value.

Since Baylor and Means (1932), the division of ownership and management has been research from business management scholars. When the manager is without any shareholding, there is a basic commonality to the risk appetite related to business decisions (Boyd & Solarino, 2016 cited in Rhou, et al., 2019). Ownership and human rights, when the dichotomy between age roles and the decentralisation of ownership leads to a reduction in charge observing of running business, some leaders may avoid their responsibilities or undertake sub-optimal business projects, cause the owner's agency costs. To decrease this expense, equity is usually awarded to leaders of the International Management Association, allowing them to act like owners, thereby coordinating the gain of leaders and shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1979). According to agency theory, existing research involves corporate performance, innovation, growth strategy, company performance, structure, performance, and other institutional results for example board independence, liabilities costs, and company

acquisition possibilities (Boyd and Solarino, 2016 cited in Rhou, et al., 2019).

Another explanation for franchising is agency theory. Rubin (1978) claimed that because the franchisee's ownership incentives maximise the performance of self-motivation, when the store is chartered, the entrepreneurs either directly supervise the manager or establish a hierarchy to monitor them, then these pipelines will be permitted. Consistent with this theory, franchisees are used to monitor where employee managers are costly (Gills, Cobs and Yin, 2018).

By sharing the claim on income with the franchisee and requesting the payment of the deposit in the form of a franchise fee, the franchiser wishes to cause the franchisee to make necessary efforts to manage the store (i.e., eliminate the avoidance costs) and the relationship with the agent. With its original and specific operating methods franchising produces many benefits by its very nature, making franchising an effective business practice. (Caves and Murphy, 1976 cited in Scott, 1995); Martin, 1988). However, Rubin (1978) defined that it also stipulates a variable payment based on the royalties used by the outlet store to the franchiser, which ensures that the franchiser can also guarantee that he still has an incentive to properly manage the entire system (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996).

In contrast, other types of vertical agency problems still exist, because opportunistic shirking behaviour may be two-sided (Lafontaine, 1992). Erm and Schon (1994) list possible arithmetic behaviours. For example, a franchiser can put the outlets too close to maximise the interests of the franchiser and terminate the reopening of a franchiser-owned branch at the same location. Other negatives to the franchisee can revolve around contracts, forcing the franchisee to purchase dictated inputs, requesting an inappropriate advertising fee, or writing a contract to benefit the franchiser in a dispute. Operators may damage franchisers by publishing proprietary information, not paying royalties, or failing to comply with quality standards. In addition, Castro and Justis (1998 Rondán Cataluña) believe that other agency support privileges may come from franchisees' hunger for autonomy. However, franchisers usually exercise control to minimise the risk of franchisees taking opportunistic behaviour and ensure that they comply with written contracts. Therefore, in the franchise system, control is used to protect the franchiser's brand name. Tools are used to provide standardised and guaranteed products and services to customers through franchisees.

In academia, many previous studies have examined the effectiveness of agency theory in the context of franchising from the perspective of formal control (Monye, 1997; Shane, 1996; Stanworth et al., 1996), seeking optimal control. Structure (Eisenhardt, 1989), and check control costs (Castro and Justis, 1998 cited in Rondán Cataluña, et al., 2007). For instance, Combs & Ketchen (2003) Year proposed agency theory is a harbinger of franchising (e.g., geographical dispersion, local management expertise, franchisee input, and export size). Similarly, Aron (2013) shows that agency theory is a good explanation of the motives of franchising. The basic franchise contract generally emphasises the rights of the franchiser, not its obligations. Therefore, the agency theory ignores the franchiser's view of the contract re-joining and fails to reanalyse the franchisee and the special dynamics of the relationship between business operators (Loewenstein and Lerner, 2003). Therefore, as Eisenhardt (1989) and Sharma (1997) suggest, agency theory should be used in conjunction with other theories to understand the franchise system to overcome this limitation (Jang and Park, 2019).

2.4.3 Brand resonance

Brand resonance, the brand not only forms the basis of the franchise relationship, but also has great value in sales, predetermined demand, higher profits, better inventory turnover, image enhancement and relationship commitment (Web, Webster and Kreppa, 2000). Franchisers offer their brand "Support Nobel" (Web, Webster and Kreppa, 2000) and try to develop strong brand attachment among franchisees to motivate them to implement appropriate brand citizenship behaviour (Nyadzayo, et al., 2011). Ultimately, a strong and reliable brand-centric relationship between franchisers and franchisees helps deliver consistent products and a stable brand image to end consumers (Davis & Mentzer, 2008; Nyadzayo, et al., 2011). Brand attachment is the addition of behavioural loyalty and refers to the emotional bond with the brand, which promotes the brand to continue and maintain brand relationships (Thomson, et al., 2005). Strengthening brand attachment between franchisees is recommended to lead to positive brand evaluation and brand citizenship behaviour (Nyadzayo, et al., 2011). The theories were also broken into two categories which are theories relating to franchising and performance.

2.4.3.1 Brand resonance relating to franchising.

Like consumers, brand community awareness among franchisees has the potential to have a positive impact on franchisee performance. The brand community refers to "a professional, non-geographically constrained community based on structured social relationships between brand admirers" (Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001). Join the brand community, create greater interaction between franchisees, unite with franchise brands, and oppose competitive brands (Muniz & O'Guinn, 2001)

Keller (1993) defines the brand image as: the association of a brand that exists in the consumer's memory and reflects the concept of cognition of the brand. The brand image does not only exist in product technology, functions, and entities, but is also influenced by relevant marketing activities, publicity content and the characteristics of the recipient itself.

Through the brand image, consumers can easily identify the product, evaluate the product quality, reduce the cognitive risk at the time of purchase, and confirm that the brand can get differentiated feelings and satisfaction. Thakor and Katsanis (1997) pointed out that the brand image can be used as a clue to evaluate product quality, especially in the evaluation of empirical products, the brand image can reverse the bad image of the country of origin and improve the recognition and trust of product quality.

Trust is the willingness to rely on a trading partner and have confidence in the trading partner (Moorman, Deshpande & Zaltman, 1993), or the degree of honesty and reliability of the partner (Aulakh, Kotabe & Sahay, 1996). Therefore, trust can be regarded as one of the important factors that determine the quality of the cooperative relationship (Lee & Kim, 1999). Through the measurement of indicators such as reliability, credibility, honesty, motivation and intention, the degree of trust between partners can be judged (Smith & Barclay, 1997). For franchise brands, the brand image has a certain influence on the franchise owner's choice of the franchise headquarters. A headquarters with a better brand image can give franchisees confidence in their brands, increase their willingness to join, and thus increase trust in the headquarters.

The brand resonance, a franchisee will be attracted to enter a market brand if the brand is outstanding and the recognition high. It is believed that the revenue will be relatively high, so

it will choose to join this brand. The long-term and good interaction between the franchise headquarters and franchisees is an important issue for the development of the franchise system. Both parties sign a structured contract and use mutual trust and commitment as the basis for long-term cooperation to achieve mutual benefits. The relational contract theory, the head office and branch companies need to use contracts to protect and constrain the rights and interests of each other. The exercise of rights and obligations is clearly informed in the contract, to avoid the catering franchisees ordering goods and materials from sources other than the franchise headquarters.

In resource scarcity theory, every franchise system company has its own exclusive formula or supplier. Under the asymmetry of external resources principle, to obtain this resource, the operator needs to pay franchise-related expenses to obtain the right to operate. To prevent franchisees, the process of collecting their information must be more rigorous and careful, because if the information is insufficient and there is uncertainty, the probability of occurrence of speculative behaviour will be greatly increased (Hizam-Hanafiah, et al., 2022). If the headquarters wants to fully understand, the behaviour of franchisees is difficult.

2.4.3.2 Brand resonance relating to performance.

Therefore, the brand image is obviously a bridge to promote effective communication between the company and the market. Aaker (1992) proposed that in addition to helping consumers understand and process the company's information, brand image can also enable consumers to effectively have confidence in the company's product quality and comfort, which can enhance and produce greater willingness to consume. Since then, scholars Keller and Aaker have also conducted theoretical empirical research. The research of Aghekyan, Simonian, Forsythe, Kwon and Chattaraman (2012) has demonstrated that the brand image has a direct and significant impact on consumers' willingness to consume. Taiwan's leading supermarket chain 7-11 has been committed to the brand image change in recent years. The retail sales and sales of the original display products have been transformed into a new dining guest image, and the original business model has been transformed into a takeaway style, it can effectively increase the number of visitors and improve the operating effectiveness for different customer groups.

Taiwan's leading Chinese pot-sticker catering brands have gathered from all directions. Since the founding store in 1998, the brand image has been continuously improved and changed. If the brand image is an important foundation for the success of a company, and the signboard is the most important rock in the brand image. After nearly 18 years, the Bafang Yunji signboard has also undergone different specifications and changes, effectively enhancing the brand image and has significantly improved the performance of each store.

Brand norms, regarding the importance of cognition in brand norms. Gould and White (1986) pointed out that human behaviour is only affected by the environment that they are exposed to, while the perception and impression of the entire world is strongly influenced by the information filtered by itself. Cognitive research is a kind of organisational research, strategic management and performance evaluation, whether theoretically or empirically, it is a focus of research (Garling & Golledge, 2018).

Scott (1995) proposed that the research on organisation has long been controversial, that is, the assessment of subjective perception and objective assessment of the environment. Dill (1958), Lawrence and Lorsch (1967), Duncan (1972) pointed out that subjective evaluation is more appropriate than objective evaluation, because cognitive factors will be taken into consideration when making decisions and will affect future action decisions (Tillotson, 1980).

Gould and White (1986), Huff (1990), Reger and Huff (1993) proposed that organisational research has renewed the importance of managers' cognition and its impact on decision-making (Garling & Golledge, 2018). The empirical results researched by Dollinger and Golden (1992), Powell (1992), Delaney and Huselid (1996) show that there is a positive and significant relationship between subjective cognitive performance evaluation and objective performance evaluation (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021).

Brand awareness shows brand is the foundation of marketing. Marketing without a brand is equivalent to marketing without a foundation. Marketing is the most important sales behaviour of a company. If a company does not have a brand, it will seem to be losing its direction in the marketing arena. It will sell aimlessly and have no direction. It can only rely on price-cutting competition. Therefore, the brand is not only the foundation of marketing, but also the root of business management.

Aaker (1991) believes that brand awareness refers to consumers' knowledge and memories of product brands. It is also pointed out that brand awareness is the ability of potential customers to recognise or recall a certain brand in a specific product category, that is, the strength of a brand in the minds of consumers. There are two main types of brand awareness: brand awareness and brand recollect; brand awareness refers to the ability of consumers to recognise the previous impression of the brand when they see a brand; brand recollect refers to when consumers read the manufacturer's catalogue and look at the catalogue to buy what is needed, whether consumers might recollect a particular brand in the context of purchase and use.

Holden (1993) proposed that brand awareness is an explanation of the context based on memory and relies significantly on eye-catching information prompts subjectively. Therefore, "brand recall" refers to the product brand, the customer has the ability to evoke the memory link to the brand, obtain a certain degree of satisfaction through the product category, or have other forms of memory collection, just like clues, etc.; that is to say when the customer sees a particular product category, they can regain the impression in their memory and correctly link the strength of the brand name of the product category; while "brand recognition" means that customers can correctly distinguish the brand (Radder & Huang, 2008).

Hoyer and Brown (1990) pointed out that the higher the brand awareness of the company's products, the more likely it is for customers to buy this product. Keller (1993) proposed that the higher the brand awareness, the more positive the influence on customers' buying behaviour. It also means that product packaging may also affect customers' purchasing decisions and attitudes. It can remind customers of the surrounding assets of a brand, which will greatly and effectively help build the value of the brand (Chi, et al., 2009).

The empirical research of Laroche, Kim and Zhou (1996) also pointed out that the higher the brand familiarity of the customer, the better the brand attitude towards the product. That is to say, the willingness to buy a product produced by the brand is relatively higher.

Samiee (1994) pointed out that even if consumers face an unfamiliar product, if the product belongs to a high-profile brand, there will still be a possible positive evaluation of the product. Compared with products with low brand awareness because customers are relatively less familiar with the brand, it is necessary to use the various information provided by the product

as the basis for product consumption evaluation. The key strengths in relation to the context of this study, the franchise system understands the operation methods related to the agency through the theory of agency mechanism and can have a deeper understanding of the brand marketing operation and apply it in practice.

2.4.4 The theories associated with both sides of the franchise.

2.4.4.1 Transaction costs

Transaction cost theory: Cyert and March first proposed this theory in 1963. Moreover, Williamson (1996) pointed out that there are many contracts that create value for the company within the company or through the market. Every contract signed with an external party has associated costs; such costs are called transaction costs. If the transaction cost of using the market is high, the company will bear the transaction by itself (Hennart & Verbeke, 2022).

Williamson's theory of transaction costs (1975, 1985) is important for understanding the relationship between franchisers and franchisees. According to Williamson (1975), transaction costs occur when a product or service is transferred through a technically separable surface. Therefore, each time a product or service moves from one phase to another, transaction costs are incurred. Uncertainty, opportunism, risk, boundedness, and core company assets may increase transaction costs. Therefore, under the franchisee-franchiser relationship, opportunistic behaviour may increase transaction costs and undermine this relationship. Dalstrom and Nigard (1999) also studied organising electronics companies to limit post-trade transaction costs between franchisers and franchisees. They believe that opportunity behaviour is the determining factor of transaction costs, and that cooperation and formalisation are the control tools for mitigating opportunity behaviour. In the end, Dalstrom and Nigard (1999) found that opportunistic behaviour continued to increase transaction costs, but cooperative interaction inhibited the cost and formalisation of negotiations and reduced opportunism (Jang & Park, 2019).

2.4.4.2 Social Responsibility

The concept of "corporate governance" appeared as early as the 1970s, but it was not until the 1997 Asian financial crisis that this topic was brought up again and discussed further. The

reason for this is that after the financial crisis, most scholars believe that strengthening the corporate governance mechanism was an effective way for enterprises to fight against the problems that arose from the crisis. Recently, the investors in the market have begun to question the sustainability of the bull market, especially this kind of bull market that is based on liquidity and suffers severe damage to the real economy (Chakraborty, 2021). In China, the topic of "landmine stocks" a while ago has reduced the public's enthusiasm for the domestic securities investment market. As the result of a series of vicious bankruptcies such as BD, Xunde, and Huangtong, the hard-earned money of two or three billion investors evaporated in an instant. Not only did they embezzle a large amount of funds, but they also eroded the confidence of many investors in Taiwanese enterprises. Driven by this background, "corporate governance" has become increasingly important. This is not only because it is a major international issue, but more importantly, good "corporate governance" is of great help to the company itself.

Franchiser Social Responsibility (FSR), Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an ideological practice under which companies operate in ways whereby the workings of the company have a positive impact on the nearby environment or society at large by engaging in practices that bring good to the local or national community (Lee, et al., 2012). While previous academics and operators (Wallich and McGowan, 1970) concentrated on business interests and methods that helped promote social good (e.g., manufacturing quality items for the customer while bringing profit for the shareholders), some alternative views have surfaced over the past twenty years (Coles, et al., 2013; Lee, 2008). Some academics have studied the results of CSR on different parties including customers, the local community, and staff in addition to the results on business or monetary outcomes lined with CSR (Brown and Dacin, 1997; Lee, 2008; Luo and Bhattacharya, 2006; Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001 cited in Luo & Bhattacharya, 2006).

FSR (Franchiser Social Responsibility), the concept of corporate social responsibility refers to activities that companies do to connect with or give back to the community. The term originated in the late 1960s, but it has only gradually gained attention in recent years. From the perspective of the franchiser, social responsibility has many benefits in terms of brand awareness and increased market opportunities. The franchiser can take these measures to increase brand awareness nationwide and participating individual franchises can help increase brand awareness at the regional level. The reason for building brand awareness is

because when the franchise is involved in a community or social cause, it has news value and is attractive to journalists and other media. Symbiotic relationship, FSR, broadly speaking, socially responsible activities range from employee volunteer service plans and fundraising activities to sponsorship of local community groups, usually involving management and employees. (Franchise Direct, 2012)

With a highly developed economy, the advent of the consumer era and marketing era, price competition, product services, store image, and strong activities all dominate consumers' willingness to consume (FAO, 2020). Therefore, in the past, single-handedness alone was no longer in line with economic benefits. The chain franchise system has become the most popular type of operation in modern business activities. Through multi-site marketing, unified purchase, collective publicity, and promotion, not only can it reduce costs and operational risks, but it can also improve the competitiveness of enterprises. However, legal issues within the scope of the fair-trade law, such as the regulation of rights and obligations between franchise owners and franchisees, undisclosed information damages franchisees, and unscrupulous players who borrow money from franchises all offer difficulties to overcome. These are obstacles that the franchise industry must deal one after another and indeed must overcome. (Lumen, 2020)

CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility), CSR is an evolving business practice, and sustainable development is incorporated into the company's business model. It has a positive impact on social, economic, and environmental factors. As the use of corporate responsibility expands, socially conscious images become more and more important. Consumers, employees, and stakeholders begin to prioritise CSR when choosing a brand or company. They require companies to be responsible for social change with their business philosophy, practices, and profits. (Schooley, 2019)

2.4.4.3 Resource Dependence & Scarcity

Resource dependence theory focuses on the role of the board of directors. The role of the board of directors can be divided into four categories: internal staff, business experts, support experts and community influence. They provide access to resources guided by Hillman, Canella, and Paetzold (2000), such as information, skills, key suppliers, purchasers, public policy makers, legitimacy of social groups, and legitimacy of the company. Hillman, Canella

and Paetzold (2000) believe that resource dependence theory focuses on the role of directors in providing or ensuring basic resources to the organisation through contact with the external environment.

The resource scarcity theory was proposed by Oxenfeldt and Kelly (1968) and is rooted in a resource-based company perspective (Wernerfelt, 1984). Oxenfeldt and Kelly (1968) argue that to expand rapidly in a growing market, companies choose franchising to obtain scarce resources (business, management, and information). In general, if a restaurant experience raises enough funds to grow through traditional markets or internal cash, then franchising can be an attractive option (Shane, 1996; Thompson, 1994). Through the rapid expansion of franchising, the company achieved economies of scale in procurement and advertising, exceeding the company's internal capabilities, which in turn made it competitive in the market (Castrogiovanni, Combs & Justis, 2006).

The issue of ownership reorientation is primarily studied in the literature from the perspective of resource constraints (Oxenfeldt and Kelly, 1968; Norton, 1988) or institutional incentives (Brickley and Dark, 1987; Rubin, 1978). Under the assumption that entrepreneurs and retailers naturally like to have their own outlets, presumably for reasons of greater income sources and / or personal uncontrollable resource constraints; (Dant, 1995; Lafontaine and Kaufmann, 1994), the argument may be especially true. This is evident when business success depends on rapid market expansion and first-mover advantage. Rapid growth requires significant capital, human and information (i.e., market knowledge) capital, which is not readily available to young organisations (O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996).

However, as mentioned earlier, Rubin (1978) questioned the interpretation of resource constraints. However, empirical results do not consistently support Rubin's position (Dant, 1995), and Lafontaine (1992) has documented a resource-based alternative interpretation of franchising. However, regardless of whether the franchise was initially the best source of expansion capital, capital constraints should gradually relax as the system grows. When this happens, the resource-constraints argument indicates that it will move in the direction of full company ownership except for possible marginal units. (Oxenfeldt and Kelly, 1968 cited in O'Reilly & Chatman, 1996).

Research on scarcity theory has been empirically tested, and some studies have found

evidence supporting this theory (Combs, et al. 2004; Kaufman and Dante, 1996), while others have no evidence (Combs & Ketchen, 2003). Recently, Shane et al. (2006) reported that franchisees showed growth if they had low initial costs, had appropriate commercial support programs for franchisees, and avoided inlining in company-owned outlets. Once the company reaches the point of scale economy, rapid expansion seems to have lost its strategic focus, and franchisers tend to maximise their profit. At that point, franchisees tend to try to buy back their most affluent franchise stores, which is called ownership redirection (Beck and Dante, 2008; Dante and Kaufman, 2003; Dant et al., 1996).

It is undisputed that ownership reorientation may lead to degradation of the franchiser-franchisee relationship. Although ownership redirection has been consistently controlled by US law since the ground-breaking reports of Oxenfelt and Kelly (1968) and Ozanne and Hunt (1971), there is hearsay evidence of ownership redirection (Dant et al., 2011). Formerly, Windsperger et al. (2004) and Windsperger and Dant (2006) only have a strong bargaining power in the franchiser, but the franchisee has only the right to transfer ownership if there is little information, management, and assets.

Therefore, the resource scarcity theory not only provides theoretical motivation, but also provides the potential for franchisees and franchise relationships to be threatened by ownership reorientation. Therefore, when the franchise system is at a mature stage, the collapse of the relationship between the franchisee and the franchiser may be due to the privileged opportunistic behaviour of the franchiser (Jang, et al., 2019).

2.4.4.4 Managerial ownership

Stewardship theory, Catalyst's (2004) survey also found that CEOs of Fortune 500 companies agreed that board heterogeneity is an important "bottom line" for considering achieving profitability, and similar boards composed of CEOs' own partners may not be effective Consultants and supervisors. Putnam (2007) reported that board heterogeneity may stem from differences in many areas, such as director education, experience, occupation, gender, race, and age. Stewardship theory, Davis, Schoorman & Donaldson (1997) define it as "the steward protects and maximises shareholder wealth through company performance, because in doing so, based on the root's psychology and sociology, "the utility function of the housekeeper has been maximised". Administrators are company executives and managers

who work for shareholders, protect shareholders and profit from them. When the organisation is successful, the investors will be satisfied and motivated. Donaldson and Davis (1991) pointed out that it emphasises that employees or executives take more autonomous behaviour to maximise shareholder returns. Indeed, Davis, et al. (1997) added that this can minimize the cost of monitoring and controlling behaviour. Employees are responsible for their job and work hard.

Stakeholder theory, Brean (2001) stated that the theory of corporate governance emphasises the concept of "incomplete contract". The goal of corporate governance issues and institutional development to strengthen governance is to ensure that the interests of management are aligned with the interests of shareholders. Thus, the main goal of corporate governance is to improve company operations and pursue the best interests of shareholders (Brean, 2021). Companies with good corporate governance can properly plan business strategies, effectively supervise the implementation of strategies, safeguard shareholders' rights and interests, and disclose relevant information in a timely manner.

There are many definitions of "corporate governance", then, corporate governance is a mechanism of guidance and management, with the purpose of executing the duties of the company's operators, and considering the interests of other stakeholders, by establishing the company's performance, and protecting the rights and interests of shareholders. In the relevant research on corporate governance, it is found that there are different interpretations of the integration of governance and sustainable development in geographic regions. However, vision, mission, and leadership are the most important drivers of the sustainability framework that deals with corporate governance (Sahar, Zulkifli and Zakaria, 2018) In recent years, international investment institutions have attached great importance to Asian financial markets, and when it has been increasing year by year, corporate governance is often an important reference for institutional investors in making investment decisions. They generally require credible financial statements, the ability to hold the company's board of directors and senior managers accountable, and they hope to see the company's strong internal checks and balances. According to a research report conducted by McKinsey & Co. in June 2000 on more than 200 institutional investors in 31 countries, companies with better corporate governance performance, under the same issuance conditions, investors are willing to pay relatively higher prices (including corporate governance premiums).

Wheeler et al. (2002) pointed out that stakeholder theory combines sociology and organisation disciplines. It puts the responsibility of supervision in the supervision of all relevant parts. It points out that the managers in the organisation all have a service network-including suppliers, employees, and business partners. Donaldson & Preston (1995) believe that the theory focuses on management decision-making, the interests of all stakeholders have intrinsic value, and there is no interest assumption that can dominate other interests. Their stakeholder model is included in investors, political groups, customers, communities, employees, trade associations, supplier, and government.

2.4.4.5The Relational Contract

The relational contract theory, a good long-term interaction between the franchise headquarters and franchisees is an important issue for the development of the franchise system. Both parties sign a structured contract and use mutual trust and commitment as the basis for long-term cooperation to achieve mutual benefits. Thomas (1998) pointed out that trust usually involves believing that the other party will act in a predictable manner, and will consider the interests of partners, rather than fully committing to self-interest. The cooperative communication and trust will positively affect the emotional commitment, and the cooperative communication will also promote the trust of the franchisee to the franchise headquarters (Thomas, 1998).

Just as the joining headquarters and joining master have unequal resources and powers, if the two parties have good communication and promote the spirit and cognition being in the same boat, they will help each other in the cooperation process due to their trust and emotions, promoting franchisees to renew their franchise and have a positive reputation. If you want to increase the franchisee's commitment to the franchise headquarters, it can be started by strengthening the franchisee's trust in the franchise headquarters, promoting the franchisee and the franchise headquarters to share common goals, and enhancing the franchisee's dependence on the franchise headquarters.

The relational contract theory, when Macneil (1978) explored how traditional and neoclassical contract law fit into modern economic structures in the production and distribution of goods and services, the concept of relational contracts began to attract scholars' interest. As a legal scholar, Macneil has studied that relational contract theory and code of conduct for over 40

years to assess communication in business (McLaughlin, et al., 2014). The relationship contract was deliberately incomplete, so the parties had room for manoeuvre (Jeffries and Reed, 2000), and they were still very clear about how the contract started and how to withdraw the contract (Leblebici and Shalley, 1996).

Zaheer and Venkatraman developed a relational governance model in 1995, using trust as an intermediary for international exchange, thus suggesting a dynamic view of its role. Macneil (1999) defines the relationship contract theory using the following four core recommendations: 1) each transaction is embedded in a complex relationship, 2) understanding any transaction requires understanding of all the basic elements, i.e. relationships, 3) franchisee analysis needs to identify and consider the inclusion of corresponding elements, 4) combined with context analysis relationships and transactions are more non-contextual analysis (Rosado-Serrano & Paul, 2018).

Traditional contracts may lack provisions and are ambiguous; however, they are recognised by the court (Hart, 2017). Traditional contracts face moral risk and asymmetric information problems, which can create difficulties for franchisers and franchisees (Alon, et al., 2015; Hart, 2017). Sometimes, verifying the performance of a contract based on the original conditions of the contract is “unsatisfactory,” and parties in a long-term relationship (such as a franchise relationship) may rely on self-executing or relationship award contracts (Doornik, 2006). Because of the internal and external dynamics of this economic relationship, it is important that there is room for renegotiation.

Trust in many different models, Research (McAllister, 1995; Rotter, 1967) has looked at trust in many different models such as employer–employee relationships, business-to-consumer (B2C) relationships, and business-to-business (B2B) relationships. Most research found that trust is necessary in a range of organisational structures and outcomes such as problem-solving, goal setting, cooperative behaviour, and work performance (McAllister, 1995). In organisational writings, staff trust has been firmly attached to many positive working environments such as job satisfaction, loyalty, productivity, low turnover rate, and a desire to make the company successful (Chughtai and Buckley, 2009; McAllister, 1995).

Marketing literature (Dwyer et al., 1987) also demonstrates that trust is a vital instrument in altering the nature of the relationship. According to Morgan and Hunt (1994), trust is

specifically crucial in business-to-business (B2B) cooperation because it entuses businesses to work together toward reaching beneficial goals. Trust is a vital factor in altering a business-to-business (B2B) relationship from the most seen lowest cost/profit only interaction to a reassurance risk free based cooperation between the supplier and the client (Morgan & Hunt, 1994 cited in Lee, et al., 2016).

The key strengths of theories associated with both sides of the franchise in relation to the context of this study, from the perspective of the franchisee, try to decrease the purchase cost, and to less the substitutability of materials which can avoid imitation by other competitors. From the perspective of franchiser, social responsibility can affect the company's image and their stock price. Therefore, when operating a franchise chain business, on the one hand, it is necessary to attract new franchisees, and on the other hand, it is also compulsory to attract customers, so that the company can flourish. In addition, when a franchiser's products are unique and difficult for competitors to imitate, there are usually so-called secret recipes, or materials imported by the exclusive agent that may not be available in Taiwan. These are the reasons why resource dependence and scarcity theories are discussed. Of course, the business management of both franchisee and franchiser affects business performance through their equity structure, which is also directly related to this study managerial ownership.

2.5 Chapter Summary

All in all, in the context of this study the review above highlights the importance of agency theory assumes that the agent is selfish and that the interests of both parties (such as the principal and the agent) are not necessarily consistent. For example, the interests of a paid employee (or agent) are inconsistent with the interests of the company (or principal). Therefore, poor incentives may lead to the shirking of responsibility of salaried employees (Rubin, 1978), which is known as the vertical agency problem. In this case, the franchise system in which the principal franchiser cancels the power/ownership of the franchisee can be an explanation. The contractual relationship between the franchiser and the franchisee stipulates that the franchiser will provide information and operational support to the franchisee, sometimes even providing commercial support for management outlets (Nisar, 2011), while the franchisee gains income only after paying royalties and other fees, plus there

are residual claims. Another perspective nested in the principal's literature portrays franchising as the best form of organisation that effectively combines the interests of franchisers and franchisee.

Brand is a corporate image, can partly effectively reflect consumers' brand positioning and become a key factor for consumers to decide on consumption. Simply put, brand image is an asset added to products or services. The needs of society have a certain meaning for consumers. (1) Aaker (1992) once mentioned that brand image is the most acceptable method for customers and can create more added value for the brand. For example, it can generate more loyal customers and reduce the market. Costs, attract potential customers, differentiate with competing companies, make consumers feel their preferences, etc. (2) Keller (1993) proposed that brand image can enable customers to produce brand-related clues in their memory when they want to consume, so that customers will have a certain degree of evaluation of the brand. If consumers have a positive affection for the brand image they prefer, consumers will feel more interested in the brand's products or services and increase their willingness to consume.

Chapter 3 –Related Research on the Performance of the Catering Industry

3.1 Introduction

This chapter evaluates the following theories, performance appraisal and key success factors, plus discussing the franchise managerial ownership related literature in the context of Taiwan, the aim is to continue the chapter 2 history of franchise and deeply explain the American countries and Asian countries franchise types, global development and their pro and con. As well as discussing the Covid-19 crisis handling.

The food and beverage section are the UK's largest manufacturing industry, accounting for 7% of GDP and annual turnover of 80 billion pounds. In the face of economic fluctuations, the industry has also shown a certain degree of flexibility, which can maintain stable growth employment. In Britain there is an increasing demand for a diverse choice of menu and convenience dining is increasing, which means that if you find a well-known brand and open it in a suitable location, you have a great chance to earn money (Franchise Direct, 2020).

The United States is the birthplace of franchise operations worldwide. After the Second World War, the US government provided employment for veterans who had no skills or funds, so they jointly created a business model of authorisation to join the enterprise. The corporate headquarters provides knowledge, trademark rights use and business guidance, the franchisee pays the franchiser technical compensation, and the government provides entrepreneurial financing to promote the rapid growth of franchise chains.

The American Franchise Association (IFA) was established in 1960, which was also the budding period for the franchise industry. By 2001, according to a survey by the association, there were more than 760,000 chain stores across the United States, with an all-inclusive format, creating an output value of 624.6 billion U.S. dollars, and driving peripheral commercial output value of more than 1 trillion U.S. dollars, accounting for about the whole private 10% of the enterprise's output value. The US franchise industry is now the main force of the retail service industry, with a population of about 10 million people, covering the surrounding industries, and a total of about 18 million employees, accounting for about 14% of the civilian employment population.

The chain operation mode is an inseparable organisation form. A strict management mechanism is formed within the enterprise, which regulates the operation rules and behaviours of each branch, thereby ensuring the reasonable and efficient operation of the organisation. The management control of the branch stores of the chain is mainly reflected in the implementation of the management model and the grasp of the information flow.

In general, the biggest advantage of this business model is that every store adopts the same brand logo and visual signage, the same management model, and the same goods (Siebert, 2015). In plain language, the services you can enjoy are the same, and the standard of each service is unified.

If an enterprise wants to make the enterprise bigger and stronger, it adopts a direct-operated chain approach, which has advantages in shaping the image of the enterprise and binding customers at the early stage (Siebert, 2015). Because in the concept of regular chain management, the headquarters adopts a vertical and horizontal management approach, that is, the headquarters directly manages each retail store, and each retail store must also obey the headquarters' arrangement without question. In this way, the direct result is that each store has the same profit method, the same promotion plan, no matter which store the consumer consumes from, the same price and the same service. It directly avoids the damage to the company's reputation caused by product prices or product quality. For example, the common supermarkets such as Wal-Mart and Carrefour all adopt the model of regular chain operation (Kknews, 2017).

According to the definition of IFA, chain franchise refers to the head office granting the franchisees privileges and licenses to enable them to legally use the company's brand to participate in the business, and an obligation to provide franchisees' knowledge on organisation, training, procurement and management. That is, by copying the entire business model of the head office, the franchise master can be quickly put on the operating track, and even the profit period can be shortened. In recent years, due to the global economic downturn and the fierce influence of international brand competition, both local brands and internationally renowned brands have faced severe challenges in market expansion plans.

How to effectively respond to changes in business conditions, adjust the business model flexibly and launch an innovation plan is the way for the brand to win. The ecology of the

chain industry is changing, and the market supply and demand structure is reorganizing, which will show the new structure and style. In the century of diversified, large-scale and chain-type enterprises, they are showing their talents. With the development, enterprises of this century will be fully integrated into the Internet, with new strategic business resources combined with opportunities, which have sprung up and the chain of international supply, production and sales has become a paradox.

3.2 The studies involving the company's operating performance.

3.2.1 Performance Appraisal

The so-called performance evaluation refers to the use of mathematical statistics, operational research principles and specific indicator systems, in accordance with a unified standard, according to a certain program, through quantitative and qualitative comparative analysis, to make an objective and effective analysis of the project's operating efficiency and operator performance during a certain period of operation. Fair and accurate comprehensive judgement.

Performance appraisal, also known as performance evaluation and employee appraisal performance evaluation is a formal employee evaluation system, which is to evaluate and measure the employee's job behaviour and work results through systematic methods and principles. Performance evaluation is a management communication activity between enterprise managers and employees. The results of performance evaluation can directly affect the vital interests of many employees such as salary adjustment, bonus payment and job promotion.

Ven and Ferry (1980): In his research, he found that the so-called traditional financial performance usually refers to the measurement indicators that researchers point out most often, such as: profitability, return on investment, and sales. The amount of income, etc., among such various items, the income from merchandise sales is the most widely used item among all researchers.

Chakravarthy (1986): His research found that the so-called classification and measurement methods of business performance can be divided into four categories, which are described

as follows: (1) Business objective: It represents the business policy plan of the company, which is what it means to include the annual budget, annual expected capital increase, annual mergers and acquisitions, annual expansion plans, annual joint ventures, etc., to achieve all objectives. (2) Productivity: This refers to the usage of various plants and machinery and equipment in general. (3) Profit: This is the performance of the flow of funds for the overall enterprise that can be properly used in terms of return on investment. These can be calculated from the growth rate obtained. (4) Long-term superior resources: This is the basis of whether the company can continue to grow and operate steadily and sustainably.

WeAer (1963) on how to define organisational performance is based on the decision-making level of the organisation to make the most reasonable decision, which must receive the highest effect in substance, so that the organisation can fully achieve the goals set by the organisation; Katz and Kahn (1966) Pointed out that organisational performance is the use of various organisational methods to achieve goals, and the greatest return can be obtained. There are many channels for such feedback, which may come from consumers, may come from corporate financial profits, and more likely will come from the centripetal force of all employees of the enterprise itself, or in other aspects.

The Pickle and Friedlander (1967) study mentioned that organisations are organised by people from all walks of life and all levels. For example, the company's shareholders, related communities, governments, and organisations are correlated to the organisation. For related suppliers, creditors, consumers, corporate employees, corporate managers and other members, organisational performance is the degree of perception that meets the needs and expectations of various members. Yuchtman and Seashore (1967) pointed out that organisational performance is the ability of the organisation to obtain resources and negotiate from the external environment.

Mott (1972) pointed out that the ability to mobilize all the resources in the organisation to achieve production and adaptation activities is organisational performance. Steers (1977) mentioned in the research on organisational performance to effectively reduce the obstacles for the organisation, so that the enterprise or organisation can meet the needs of the service target in the process of operation. He believes that a more effective organisation must be able to satisfy the service target. The needs of the target may reduce the disappointment of the target to the organisation. Gross and Etzioni (1985) pointed out that the relevant

organisational performance is regarded as the degree to which the organisation achieves its goals. The goal of all organisations is the ideal situation that the organisation achieves in all aspects. That is to say, the degree to which the organisation can achieve this ideal situation. If the organisation's action performance meets or exceeds its goals, the organisation can be said to have good performance.

Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) pointed out that the so-called organisational performance refers to the extent to which the organisation achieves a certain goal. From the perspective of process, performance converts inputs into product outputs to achieve a specific result, which includes effective cost and realised output., The extent to which these goals are achieved. Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) clearly think of organisational performance into two different definitions and interpretations: narrow and broad: the so-called narrow performance refers to the effective satisfaction of the organisation's financial indicators, if viewed from a broad perspective. The so-called organisational performance should include financial data such as revenue, return on assets, and operational indicators such as product quality and market share (Rogers and Wright, 1998).

Hall (1991) clearly pointed out that organisational performance is a description of the organisation's ability to develop surrounding contexts to obtain scarce or valuable resources in order to maintain its functions. Aorman and Motowidlo (1993) pointed out that organisational performance is all behaviours related to organisational goals, and this behaviour can be evaluated based on the degree of contribution of all individuals to those goals. Organisational performance should be recognised to varying degrees according to various objects, values, and preferences. In contrast, stakeholders in different organisations have different values and preferences. Regarding organisational performance to satisfy the preferences of different members, members within the organisation may be concerned about the work situation and various conditions, just like shareholders. The most important thing is the profit rate, and different members of the organisation will have different preferences (Scott, 1995).

3.2.2 Key success factors

Conceptual source of key success factors, the concept of key success factor (KSF or critical success factor) was put forward by Daniel (1961) some time ago. He pointed out that many

industries have three to six key factors that determine success. If a company can achieve these key factors well, then the company will be successful. The concept of "limiting factor" put forward by the famous economist Commons (1974) is to apply it to negotiation and management in the economic system. Later, Aarnard (1976) will also be applied to decision management theory. He clearly believes that the analytical method required for decision-making is looking for a "strategic factor".

In addition, Tillett (1989) applied the concept of strategic factors flexibly to the theory of dynamic organisational systems. He believed that an organisation has the most resources, that is, the key resources. However, the meaning of strategy is to maintain and make good use of the advantages that can be brought about by having the most resources, while at the same time avoiding the disadvantages of their own enterprises caused by the lack of certain resources. The above can clearly know that the analysis of various industries and competitive ecology can understand the key success factors. Critical success factors are the most important considerations in industry analysis and the most important control variables in management, and they are the source of various competitive advantages.

The definition of critical success factors, Aaker (1984) proposed that critical success factors generally refer to the most important competitive assets or competitiveness in a company. The advantages that a successful company can have over other competing companies must be the key success factors in the industry. Relatively unsuccessful companies usually lack one or several key success factors. Therefore, it is unable to use its competitive advantage to succeed. Leideeket and Aruno (1984) also clearly stated that key success factors refer to some of the characteristics, conditions, or variables of the enterprise, and if these enterprise conditions can be appropriately and continuously maintained and managed, they can have a significant impact on the company's competitive success in a specific industry. Influence.

Wu (1988) also clearly stated that the key success factors refer to the technologies or assets that are required to successfully compete with other competitors in a specific industry. By knowing the degree of cooperation between the company's own advantages and key success factors through various analyses, it can be clearly judged whether the company can be competitive. Assuming that the company's advantages are reflected in the industry's key success factors, the company will be able to Gain a competitive advantage. From the definition of key success factors set by all the above-mentioned famous scholars, it can be

known that the key factors of a company can be referred to as the necessary conditions for the success of the business. Obtain a permanent competitive advantage and achieve the goal of sustainable operation.

3.2.3 Review of the dynamics of family businesses

Since the corporate governance of family businesses is an imperial system, when a family business expands, the family's profits must be far greater than those of other stakeholders in the company, which is obviously detrimental to dynamic fairness. From the perspective of agency theory, management ownership (i.e., a non-franchise business) has the same interests between the principal (i.e., the shareholder) and the agent (i.e., the manager). A basic assumption of agency theory is that principals and agents have a risk-taking tendency (Hasent, 1989). While shareholders are considered risk-neutral because of their portfolio, managers are risk-averse because they focus on firm-specific investments (e.g., firm-specific knowledge, skills, and years of experience). To protect the wealth and human capital associated with the company, the agent may abandon the high-risk but pro-Philippine investment project in line with the interests of shareholders and turn to a project that is safe but sub-optimal for investment in its own interests. From a shareholder's perspective, managers' low-risk tendencies are not conducive to value maximisation because economic and financial theory associates high risk with high returns (Kim, et al., 1993). In order to achieve incentive consistency between managers and shareholders, agency theorists suggest giving managers a greater proportion of equity because management ownership is assumed to increase strategic risk taking and company value (Jensen & Merkel, 1976 cited in Lee, et al., 2016).

Chain operation mode: According to the ownership, the chain operation area can be classified as: (A) A centralised direct chain system. (B) A decentralised franchise chain system. High ownership levels can also promote management consolidation. Deep-rooted managers control most of the company's shares, which may give them enough voting rights to ensure their work is not subject to external constraints. As a result, entrenched managers may engage in activities that are not fair to themselves, nor to shareholders. In other words, there may be an intrinsic relationship between managing ownership and taking risks, or there is a positive relationship between management ownership and franchise. Costs coexist with management's own interests, and the best incentive contracts are needed to strike a balance

(Jensen and Murphy, 1990). Previous research has shown and supported the inverted U-shaped relationship between human age ownership and corporate risk (Wright, et al., 2007).

In other words, management ownership has a certain positive impact on the company's risk taking; in the past, management ownership has certain considerations for the company to take risks. Interestingly, although Stulz (1988) and McConnell and Servaes (1990) both reported that the company's value was maximised at around 50% of management ownership, Park and Zhang (2010) studied that the company's value maximised, in a display of the company's low level (about 38% - 40%) management of the catering industry (Rhou, et al., 2019). Among the business types of enterprises, family business is the most common type of organisation that has the greatest impact on society and the country. (Dale, et al., 2008) In countries all over the world, the model of family business type has been confirmed in many studies in many countries (Anderson & Reeb, 2003), in Western Europe, South Asia, East Asia, Middle East, Latin America and Africa, most publicly issued companies are also controlled by the family (Faccio, et al, 2002). From the perspective of entrepreneurship and employment, family businesses are a hotbed of entrepreneurship (Dale, et al., 2008), from which it can be seen the importance of family businesses to individuals and national societies as a whole (Bettinelli, 2012).

Under different management philosophies, organisations have produced different organisational cultures and organisational mechanisms, as well as the design of organisational mechanisms for management rights and ownership. Like modern organisation theory, it is believed that enterprises should separate ownership from Management control, and that only small and medium-sized enterprises are suitable for adopting a system of two powers in one (Bettinelli, 2012). However, in the research of family business performance, some studies have shown that the performance of family business is better (Miller, et al., 2005), whereas some show that non-family companies perform better (Tsai, Hung, Kuo, et al., 2006). According to a study by Chandler (1977), the United States, Britain, and Germany have grown up in the direction of unity in the 19th century (Bewayo, 2009).

Managing ownership, usually as a percentage of the shares held by its top management and directors (Himmelberg, et al., 1999), is an important corporate governance mechanism that companies uses to mitigate agency problems (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). In the United States, the management ownership of listed companies increased from 13% in 1935 to 21%

in 1995 (Holdenes, et al., 1999). Between 1989 and 2000, the average management ownership rate was 22%, compared to 23% for other English-speaking countries and 43% for continental European countries (Gugler, et al., 2008). For companies with at least 1% insider, the average management ownership is 9.18% (Bauer, et al., 2016). In emerging markets, management ownership has also seen a similar upward trend (Boyd and Solarino, 2016; Rhou, et al., 2019).

3.2.4 The correlation of ownership structure and company performance

Shareholding ratio of directors Yang (1998) used statistical regression to study the listed companies from 1991 to 1996 and explored the relationship between shareholding structure and operating performance. The results of the study found that the proportion of shares held by directors and supervisors was significantly positively correlated with operating performance. Yang (1999) believes that the shareholding ratio of directors and supervisors is significantly related to the earnings per share and return on assets of the company's operating performance indicators but is not significantly related to the net profit rate and the return on equity.

Chen (2001) used narrative statistics, correlation coefficient analysis and multiple regression analysis to study all listed companies at the end of 1999 and believed that the shareholding ratio of directors and supervisors was positively correlated with accounting indicators (ROA). Yang (2008) used data envelopment analysis to study the operating performance of listed tourist hotels in Taiwan from 2001 to 2005 and found that the shareholding ratio of directors and supervisors and operating performance showed a positive and significant impact. Chen (2013) studied 69 listed and OTC construction companies between 2007 and 2012.

The results of the study show that the shareholding ratio of directors and supervisors is positively correlated with operating performance. Yang (2014) used the equity concentration and the characteristics of directors and supervisors of listed companies from 2006 to 2012 as the research objects and believed that the shareholding ratio of directors and supervisors was significantly positively correlated with company performance.

Institutional corporation shareholding ratio, Zhuang (2005) conducted an empirical analysis based on the data of listed companies in Taiwan and found that the shareholding ratio of

corporations' performance was significantly negatively correlated. Wang (2006) took the financial shareholding company as the research object and believed that the shareholding ratio of institutional corporation is positively related to the company's operating performance. Lin (2007) conducted an empirical analysis based on Taiwan's construction industry and banking industry and believed that the shareholding ratio of institutional corporations was positively correlated with the company's operating performance. Chen (2013) used construction companies as the research object and found that the shareholding ratio of institutional corporations has positive and negative correlations with operating performance.

Insider manager shareholding ratio, domestic scholars have different research results due to different research objects. There are different research results of positive correlation and negative correlation. They are summarised as follows: Hong (2004) uses listed companies from 1989 to 2002 as the research object and uses the re-regression test. According to the analysis, it is believed that the proportion of insiders' shareholding is significantly positively correlated with company performance.

Separation of ownership and management. With the changes in economy, culture, and society, the traditional business model that can fully meet the needs of working capital with its own funds can no longer be maintained. When the company is getting bigger and bigger, to raise sufficient working capital, besides borrowing, another way for the company to raise funds is to issue shares. As a result, the company's equity will no longer be in the hands of a single shareholder, the company's shares, and ownership will become more and more dispersed. Under the circumstance of gradual decentralisation of company ownership, if the company's various decisions need to be decided by all shareholders, it will not be in line with the principle of cost-effectiveness.

Therefore, the company must appoint professionals to operate the company for many shareholders, which will result in the separation of ownership and management rights. In addition, with the increasingly fierce competition in the industry, companies tend to diversify their operations, the demand for specialised division of labour is increased, and management rights and ownership are gradually separated. In other words, shareholders no longer directly control the company's operating rights, but maintain an agency relationship with the company's management.

Meams (2017) believed that when ownership is gradually dispersed, the ability of company owners to restrict managers will gradually weaken, separating decision-making managers from risk-bearers, and the interests of managers will not be completely the same as those of company owners. In other words, managers may not strive to maximise the value of the company to pursue the maximisation of personal interests, company assets may be used to satisfy the personal interests of managers, that is, managers will not follow the goal which is to pursuit profit and allocate company resources. The personal interests of managers include enjoying privileged expenditures and pursuing goals that have nothing to do with the maximisation of the company's value.

Adam (1776) supposed that "In a company with separate management rights and ownership, the funds used by directors are not owned by themselves but invested by other investors. Therefore, it cannot be expected that these directors will be similar. The careful attitude of the partners to supervise and use the company's assets. Therefore, Adam (1776) predicts that in such a company which was a company with separate ownership and management rights (Jensen and Meckling, 2000).

3.3 Taiwan development of franchise chain business

The development of Taiwan's franchise business started in 1979 when Uni-President Co., Ltd. cooperated with the Southern Company of the United States and introduced the "7-ELEVEN" brand to operate chain supermarkets. With a full set of management systems, it became the first domestic convenience store chain with international know-how. In 1984, Kuanda Enterprise introduced McDonald's fast-food restaurants in the United States, making the domestic chain industry more mature. The prosperity and development of Taiwan's franchise business and the upsurge of domestic small and medium-sized enterprises and micro-enterprises have played a complementary role.

Through the franchise business, franchisees can obtain systematic services and support at all levels of products, technology, marketing, operation, and management, and realise their dream of starting a business. Therefore, in recent years, the domestic franchise business has gradually become institutionalised. With the increasing range of franchise fees, it has become the best way for many inexperienced people to join and start a business. With the optimism about the counselling and support system provided by franchise, as well as the low threshold

of some franchise fees, women are becoming more involved in franchising businesses, starting with Portuguese egg tarts, bubble black tea, breakfast shops, fried chicken shops, etc. in the 1990s. Similarly becoming involved in the system of large-scale women's clothing, wedding dresses, vital food, maintenance, and beauty.

After McDonald's entered the Taiwan market in the 1980s, the catering industry started the first wave of international chain development. The influx of foreign brands and funds quickly pushed the catering industry from a stand-alone store competition to emphasise scale, quality, standardised operations, and the stage of chain operation. After years of accumulation, in 2010, local chain catering brands such as Wowprime, Anxin and Wacheng were listed one after the other. The internationalisation, diversification, capitalization, and technological development of the brands accelerated their growth. The scale of Taiwan's catering industry has grown rapidly for two consecutive decades, coupled with a stable trend and a higher operating profit rate than the retail industry, it is a brand group of upstart catering brands and has become a popular livelihood channel category that has attracted much attention in the capital market and commercial competition. The single-store model, chain replication model, and multi-brand extension model in the investment value evaluation of the chain catering industry are explained separately, as an auxiliary point of view for understanding the layout strategy of each group. (MIRAI BUSINESS, 2020) Taiwanese chain catering group three development models.

1. Single-store model: Apply a single store type to create excellent floor effects

The single-store model is an important value evaluation basis for chain enterprises. It is based on averaging the operating results of a single store to gain insights into the business's cost-benefit, site selection effectiveness, and operating expenses; a successful single-store operating model is also a brand foundation for chain expansion (MIRAI BUSINESS, 2020). For example, Din Tai Fung and Kura Sushi.

2. Chain replication model: Show the energy of international exhibition stores

The key to the success equation of the single-store model is whether the company has the ability to replicate chain expansion operations and can replicate the operating results of a single store to the entire market. For example, based on a single store type with excellent

performance in Taiwan, Din Tai Fung has successively expanded to 22 overseas markets, with a total of 153 overseas exhibition stores, becoming the leader of Taiwan's restaurant stores. Another strong catering group is Wowprime, their overseas expansion strategy targets a single market in mainland China and has successively launched more than 10 brands totalling 142 stores (MIRAI BUSINESS, 2020).

3.The multi-brand extension model: Strategy display of deep and straddling operations

After enterprises have established chain expansion and international expansion capabilities, some chain restaurant groups have chosen to further adopt a multi-brand extension model to break through the limitations of a single market. Observing the context of the multi-brand model of the Taiwanese chain restaurant group, it can be concluded that there are two completely different development models for in-depth operations and cross-over operations.

The specific manifestation of the in-depth combat is the vertical expansion of the market with core brands as common characteristics, such as Wacheng. Across the battle is to lock in customer groups with consumer potential and launch highly diversified brand options at similar consumer prices to seize market share. A typical representative company is Wowprime Group, which has launched 20 operating brands in the Taiwan market. Its brand features include Western steak, Chinese pasta to Japanese hot pot, and a wide variety of products. Another group is La Kaffa International, starting from the chain of handshake drinks, expanding to Japanese fast food, cake baking and pasta cooking and other food fields to reach more consumers (MIRAI BUSINESS, 2020).

This COVID-19 epidemic wave of high-intensity stress testing has also become an opportunity for the industry to re-examine the single-store model and basic business physique as the cornerstone, build a single-store model with stable profitability and operating moats, reduce the risk of capital disconnection, and improve the risk resistance of the entire group ability has become an important key to evaluating the strength of brand management.

3.3.1 The development of Taiwan's catering industry

Thanks to the economic leadership of advanced countries, Taiwan's economic momentum in global trade, investment, and financial markets has been active. In recent years, the overall

economic performance has been better than expected. However, its import and export trade rely on the United States, Japan, Mainland China and other countries, and the economic enthusiasm is highly linked. Therefore, it will change with the international situation. The main factors are the intensified turbulence in the US-China trade war, the FED's balance sheet reduction plan and interest rate hike strategy, and international fluctuations in oil prices which have caused the global economic momentum to turn from prosperity to decline (MOEA, 2019).

In addition to understanding their own food culture, Taiwanese local food and beverage brands can take a place in the fiercely competitive food and beverage section. They can also pay attention to the world's food and beverage trends and learn the advantages of foreign food and beverage brands. The local speciality snacks have been upgraded to inherit the tastes of Taiwanese culture and memory, to stimulate the restaurant industry and bring more directions and possibilities in the future (Zheng, 2018).

Observing the forecast values of various economic research units, the economic growth rate in 2019 is expected to drop by 0.3 to 0.5 percentage points, indicating that the economic outlook of various countries has become conservative. Therefore, in addition to continuing to assist domestic companies to expand overseas markets, they also need to turn to expand domestic markets. It needs the market, stimulates private consumption, attracts foreign tourists to Taiwan, and uses domestic demand to drive the main force of economic growth in the future (MOEA, 2019). It is essential to boost the momentum of private consumption, by stimulating daily expenses (food, clothing, housing, transportation, education, and entertainment) to activate the market, and for various companies to seize the opportunity to expand the scale of enterprises through a franchise service model, to increase consumer brand impression and value and to enhance brand loyalty to achieve the purpose of continuous repurchase consumption. The operating format of the chain model can be summarised as general retail, life service, and catering services, which are closely related to people's lifestyles.

According to the 2016 The Chain Industry Operation Survey by the Ministry of Economic Affairs, output value of the chain industry economy is as high as 2.68 trillion new Taiwan dollars, accounting for 24.4% of the output value of Taiwan's service industry. In addition, there are more than 153,000 stores and 690,000 employees, and the overall scale is showing

a continuous upward growth trend, which shows that the franchise industry is a very important format for Taiwan's service industry, and has a dramatic impact on society (MOEA, 2019). At the same time, as the people of Taiwan regard food as their heaven, the turnover of Taiwan's catering industry has set new highs for consecutive years since 2012. As of 2018, it has reached a record high for 6 consecutive years. As of November 2018, the overall turnover of the catering industry has reached NT\$4,299. 100 million new Taiwan dollars, an increase of 4.9% over the same period last year. It is estimated that Taiwan's catering industry market will continue to grow in the future (MOEA, 2019).

An overview of the importance of chain franchising in the catering industry to the overall development of the domestic service industry, to achieve the goal of activating the domestic market, in addition to strengthening the capabilities and quality of the front-line first-line service of the enterprise, it should also return to the back-end system to attract customers, gather customers, and retain customers. Having customer and return strategies, and comprehensively enhancing the service functions of the enterprise, can continue to stimulate consumers to come back (MOEA,2019). Therefore, it is important to systematically and strategically promote consumer experience optimisation, characteristic catering environment, improve service positioning, co-branded marketing and other practices to drive franchise and catering industry operation growth, boost buying momentum, and continue to assist domestic chains and the catering industry exports opportunities overseas to expand the popularity of overseas brands, which will simultaneously affect foreign tourists' awareness of Chinese chains and catering brands and then come to Taiwan for consumption, to create a higher industrial output value, and activate the industrial economy (e-volunteer, 2021).

According to the definition of the 10th revision of the "Republic of China Industry Standard Classification" promulgated by the Executive council in 2016, "catering industry" refers to "industry engaged in conditioning meals or beverages for immediate consumption or take-away" Delivery and catering contracting, etc. also fall into this category. In the "Industry Standard Classification", the catering industry is further subdivided into the catering industry, outsourcing and group meal contracting industry and the beverage section. The definitions of each industry are shown in the following table 4 (TTR, 2020).

Table 4 Definition of various categories of catering industry of Taiwan

Section name	Definition
General Catering Section	Shops and vendors engaged in preparing meals for immediate consumption.
Outsourcing and group meal contracting Section	Engaged in contracting customers to conduct catering services at designated locations for sports events, conferences, weddings, and other similar activities; or specialising in providing catering services for schools, hospitals, factories, companies, companies, and other groups.
Beverage Section	Shops and vendors engaged in conditioning beverages for immediate consumption.

Source: Directorate-General of Budget Accounting and Statistics, Taiwan cited in TTR 2020

The importance of the franchise chain to the catering industry and the development of the overall domestic service industry, also goes on to achieve the purpose of activating the domestic demand market. (TTR1, 2018) According to the "Taiwan Chain Store Yearbook 2017" published by the Taiwan Chain and Franchise Association, the development of chain brands in 2016 was investigated. The number of chain headquarters in Taiwan was 2,739 and the total number of stores was 102,408, which is an increase from the previous year's growth rate. The rate is 5.4%, of which the number of new brands in the chain catering industry is the largest. The big company remains a large corporation; but the small and medium-sized enterprises have individual operating patterns and are still the mainstream of the market (Li, 2017).

Therefore, it should be systematically and strategically promoted the optimisation of consumer experience, distinctive catering environment, improve service positioning, and co-brand marketing to drive the growth of franchise and catering industry operations and boost buying momentum (Einstein, 2012). At the same time, it must be continued to assist the domestic chain and catering industry to export opportunities overseas to expand the popularity of overseas brands, creating a higher industrial output value, and activating the industrial economy (MOEA,2019). To enable consumers to obtain consistent services and products, enterprises through the franchise business model, open to other business owners joining the brand to expand the scale of the enterprise (Nyadzayo, Matanda and Rajaguru, 2018). Due to the advantages of a business model of sustainable replication, the chain operation has a wide range of applications, including food, clothing, housing, transportation, and entertainment. It is inseparable from daily life. It can be divided into a comprehensive

¹ TTR, Taiwan Trend Research

retail industry, general retail industry, life service industry, and catering service industry (Lumen, 2020). Lindblom and Tikkanen (2010) claim that franchising is one of the business models available to start an instant new business. This model has been used by many successful firms as the failure rate is lower than normal business models, plus it is a quick way to start a business. How the franchiser converts the tacit knowledge (such as insight, ideas, and hunches) held by the franchiser into explicit knowledge and contributes to the knowledge creation and management research in commercial franchising (Lindblom & Tikkanen, 2010).

However, if the franchising system is not comprehensive, there may be many conflicts and issues of recognition of rights and obligations between the franchiser and the franchisees. This research will investigate the level of franchising and managerial ownership within the restaurant industry and evaluate the performance and effectiveness of franchising in the restaurant sector. Finally, I will give a recommendation of an effective approach strategy relating to performance in the restaurant companies. The practice of franchising is common in most Western economies and was predicted as "the main retail form of most developed countries in the world" (Reynolds, 1990 cited in Hing, 1996). In Australia, more than 17,000 franchise companies have annual sales of \$32 billion, an annual increase of 12.7%, and the survival rate is 2.25 times higher than that of independent small businesses (Hing, 1996).

3.3.2 Future environment forecast

According to data from the General Accounting Office of the Executive Council, Taiwan's GDP output value was NT\$ 17.43 trillion in 2017, the service industry output value was NT\$ 10.95 trillion (62.87% of GDP), and the employed population reached 6.73 million, showing that Taiwan's service industry is the mainstay of economic activities (DGBAS, 2021). In addition, it is also the main source of job creation. Various data show that the service industry is Taiwan's most important economic core, and it is also an important industry that supplies the labour market and promotes Taiwan's economic development (e-volunteer, 2021).

At present, Taiwan is facing changes in the international economic and trade situation, and the country is also facing internationalisation, continuous adjustment of market demand, an aging population, and declining birth-rates. It is urgent for the government to lead the industry, academia, and research cycles to overcome these challenges, including strengthening the

enterprise's ability to create added value and rebuilding the industrial ecosystem (e-volunteer, 2021). It must assist enterprises to develop international channels and accelerate the challenges of brand internationalisation. In addition to continuing to stimulate domestic purchases, it is also expected to expand the high-quality image of Taiwanese chain brands through service exports, attract foreign tourists to Taiwan for sightseeing, and promote economic momentum (MOEA 2019). The future environmental forecast is divided into "industrial, consumer, and international" for discussion.

3.3.2.1 Industry aspect

The franchise industry is one of the main forces driving the domestic market. Various possible determinants of franchising rates in emerging countries. Emerging markets are one of the fastest growing economies in the world; in addition, the countries they represent are undergoing major economic transformations (Baena, 2012). To enable consumers to obtain consistent services and products, enterprises have opened franchise business models to attract business owners interested in franchising brands to join and expand their business scale. Because chain operations have the advantage of sustainably replicating successful business models, they are applied to a wide range of business types, including food, clothing, housing, transportation, and entertainment, which are inseparable from daily life (DGBAS, 2021). They can be broadly divided into general retail and life service industries, and catering service industries. According to the "Wholesale, Retail and Catering Trends Survey" by the Statistics Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, retail sales reached a record high for 10 consecutive years, reaching NT\$ 4.27 trillion, with a growth rate of 3.17%, the largest increase in 4 years from 2014 to 2018. The business performance of the catering industry has achieved good results for 16 consecutive years, reaching NT\$ 473 million, with a growth rate of 4.59% in 2018. It is estimated that the retail and catering industry in Taiwan will continue to expand and grow in the future.

According to the 2018 TTR "Taiwan Trends Research Report" and "2018 Taiwan Chain Store Yearbook", in recent years, the number of entrepreneurs, sales and employees in the chain franchise and catering industry have shown a year-on-year growth trend, and the consumption and eating habits of the Chinese people have gradually increased (TTR, 2018). The changes, coupled with the continued growth in the number of tourists from Japan, South Korea, and Southeast Asia, will also increase the overall revenue of the franchise and

catering industry (e-volunteer, 2021). Although the revenue from franchises in the catering industry continues to grow, the growth has slowed down in recent years, indicating that industry competition is fierce, and the catering market is gradually becoming saturated.

In response to the rapid changes in customer consumption habits, the store strategy has shifted to a qualitative improvement. According to the survey of the Taiwan Chain Stores Yearbook 2018 by the Taiwan Chain and Franchise Association, the total number of chain stores in Taiwan in 2018 has reached 104,959 (including directly operated stores and franchised stores), and the chain headquarters has reached 2,781 (TTR 2018). The growth has slowed in the past two years, and the chain headquarters is in an M-shaped development. Medium and large chain brands adopt a multi-brand strategy. After evaluating the business cycle, they will continue to display stores or relocate stores depending on the business cycle to increase market share; small and medium-sized single-brand chain headquarters, Cost assessment is more cautious, resulting in a small increase in the number of franchise stores and a decrease in the number of directly operated stores.

In addition, the “2017 Full Retail Report” by the CPAs and the “2018 Wholesale, Retail and Catering Industry Operation Survey Report” by the Statistics Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Deloitte (2018) pointed out that many companies have experienced declines in revenue performance or reduced gross profit (Deloitte, 2018). Therefore, the expansion of stores is no longer the primary goal of chain business operations. More accurately, the focus is how to use product features, high-quality services, brand value, delicious food, and dining experience, plus an institutionalised, systematic, and standardised management model. With a high-quality consumption environment, experience, and effective management of operating costs, to grasp customers and improve operating performance (MOEA, 2019).

3.3.2.2 Consumer aspect

Consumption does not only satisfy material needs, but it also an emotional connection. According to the “2018 Global Consumer Insight Report” and “The Future of Consumer Experience in 2018” by Zicheng Certified Public Accountants, the “cost-effectiveness (C/P value)” that consumers were concerned about in the past has gradually faded and been replaced with the consumption process. "Customer Experience (CX)", it can be found that

consumption habits have begun to change from satisfying life, commodity prices and quality, and material needs to emotional sustenance and connection, and more and more attention is paid to "Service Value Experience". As in all countries with representative cuisines, gourmet dishes are one of the key elements to attract international tourists. Surveys of visits to Taiwan, Thailand, South Korea, France, etc. can see the influence of national cuisines (PwC, 2021).

Service experience is one of the key factors of purchase. A study (PwC² 2018 Global Consumer Insights Survey) found that 45% of consumers around the world are willing to spend money on "experience" and 55% on "products", and the proportions of the two are almost equal (PwC, 2018). In addition, as many as 73% of global respondents said that a good consumer service experience is one of the key driving factors in addition to enhancing brand loyalty. For example, fitness venues integrate wearable devices into the training process and create consumer data to provide more customised training courses (e-volunteer, 2021). It is similar catering food through consolidation, establishing mastery and providing a delicious and enjoyable dining experience, which will create consumption and enhance the brand loyalty and reputation.

Conversely, the survey also pointed out that 32% of respondents said that if they have experienced a bad service experience, they would leave their favourite brands, and even up to 60% of respondents felt unfriendly services during the consumption process. Would cause them to give up the purchase directly. According to the "Harvard Business Review" research, the extent to which consumers with emotional connections promote corporate products and services, and the return rate of customers are three times that of ordinary consumers. Faith (2018) found that consumers have a perception of the value reflected in the price of the company's products. It also shows that competitor prices affect the company's product purchases, while online pricing informs and influences purchase decisions (Faith, 2018). In the process of promoting the globalisation of Korean food in South Korea, film and television dramas are used as delicacies promoting. The carrier of the company is jointly exporting to the world, and constantly establishes the representative cooking image of Korean cuisine-kimchi, deepening the memory and naming of the people at home and abroad.

² PwC (PricewaterhouseCoopers Taiwan), it is an alliance of multinational accounting firm PwC in Taiwan.

The potential return on investment of a quality customer experience is high. According to the report, global consumers are willing to spend 16% more on products and services with high-quality customer experience. If they can effectively cooperate with marketing and topic strategies, they will be more effective in driving sales (TTR, 2018). According to the survey report of "New Blue Ocean in the Retail Market in 2018", in addition to enhancing the functionality, high purity, and high quality of products, through effective emotional connection (such as packaging and taste will imitate daily life). Chen and Lin (2015) tested and empirically confirmed the mediating role of continuous intention and satisfaction on blogs between customer experience and perceived value (Chen & Lin 2015). Korean style concept, to increase sales performance by 12%, coupled with seasonal and topical operations, to bring consumers closer to successfully drive the topic (e-volunteer, 2021).

Taiwanese cuisine has become an attractive commodity and effort should be focused on promoting, this as food tourism is the future trend. Many countries have begun to attract tourists with food and improve their international competitiveness. Since prehistoric times, humans have given meaning to everything related to food (Civitello, 2011) All food kingdoms called by the world will have representative foods, such as French cuisine, Japanese cuisine, Thai kitchen, Korean food, etc., with clear ingredients and tastes, which can be used as targets for attracting visitors and exporting food. Although some Taiwanese delicacies such as bubble tea, Taiwanese fried chicken, braised pork rice etc, have been well received and loved by people around the world, and have become successful exports, the number of representative items is still insufficient. In Taiwan, in terms of representative food items, it is necessary to enrich local ingredients to develop a more representative Taiwanese food system (TTR, 2018).

Combine multiple channels to provide a convenient consumer experience. According to the 2016 "Survey of Chain Industry Operations" by the Department of Commerce of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Taiwan's franchise industry has the highest proportion of mobile e-commerce introduced by new technologies (46.7%), followed by online and offline virtual and real integration (25.1%), and mobile payment (25.1%). 14.1%), showing that chain and

catering companies have begun to cooperate with consumers' mobile shopping behaviours to develop new sales channels (MOEA, 2018). In the application of e-commerce tools, the proportion of using FB fan groups is the highest (61.0%), followed by self-built corporate shopping websites (35.3%) and shopping platform sales (23.5%), showing that chain and catering industry players are on the social network. The sales method still holds the most interest and application (TTR, 2018).

The decline of traditional media, coupled with the development of information and communications and the rise and rapid penetration of digital media, related marketing tools have been greatly digitized. In the application of chain and restaurant enterprises, digital tools should be appropriately used for marketing, such as social media FB, Self-media and e-commerce platforms, etc., to quickly provide consumer information and services (e-volunteer, 2021).

International visitors to Taiwan continue to increase. From 2008, various policies such as the opening of land visitors to Taiwan for sightseeing, simplifying entry and exit procedures, and expanding international routes have greatly improved the accessibility of international travellers to Taiwan (MOTC, 2021). In 2017, it has exceeded 10.73 million single person visits, an increase of 4.61% from 2016; December 2018 the target of 10 million passengers was reached on February 2 two weeks ahead in 2017. With the different people-times, the reasons tourists were attracted to Taiwan changed. In 2009, the number of tourists to Taiwan was 2,298,334. The number of tourists to Taiwan increased year by year and by 2017, the number of tourists to Taiwan reached 7,648,509 single person visits, an increase of 232.78% (MOTC, 2021).

3.3.2.3 International aspect

In response to strengthening the export power in the international market, large enterprises tend to diversify their operations and expand their footprint. Cooke, et al. (2018) researched that in recent years, the expansion of Chinese companies' global footprint has revealed their increasingly obvious strategic intent and emerging capabilities and called for the need to (re)examine how the internationalisation strategy of emerging multinational enterprises (EMNE) is conceptualised and has an impact on human resources (Cooke et. al, 2018). To continue to expand the market, most large-scale chain and catering companies adopt

diversified development strategies to add value to existing core businesses, such as horizontally developing highly related products in the industry, or vertical development from the perspective of supply chain, vertical integration of upstream, middle, and downstream, and strengthening of the main body operating industry. And when the main operating niche is stable, in response to the different habits of consumers in various countries, it also expands its territory toward a multi-brand and multi-format approach (Felix, 2014).

The domestic demand market in China is strong, and the international markets in Europe, America, Japan, and South Korea are also attracting attention. Taiwan's chain industry began to expand outward in about 2000, expanding overseas markets with a more complete chain system and technology. So far, the accumulated number of overseas chain stores has exceeded 40,000 (TTR, 2018). Among them, the catering industry is the largest. The exhibition area is mainly in mainland China (such as Tenren tea, Baodao glasses, Daphne, Din Tai Fung, COCO tea, 85 degrees C) and Southeast Asian countries (Such as Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines). According to the 2016 Survey of Chain Industry Operations, mainland China is the primary area for chain enterprises to expand. Due to the strong domestic demand market in the mainland, coupled with the advantages of language communication and cultural similarity, the cumulative number of Taiwanese chain headquarters entering mainland China has so far exceeded 200 stores.

Sidali et al (2015) found that rural tourism of food tourism, niche markets and products, combining intimate models and experiences as a rural development strategy (Sidali, Kastenholz & Bianchi, 2015). In the catering industry, the beverage section has emerged internationally in recent years. In addition to attracting celebrities in Europe and the United States to drink, rely on the vertical integration of raw materials, food machinery, packaging materials, brand authorisation, etc., to successfully seize North America and Europe with industrial clusters and entire store output, and niche markets such as Australia.

New South policy's countries³ which has strong consumption power attracts international capital investment. The ASEAN market belongs to a new economic area that has been highly developed in recent years. The ten ASEAN countries established the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC) at the end of 2015, which continues to expand at an average annual

³ New South policy's countries: India, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Thailand, and Vietnam.

economic growth rate of 5-7% and is in a high economy (Executive-Yuan, 2016). In the growth stage, the average income of the middle class in the new southern countries is gradually increasing, with more than 50% of the young labour force and demographic dividend, young people who like to consume, natural rich resources, preferential investment conditions, etc (Sidali, et. al, 2015). The amount of foreign investment has increased year by year. International brands continue to enter important economic development metropolitan areas, creating rapid growth in the ASEAN market (Executive-Yuan, 2016).

The global catering market continues to grow, and the Asia-Pacific region is still the fastest growing market. According to Statista's "Global Catering Industry Market Scale Research Report", the global catering market reached USD 239.7 billion in 2016. The top five catering markets in the world were the United States (USD 78.2 billion/year) Mainland China (USD 48 billion/year)., Japan (31.4 billion U.S. dollars/year), India (14.8 billion U.S. dollars/year) and Brazil (11.5 billion U.S. dollars/year). In the European catering market, France, and the United Kingdom account for a relatively high proportion of total consumption.

According to China Statistical Yearbook data (NBS, 2021), since 2010, the average annual expenditure on dining out of Chinese urban residents has continued to increase, and the proportion of expenditure in total consumption expenditure has increased from 5.76% in 2010. Fluctuation rose to 7.89% in 2012. According to an international statistical research company Cushman & Wakefield's report (2017) on the growth trend of the global catering market, the Asian catering market is still the fastest growing country from 2006 to 2026 (prediction), with an average annual growth rate up to 9.8%, followed by the Middle East and Africa, with an average annual growth rate of about 7.4%, while the catering markets in the US and Europe are more mature, with a lower average annual growth rate of 6.1% and 4.2%. As shown by the above data, there is still much room for development in the international catering market (TTR, 2020).

Asia leads development in the world market. According to the development of Taiwan's service industry, the franchise and catering industry have established standardisation and systematisation advantages (Siebert, 2015). Stable control of marketing channels, free franchise market and price determination. Therefore, good cooperation and network need to be managed (Wardenski & Werner, 2012). Through brand international authorisation, they can replicate management, marketing, and service experience so that chain operators can

effectively and rapidly expand and deploy in the international market (e-volunteer, 2021).

According to the current international development trend, most of them are Chinese with the same language and the same kind. They have developed from China to Asia and the new southern market. After gaining a firm foothold, they will gradually develop into European and American markets, such as 85°C, Coco, etc. In the future, it will represent Taiwanese chain stores. The overseas layout of the brand should also be developed along this path (TTR, 2018).

3.4 Franchise system of catering

The development of the domestic and international consumer market is changing rapidly. According to the survey of the "2018 Taiwan Chain Store Yearbook", the average number of chain headquarters stores (total number of stores/total number of companies) in 2018 only slightly increased by 0.8% (about 37.7 stores) over previous years. Among them, the retail industry with the highest proportion of output value in the franchise industry is affected by e-commerce, which affects the turnover of the physical retail industry (TTR,2018). At the same time, new forms of marketing and diversified payment models affect consumer buying behaviour patterns; the catering industry is attacked by Taiwanese international catering brands The domestic catering market is affected by saturation factors, not only gradually consuming the Taiwan catering market, but also partially squeezing the catering consumption in regional commercial districts and characteristic towns (Sidali, Kastenholz & Bianchi, 2015). Therefore, in addition to promoting the domestic consumption market, it is vital to use limited resources to do a good job in overseas deployment. Planning effectively to enter the international market. (e-volunteer, 2021).

3.4.1 Catering management functions

Broadly speaking, management means using the efforts of others to achieve goals. (Zhou, 2020) From the perspective of an enterprise, management is the ability to efficiently integrate human resources, financial resources, materials, methods, and other resources in an organisational unit. In addition, to generate effective results through marketing planning, preparation, service, control, and promotion, achieving various long-term and short-term goals set by the organisation. Catering management functions can be divided into the

following five types.

Marketing is the activity, organisation, and process of creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging products that are valuable to customers, partners, and society (AMA, 2017). The marketing of the catering industry, the design of menus and beverage lists. Marketing refers to the activities carried out by a company to promote the purchase or sale of products or services. It includes advertising, selling, and delivering products to consumers or other businesses. Some marketing is carried out by affiliated companies on behalf of the company (TWIN, 2020).

Preparation is something that is carried out during the process so that everything is ready for a specific purpose or arrangement (COBUILD, 2021). Planning the management of the kitchen, procurement, acceptance, storage, distribution of raw materials, and preparation, hygiene, and safety of catering.

Operation is discussed that service operation process planning management. Catering services may have their own chefs to prepare food, or they may obtain readymade food from contractors or third parties to provide to customers. For sit-down dining activities, the service usually sends waiters, waitresses and waiters to prepare tables and provide meals. For buffets and informal gatherings, the catering contractor can send employees to set up hot pots, bowls, and plates full of food to supplement and provide food to the participants (Moro, 2020).

Control which is both catering cost control and labour cost control. It involves establishing performance standards based on company goals and evaluating and reporting actual work performance. After the management has completed these two tasks, they should compare the two to determine any necessary corrective or preventive measures. The control process is in progress. Through control, management can discover any potential problems and take necessary preventive measures. Management can also identify any developing issues that need corrective actions to resolve them. (ecourseonline, 2020)

The promotion of catering business and the formulation of strategies. Promoting the catering business is a key part of your operation, helping to spread people's awareness of your cooking services and attracting new customers. Public relations campaigns can be used as

well as traditional advertising methods and flooding in social networks to show what type of food and first-class service you offer. Identify the market segments you want to target-such as ethnic cuisine or certain types of events, weddings, or conferences, which will help guide the restaurant's promotional efforts. Durant (2020) claimed the four ways to promotion are press releases, targeted brochures, referral bonus and exhibition stand.

3.4.2 Service operation side

The rapid changes in the market have led to fast expansion of emerging chain companies. The advantage of the chain and catering development model is that it can break through the thresholds encountered in the scale of the service industry, such as fund preparation, talent team, and channel development. The development process roughly follows the single store operation, multi-store expansion, establishment of a chain system (headquarters), and brand overseas licensing (Jayachandran, Kaufman, Kumar & Hewett, 2013); however, this is not what it used to be. Brand authorisation seems to be of strategic significance, and effective and lasting competitive advantages can be established by acquiring and further developing brand capabilities. This seems to support the idea that brand licensing can represent a useful tool to overcome brand barriers, and it can also interact with the company's knowledge management field (Cardinali, Travaglini and Giovannetti, 2019).

Many external factors have made the chain development process explosive growth, such as the influx of venture capital, a large amount of willingness to join, thorough information disclosure overseas. Although the authorised business opportunities have caused chain and catering companies to leapfrog and expand, the management facilities and talent development cannot keep up, so that they are not locked and cannot give full play to the advantages of chain operations (Kim and Park, 2018). In addition, the obstacles for companies at different stages of development to improve their management physique are not just a single problem. Most of them are cross-domain and cross-level interactive problems. Therefore, it helps companies understand the operating knowledge of chain management and can effectively spread it. It is indeed a Taiwanese chain problem as well as the primary issue of the catering industry. Table 5 shows frequently asked questions in the development of typical chain and catering companies.

Table 5 Frequently Questions in the Typical Chain and Catering Companies.

Type	Explanation	Common business problems
Single store	Those who have successful experience in a single store and have a long-term experience with unique products or services to replicate the successful model to increase revenue, such businesses are the founders of franchising.	Lack of multi-store operation thinking, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accumulation of brand value • Site assessment of knowledge and resources in the business district • Standardised system and operating knowledge of exhibition stores <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store customer service process • In-store sales skills, use of emerging advertising tools
Multi-store	Those who have established 2-6 stores, initially have the scale of chain operation, and have successful replication experience, and are facing continuous expansion in the future. It is necessary to introduce the concept of franchise headquarters, so that the resources and information between the stores can be properly connected, and the management effect can be exerted.	Lack of headquarters management mechanisms, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chain management thinking of standardisation, simplification, specialisation, and concentration (3S1C) • Division of functions and responsibilities of the chain headquarters • Operational Information Integration System • Understanding of chain laws and regulations • Understanding of franchise types and systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall planning of a new generation of storefronts (flagship stores)
Chain system	For businesses that have more than 7 stores, including those that have established chain headquarters, this type of business has matured franchise status. In the face of system expansion, the headquarters should have comprehensive operational management and control capabilities and exert system functions to achieve operational goals.	A more efficient management system or system is needed, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Headquarters operating functions and roles (supply, shop, coach, management) • Establishment of brand value consensus • Headquarters organisation and supervision system rights and responsibilities • Headquarters human resources system, performance management • Franchisee coaching planning • Operating cost control and analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inventory concept of distribution and invoicing system • Countermeasures to the industrial structure and e-commerce
International potential company	Usually, an industry with a large chain, with headquarters, and at least meeting the basic conditions for international development potential (such as finance, operation management, brand management, and technical capabilities), and a preliminary idea or a base for overseas layout, to certain extent Market preparation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enter the overseas market model, such as direct management, joint venture, brand authorisation, technical cooperation regional agency) Evaluation • The overall international division of labour mechanism, such as trademarks, technology transfer, draw materials & equipment output, brand promotion, personnel, and related operations management, and technical capabilities), and a • Local support resources, such as product modification, local raw material procurement, local talent selection and training, local laws, tax regulations, foreign site evaluations, etc. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection and management of overseas agents and franchisees • International licensing contract planning

Note: source is from Catering industry development trend, TTR Taiwan Trend Research Report (TTR, 2020).

The service quality of different stores of the same brand is different, and the source comes from the chain enterprises. This type of chain industry has been developed in Taiwan for more than 20 years, and the type is also diversified (mainly divided into direct operation, voluntary franchise, entrusted franchise, and franchise, etc.) (e-volunteer, 2021). As the number of chain stores continues to grow, in addition to continuing to strengthen the brand image, formulate standardised procedures, and strengthen store management and logistical support assistance, the operation headquarters will often join with the expansion of the scale and increase the number of organisational personnel (TTR, 2018). Disagreements in communication have caused chain companies to encounter the phenomenon of interlocking, even jeopardising the brand and reputation, or the headquarters' ideas cannot be implemented in the store, so that the corporate brand culture cannot be effectively displayed to consumers (TTR, 2020).

Competition in the domestic catering market is fierce, and it is difficult to operate on a single-handed basis. Although Taiwan's catering market has been growing year by year, the domestic catering market has become fiercely competitive due to the low barriers to entry of capital and technology in the catering industry (e-volunteer, 2021). In recent years, due to the booming consumer market in Taiwan's catering industry, many people have been attracted to it from Japan and China since 2016. International catering groups from the mainland, South Korea, Singapore, and Malaysia continue to enter China's catering market (e-volunteer, 2021). The catering brands launched in Taiwan include Japanese Matsuya Donfan, Ichiran Ramen, Osaka King Dumplings, Chinese Haidilao Hot Pot, Hong Kong's Liaofan Chicken, Korean Ba-color BBQ, Singapore Treasure Seafood, Malaysian Huang Ya Fine Bak Kut Teh, etc. These, combined with the operating strength of international catering groups and the high reputation of overseas origins, have continued to increase the intensity of competition in the domestic catering industry (TTR, 2018).

Taiwan's catering industry is comprised mostly of small and medium-sized businesses, and the business type is also mostly sole proprietorship. It is inherently inadequate in the soundness of the food supply system, the control of raw material costs, the development of international talents, the development of new menus, and the marketing resources (Reisch, et al., 2013). In addition, international catering groups the competition and the fast transmission of consumer information about catering has prompted consumers at

home and abroad to have more choices and rapid changes in their preferences (TTR, 2018). If the catering industry continues to work alone in the domestic and foreign catering markets, it will mean the market is under pressure to survive (TTR,2020).

The integration of Internet and physical channels is full of challenges. In response to different consumer groups, chain companies have introduced different sales channels to enhance consumers' shopping experience (Jocevski, Arvidsson, Miragliotta, Ghezzi & Mangiaracina, 2019). According to data from the Ministry of Economic Affairs' "2018 Wholesale, Retail and Catering Industry Operation Facts Survey Report", the retail industry's merchandise sales channels are mainly physical stores, accounting for 92.0%, and e-commerce platforms which account for 5.7% (e-volunteer, 2021). Compared with 2016, sales through e-commerce increased by 0.4%, indicating that most Taiwanese businesses still operate physical stores. While e-commerce is growing rapidly, the integration of Online and Offline is still not mature enough to effectively utilize the characteristics of Online and Offline (Cui and Pan, 2015).

According to the "2017 Total Retail Report" statistics, the biggest challenges faced by companies when providing consumers with multi-channel experiences are "budget constraints (30%), too many old systems to change (21%), and difficulty in "integration Existing system" (20%)" which shows that there is still a lot of room for companies to integrate virtual and real channels (Deloitte, 2018).

3.4.3 Diversified consumption

The industry has a low degree of grasp of changes in consumer market preferences. In the "Future of Consumer Experience 2018" report, 71% of consumers believe that store staff have a significant influence in the physical service experience, but only 44% of consumers believe that store staff have a clear understanding of their needs. The "2017 Total Retail Report" further pointed out that there is a huge gap between the service satisfaction shown by companies and consumer expectations (Deloitte, 2018). Among them, "the sales staff's in-depth understanding of the product series (-15%) and the ability to quickly check product inventory (-10%). "Instant and personal products or services (-9%)" have the largest gap (Deloitte, 2018). The above data shows that the service performance of companies cannot meet consumers' expectations for physical store

services, and in the face of a new generation of consumer groups, it is more difficult for stores with a single category and service to attract consumption.

According to the “2017 Global Retail Industry Development Trends and Transformation Strategies” by Qinye Zhongxin Certified Public Accountants, it is quite difficult for companies to substantially increase new customers in the mature consumer market (Deloitte, 2018). If companies cannot consolidate the benefits of repeated purchases by loyal consumers, they will be unable to make sustained profits. The main reason for the low degree of consumer preference change is that the company has not selected the appropriate membership management system and smart technology according to its own business scale and business format to analyse and apply data on member information and consumption behaviours, understand consumer profiles, and provide customers with customised products or services so they will become loyal members who repeat consumption to achieve the purpose of precise member services (Guadix, Cortes, Onieva and Munuzuri, 2010). There is still room for improvement in the existing service model and product portfolio.

According to the “2018 Wholesale, Retail and Catering Business Facts Survey Report” by the Statistics Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, the most important problems in the business difficulties of the wholesale, retail, or catering industry are “intensified competition, shrinking profits, and low gross profit”, indicating that the company’s products or services are falling into high level of competition in the industry, and unable to create differentiated services to increase profits. Resulting in low gross profit and unable to continue to make effective profits, affecting overall revenue performance (MOEA, 2019).

The “2017 Survey Report on the Operation of Wholesale, Retail and Catering Industry” pointed out that the industry’s main shortcomings include “improving service functions (50.1%), creating product differentiation (30.3%), and expanding product categories (23.6%)”. Due to e-commerce and new types of marketing in recent years, most businesses lack an overall plan for online & offline integration. The actual benefits for enterprises are relatively limited. Enterprises understand that they need innovative services or products to separate the market, but they cannot effectively upgrade and transform to enhance the value of services (Guadix, et.al., 2010).

Physical stores cannot highlight the value of consumer experience. According to the "2017 Total Retail Report" by the CPA Accounting Firm, the proportion of shopping channels for consumers in various countries around the world is still dominated by "physical stores (44%)", and the sales channel market share of Taiwan entities is as high as 85% (Deloitte, 2018). Most people still like to spend in physical stores, so these also need to transform in response to the trend to maintain profitability. However, according to the statistics database of the Ministry of Finance, the domestic demand-oriented service industry market has shown a decline in recent years, and the domestic sales of three industries including cloth and apparel products, household appliances and supplies, and book and stationery retail have been seriously affected. In other retail channels, according to the insight report of "The Warring States Period of Taiwan's Retail Channels" by Nielsen Consulting (NielsenIQ, 2018), in 2018, except for the mass sales channels, the rest of the retail channels are actively exhibiting stores, such as chain supermarkets, convenience stores, and personal products.

But while expanding the scale to seize the market, single-store stores are facing the dilemma of declining visitor numbers and lower sales growth rate (the overall retail channel single-store growth rate decreased by 0.4%, of which chain supermarkets fell by 6.5%) (Deloitte, 2018). Therefore, to avoid the continuous loss of customers, the business methods of chain channels and catering should also begin to transform, to highlight the service value of physical stores, reach the service temperature that e-commerce sales cannot feel, and stimulate consumption to achieve "attracting customers and guiding customers." The purpose of "customer and retention" is to establish shopping emotions with consumers (TTR, 2021).

3.4.3.1 Create a good experience environment.

To attract consumers to visit stores, companies start with the store to enhance the value of consumer experience, such as combining leisure and lifestyle service models to promote the development of retail cycles and generate service connotations centred on consumer experience. For example, through sports venues, beauty and make-up, speciality catering, etc., attracting consumers to enter the physical field (Gauri, Jindal, Ratchford, Fox, Bhatnagar, Pandey & Howerton, 2021). In addition to choosing a suitable sales location and designing a comfortable store environment, consumers will enjoy food

through the five senses, with the retail part selling products through actual touch and wear, expanding the advantage of the on-site shopping experience. For example, Starbucks combines bakery workshops, selected bazaars, open bar counters, libraries, restaurants, etc., to stimulate customers' emotions from the five senses of eye-catching, listening, smelling, taste, and touching, giving a multi-sensory consumption journey (Murphy, et. al., 2011)

3.4.3.2 High-quality personnel service

The service personnel of the physical stores are very important to the relationship establishment, brand recognition, and purchase advice during the customer's consumption process (Jayachandran, Kaufman, Kumar and Hewett, 2013). According to the "2017 Total Retail Report", high-quality shop assistants with technical and related product knowledge can provide customised suggestions, and even actively invite customers to visit the store to provide unique customer care services such as warm greetings, dressing consultants, itinerary consultation, and after-sales service, to produce the most important differentiated experience in the consumption process (Deloitte, 2018).

3.4.3.3 Apply emerging technologies to enhance experience services.

Qinye Zhongxin United Accounting Firm's "2018 Retail Power and Trend Outlook" report pointed out that various emerging technologies such as AR/VR, IoT and AI. are gradually being widely used in retail scenarios, and the omnichannel consumption model is in major international retail markets (Deloitte, 2018). With rapid fermentation, retailers in major economies in various countries are gradually implementing online and offline integration through data science applications, data exploration and smart management, such as the US retail giant Amazon, China's Alibaba Group, and Japan's Aeon Group (Zhao, 2021).

3.4.4 Overseas expansion

Taiwanese chain brands have an insufficient voice in the international market. Interbrand announced the “2017 Taiwan’s Top 20 International Brands”. Service industry brands accounted for less than 20% (Chen, 2017). According to World Trade Organisation (WTO) data, Taiwan’s service exports in 2017 only reached 45 billion U.S. dollars, accounting for only 0.9% of the global share. Ranked 27 in the world, it shows that Taiwan's service industry still has a lot of room for growth in international brand awareness and service output performance. Because the authorised brand has not reached international reputation and cannot demonstrate brand value, the partners have not been able to obtain substantial support from the headquarters, which affects the dependence and trust on the brand (Chen, 2017). Under the condition of being unable to effectively control the partners, it is easy to be copied by the local franchisee to replace the local development opportunities after the expiration of the term.

Furthermore, other countries such as Japan, South Korea, and Malaysia, all participate in the exhibition in an international-scale team to form an image pavilion, unified design presentation, and joint publicity to jointly promote the national image and corporate links and make the overall brand voice and impression quite profound (Altenburg, et al., 2016). In terms of catering, compared with Korean food and Thai international kitchens, Taiwanese national cuisine has a weaker image, which slows down the pace of international expansion. The Taiwan Franchise Promotion Association stated that since most of Taiwan's franchise industry is dominated by small and medium-sized retail and catering businesses (ACFPT, 2021), if there is no thoughtful thinking and planning during the internationalisation process, a high degree of operation and management risk is likely to occur due to limited resources. Before the brand has reached a certain level of international sound volume, there are often the following three management issues in overseas deployment (e-volunteer, 2021).

3.4.4.1 Weak overseas authorisation management

When an enterprise conducts international authorisation with limited resources, there is a shortage of international talents at the headquarters. The inability to systematically conduct product development, system training, authorisation, and management results in

the inability to consider the development of overseas business or assign appropriate teams to local management, provide adequate counselling and logistics support for overseas franchisees, and it is difficult to effectively control the development and management of overseas markets (Settembre-Blundo, et al., 2021). Overseas in Taiwanese brand stores, the good and the bad are mixed, causing a negative impact, but causing harm to the "Taiwan's high-quality image."

3.4.4.2 Suitable partners are difficult to discover.

To effectively expand overseas markets, if Chinese chain companies can find suitable local companies to cooperate, they will not only reduce the market entry barriers, such as local political factors, consumption levels, habitual preferences, regulatory restrictions, etc., but also enjoy relative convenience and preferential treatment (Reisch, et al., 2013). However, Taiwan's chain and catering companies are facing overseas development opportunities and lack a complete standard and mechanism for selecting suitable agents. As a result, there are often exchanges and negotiations but subsequent failures. (e-volunteer, 2021)

3.4.4.3 Strong demand for talents in international layout

According to the estimated data of the 2016 Chain Industry Business Survey, the annual growth rate of new employees in the chain industry is 5.6%, and each company grows an average of 24 people each year; the demand for talents from 2017 to 2019 in the region is 47,000 (Moea, 2018). Domestic chain and catering companies need to strengthen their mastery of overseas consumer demand. According to the 2018 "Global Service Trade Trends and Taiwan's Service Industry External Expansion Projects" of the Institute of Business Development, the success of cross-border services depends on consumers' consumption habits. For consumers, their preferences have similar culture, religion, and Services with features such as language.

Therefore, it is quite difficult for chain and catering companies to enter overseas markets, restricted by potential factors such as cultural customs, geographical environment, etc., to successfully respond to the needs of consumers in the target market (FTC, 2021). In addition, foreign investment regulations, operating regulations, local base establishment

conditions, professional qualifications of service personnel, and capital flow restrictions in the target market hinder chain and catering brands from entering overseas markets and limit the possibility of brand service exports. Therefore, if you do not fully understand the business conditions and regulations of the target market, relying solely on experience or Taiwan's business model, it is likely to violate local laws and regulations and affect authorisation or exhibition store planning. This is also a weak link for Taiwanese companies in their international development (e-volunteer, 2021).

The global catering market continues to grow, and the global layout of Taiwan's catering requires the integration of representative cuisines. All food kingdoms throughout the world will have representative foods, such as French cuisine, Japanese cuisine, Thai world kitchens, and Korean food. They have clear items and tastes, which can be used to attract international tourists and export food. Although Taiwanese cuisine has been highly praised and loved by people internationally, due to its wide variety, it is out of focus and cannot be developed substantially like other countries (Chen, 2021). For example, bubble tea, Taiwanese fried chicken, braised pork rice, etc., are deeply rooted in the hearts of the people. Export sales are successful, but the representativeness of items of Taiwanese cuisine in the international catering market are still insufficient, meaning Taiwanese cuisines have a weaker image of national cuisine compared to Korean food and Thai international kitchens, and slowing down the international expansion of Taiwan's catering industry (Chen, 2021).

With the international development of Taiwan's catering and the continued growth of chain enterprises, the lack of consistent standards for Taiwanese cuisine (such as the combination of ingredients, the use of seasonings, and cooking methods) has weakened the taste and representativeness of Taiwanese cuisine and catering at home and abroad. This, in turn, has also affected the brand image of "Taiwanese Food" (Chen, 2021).

3.4.5 Social participation and policy communication

With the rapid changes in the internal and external environment and the diversification of industrial demand, it will be made good use of industrial operation data to expand social

participation and understand the status of the chain industry to then formulate its applicable management methods and innovation models (NielsenIQ, 2018). This will drive the development of the overall chain and catering industry, increase the relevant employment population, and drive the overall economic and social development (e-volunteer, 2021). After communicating with experts from all walks of life, including Taiwan Franchise and Franchise Association, Taiwan Franchise Promotion Association, Republic of China National Chamber of Commerce, Business Development Research Institute, Republic of China Foreign Trade Development Association, China Food Association, Taiwan International Young Chef Association, etc. The unit, based on counselling and international development, has compiled the following opinion form (TTR, 2021). When facing issues such as internal and external industrial environment, international market expansion opportunities, etc., companies can assist other companies to strengthen their internal operating capabilities in terms of management, upgrading and transformation. At the same time, after the company has established itself, it can build an overseas exchange platform and provide multiple media exchanges. Opportunities to help Taiwanese companies continue to successfully expand overseas markets (TWSE, 2021).

Table 6 Consolidation of opinions from industry and academia

	Counselling	International expansion
Industry	The introduction of technology management coaching tools is necessary, but usability, convenience, and cost are three major considerations. As the headquarters gradually expanded, it faced many challenges in store management. Taiwan's service industries are mostly faced with supply-side problems such as small scale of operation, low R&D energy, insufficient talents, insufficient competitiveness, and low expansion capabilities.	Talents are hard to find, and the turnover rate is high, requiring systematic training. Small and medium-sized enterprises face no relevant international management majors. It should assist the local linkage of the industry's overseas exports and provide one-stop service.
Academia	There should be corresponding counselling methods based on the scale of the enterprise.	To promote the international market in the future, we may face more differences in languages and cultures and difficulties in talents. Look for countermeasures.

Source from: (TTR, 2020)

3.4.6 The type of American franchise system

The main ways for American companies to join are the following, Products distribution franchising, Business format franchising and Management franchising.

Products distribution franchising. Through supply and distribution methods, franchise stores sell or distribute products of franchise owners. Franchise owners only authorise trademarks and logos to franchise stores, and basically do not provide a complete system for operating business. Distributors are the most common form of product distribution franchise. The most common types are vending machines, auto parts repair shops, gas stations, and convenience stores. For example: Coca-Cola, Goodyear Tyre, Sunoco Gas Station, Ford Motor, Exxon Gas Station, Osim etc. Even the charity sector in the UK uses the franchise model with many charity shops operating under a franchise paying a percentage of goods sold to the charity brand.

Business format franchising. At present, most of the most common franchise chain is commercial franchise. That is, after the franchise owner authorises the brand to the franchise store, it operates in accordance with the established business model, and after signing the franchise agreement, the franchise store can not only obtain the franchise owner's products and services, but also obtain the trademark authorisation and operation of the entire set of practices. For example: training / computer system / marketing plan / operation manual, etc. The most common franchise brands in this category are McDonalds, Starbucks, Wendy 's Burger, Jan-Pro cleaning service, Great Clips hairdressing, and Jenny Craig diet meals.

Management franchising. The franchise owners provide professional knowledge of business management operation, such as technology and procedures Well-known brands include Hilton, American Idol, UPS, Comfort Inn. The Federal Trade Commission has established the Franchise Rule Compliance Guide.

3.4.7 The experience of promoting franchise chain business in North American countries.

The development of franchising in North America has a long history and has always been very prosperous. According to statistics, there are currently about 3,000 franchise brands in the United States, offering goods or services across 250 industries. In Canada, the annual sales of the franchise industry are as high as 100 billion Canadian dollars, which is about 10% of Canada's GDP and accounts for about 40% of national retail sales. There are 78,000 franchise businesses across Canada, with a total of more than 1 million people directly employed³⁴. According to the unofficial estimates of the Canadian Franchise Association, about 20% of the money spent by Canadian consumers on the purchase of goods or services is from franchise operators.

The Franchise Canada Magazine published a survey report by the Canadian Franchise Association (CFA), in February 2009 on the latest franchise trends, in the Canadian franchise industry. Several important trends include: (1) The retail performance of the beauty and cosmetics industries continued to grow, reaching a growth rate of 44% as of January 2009. The subsequent growth potential is not affected by the economic recession and remains optimistic; (2) The increasing number of people in Canada who start their own businesses has led to the growing prosperity of the entrepreneurial consulting, consultants, and corporate education and training industries.

In 2008, the growth rate exceeded 40%. Instead, they grew against the trend in the wave of economic recession. (3) Coffee, bread, bakery, and pastry industries have not seen a decline. Instead, they have grown by 28%, showing that people's daily consumption behaviours may still become potential business opportunities for franchise; (4) In 2008 industries related to health, fitness, nutrition, and health care have also grown by 21%. This includes 24-hour fitness centres, physical fitness courses, weight loss and nutrition consulting industries; and (5) Quick Service Restaurants (QSR) in busy industrialised societies and metropolitan cities where rapid growth, coupled with the increasing popularity of Canadian families buying out-of-home food ("eating out at home"), saw a growth rate of 9%. In 2009, the franchise of such restaurants increased from 129 to 140. According to estimates, the success rate of franchising is about 2.5 times that of other forms of newly created businesses, and the primary industries of franchising are: fast

food, retail, service industry, automobile, maintenance, restaurant, construction, food retail, business services, and accommodation.

The table 7 and the figures 4-5 shows that the largest franchise chain brand and franchise stores in the U.S.

Table 7 The largest franchise chain brand in the U.S.

Top 10 franchisers (brands)	Number of stores
McDonald's	30,300
Yum (Taco Bell, KFC)	29,300
7-Eleven	28,200
Cendant (Century 21; Avis Rent-a-Car)	24,600
Subway	21,000
Burger King	11,200
H&R Block	11,200
Jani King	11,000
Dunkin Brands (Baskin Robbins, Dunkin Donuts)	10,800
Curves	8,700

Source form: IFA <http://www.franchisedirect.com/information/>
 Figure 4 Average franchise cost in the U.S.

Source from: International Franchise Association's 'Profile of Franchising' Report 2006

Figure 5 The average cost of investing in franchised businesses in the U.S.

Source from: International Franchise Association's 'Profile of Franchising' Report 2006

Within all industries, the education service industry has the lowest franchise fees, which means the minimum investment required; the tourism service industry-related franchise investment funds rank fifth; children-related franchise investment ranks the ninth lowest. For women, a lower franchise fee can reduce the investment cost of establishing franchise stores, so this area is especially popular with women. After the initial franchise fee, the average franchise chain industry still must pay an average of 6.7% royalty fee, and an average of about 5% of advertising expenses.

3.4.8 Experience in promoting franchise chain business in Asian countries.

Although franchise chain development is one of the indicators of advanced countries, in recent years, Asian countries have increased their national income year by year and domestic demand-oriented service industries have developed rapidly, which has led to the vigorous development of franchise businesses. According to the "2008 Global Retail Development Index" (Global Retail Development Index) issued by the well-known American market research company AT Kearney, selection Ranked among the top 30 retail markets in the world, were neighbouring countries such as Vietnam, China, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Thailand, with the Philippines top of the list. For China's wholesale and retail and its franchise businesses to expand into the international market, it should provide an important market base.

In terms of Vietnam, which ranks as the world's most potential retail market, it ranked fourth in the world's top 30 retail markets in 2007. By 2008, Vietnam became the world's largest retail market. Its appeal to Taiwan's retail and wholesale industry has long been domestically attractive. All are optimistic. Taiwanese businessmen have invested in Vietnam since the late 1980s, and in 2008 ranked first in Vietnam's foreign investment. Although Taiwanese businessmen entered Vietnam earlier than other foreign-funded enterprises, most of them were concentrated in the manufacturing industry, using Vietnam as a production base for exporting to the European and American markets. In line with the opening up of the domestic market in Vietnam, domestic distribution companies can go to Vietnam to seek development opportunities. In particular, Taiwan's franchise industry is booming and has a great competitive advantage.

Vietnam has a total population of more than 84 million people, and more than 90% of the population is under the age of 65 with consumption potential. In 2006, the average national income was about 720 U.S. dollars, but the average national income of Ho Chi Minh City, a major commercial city, exceeded 2,000 U.S. dollars, and in the capital, Hanoi, also exceeded 1,500 U.S. dollars.

Thanks to the rapid economic development in recent years, some people have gradually formed a "new wealthy class" with higher income. Brands are the primary consideration for consumption of this class. Brands such as Europe, America, Japan, and South Korea are currently very popular. For example, in recent years, Vietnam's consumption power for high-priced electronic products has increased. Consumer electronic products with higher unit prices, such as mobile phones, LCD-TVs, and computers, have great market potential. In addition, imported high-end garments, apparel, cosmetics, watches, toys, etc. An important market for manufacturers from all over the world.

Traditional Vietnamese stores or markets are gradually transforming into a modernized business process. Most of the convenience stores are transformed from traditional grocery stores, lacking modern professional knowledge, the density of Taiwan's convenience store system, diversified services, integration, and innovation, etc. The successful business model is in line with the current development needs of Vietnam; the renewal and upgrade of related commercial facilities, as well as the related equipment and knowledge of refrigeration, storage, transportation, logistics management, etc., are

all potential markets with huge business opportunities. The Taiwanese franchise industry is extremely local and has the competitive advantage.

However, due to the long-term implementation of the planned economy in Vietnam, the development of the domestic market has been restricted. As far as the retail industry is concerned, it is still dominated by traditional stores and bazaars. The way is also backward. According to estimates by the Vietnamese government, there are about 9,000 existing retail markets in Vietnam, of which 75% are rural markets. As for modern retail locations such as shopping malls, supermarkets, and chain stores, they have not yet formed a scale. They are mainly concentrated in Ho Chi Minh City, Hanoi, Haiphong, and big cities such as Da Nang.

According to estimates, in Vietnam's national merchandise retail performance, traditional stores and rural cities account for about 80-85%, while modern shopping malls and supermarkets account for only 10-15%. However, it is worth noting that Vietnam's retail industry has developed in recent years. Food outlets, large supermarkets, mass merchandisers, chain stores, etc. have great room for growth. It is estimated that by 2010, supermarket business volume is expected to account for 20% of the Vietnamese retail market.

In accordance with Vietnam's commitment to the WTO, Vietnam's domestic market will gradually open after joining the conference, and foreign businessmen can engage in wholesale, retail, and franchise businesses of domestic and imported products in Vietnam. In addition, according to the market survey results jointly conducted by the market research company GfK and the Vietnam branch of AC Nielsen, taking household appliances as an example, the current annual retail value of household appliances in Vietnam is approximately US\$1.3 billion. The demand for home appliances is strong, and it is estimated that its annual retail sales can rapidly increase to US\$3 billion. In 2008, China ranked fourth among the top 30 retail markets in the world. China's huge population and rapidly growing urban middle class have made its wholesale and retail markets a must-see for all countries in recent years.

According to statistics from the Ministry of Commerce of China, as of November 2008, the total retail sales of consumer goods in the Chinese market has exceeded the 10

trillion-yuan mark. It is expected to reach 10.8 trillion yuan in 2008, an increase of 21% from 2008. To strive for the domestic wholesale and retail markets that have been opened since China's accession to the World Trade Organisation (WTO), Taiwanese companies have long used their advantages in investing in social factories and close contacts on the mainland, deploying heavy forces on the other side and actively deploying them in various places. For example, Runtai Group owns RT-Mart's circulation business in mainland China. In 2008, it successfully reached the "100 stores in 10 years" target of opening 100 franchise stores in mainland China within 10 years, and further studied its share exchange with its shareholder Auchan Group. Work, planning to be listed on the Hong Kong stock market. RT-Mart has recently formulated a five-year plan, which is expected to increase its turnover to RMB 104.1 billion in 2012, which will surpass the market size of the Taiwanese channel by then.

In addition, Uni-President 7-ELEVEN, a subsidiary of Uni-President Enterprise Group, opened four locations in Shanghai on April 30 (2009) It is expected to start making profits after four years of operation and will reach the goal of opening 300 stores within five years. Target. Taiwanese companies are actively entering the mainland's wholesale and retail markets. However, because the mainland's relevant laws and regulations are not complete and there is a lack of transparency, they often rely on the assistance of relevant units on both sides of the strait. According to a statistical survey completed by the Taiwan Franchise Promotion Association in the first half of 2008, there are currently about 186 headquarters of domestic chain brands developing into the international market, and about 43,000 overseas branches.

In addition, Taiwanese companies have deployed the Chinese mainland market earlier than European and American companies. Therefore, many of China's well-known franchise brands have their origins in Taiwan, such as Xinyi Housing, Xianzonglin Restaurant Chain, Blue Sky Computer, etc. The Chinese market has become Taiwan's franchise chain industry to enter the outside of Taiwan. Except for the Vietnam and China markets, Hong Kong's economy is dominated by the service industry. The service industry accounts for 90% of Hong Kong's GDP. The retail industry, together with restaurants, hotels, wholesale, and import and export trade, account for 27.5% of the GDP and is the largest service industry in Hong Kong.

Since 2005, the total retail sales in Hong Kong have exceeded 200 billion Hong Kong dollars, and the number of employees is about 240,000. If calculated with the catering industry, the number of employees is more than 450,000. As a major service industry in Hong Kong, the Hong Kong Retail Management Association believes that Hong Kong should continue to improve the skills, status and professionalism of retail practitioners, maintain the long-term competitiveness of the industry, and highlight Hong Kong's image as Asia's premier financial, service centre and shopping paradise.

According to the statistics of the Association Franchise Indonesia, the total turnover of Indonesian franchise companies in 2006 was approximately US\$6 billion, which was double the US\$3 billion in 2001. There were more than 450 franchise brands in 2006. Among these, there are more than 220 foreign brands and more than 230 local brands of which restaurants, cafes, bakeries, etc. are the most common. Others such as retail stores, cram schools, beauty salons, and real estate agencies are also important franchise industries.

Although the development of the franchise industry in Indonesia started late, because Indonesia has a huge consumer market of 240 million people, it is expected that it will be the market with the most growth potential for the franchise industry in the future. In this regard, the Indonesian government plans several measures to promote the development of franchise chain industry, especially hoping to relieve the pressure of the economic downturn.

Southeast Asian countries including Hong Kong, Indonesia, and Vietnam, as well as other Asian countries such as China, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, etc., have, in recent years have actively promoted wholesale and retail, catering and other franchise businesses, and the government has provided many assistance and guidance measures, including strengthening Relevant legal system, training franchise talents, providing preferential loan programs for enterprises or micro-enterprises, etc. Among them, Malaysia has allocated 100 million MYR to develop 1,000 new chain stores for the development of franchise businesses; the South Korean government has set a goal to train 3,000 franchise professionals each year, and the national treasury will bear 50% of the training costs.

In addition, the Singaporean government not only partially bears the cost of external

consultants to assist enterprises or the public in investing in franchise businesses and has set up the "Singapore Quality Award" to commend outstanding companies, as well as the "Innovation and Development Award" and the "Singapore Service" "Quality Award", etc., to respectively commend enterprises with innovation and excellent service.

3.4.9 East Asian countries' policies and promote.

The table 8 shows how east Asian countries support franchise businesses.

Table 8 East Asian countries' policies to promote franchise chain industry.

Country	Industry Promotion Organisation	Promotion Content
Singapore	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Government units: Singapore Bureau of Standards, Singapore Innovation Board, Singapore International Enterprise Development Board * Non-governmental organisation: Singapore Productivity Organisation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conduct domestic and international industry exchanges through seminars and symposiums. 2. Provide various diagnostic consulting services. 3. Provide preferential loan programs for growing companies or micro-enterprises. 4. The government partly bears the cost of external consultants for enterprises. 5. Set up the "Singapore Quality Award" to recognise outstanding companies. <p>"Innovation and Development Award" and "Singapore Service Quality Award" respectively commend innovative and excellent service companies.</p>
Malaysia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Government unit: Ministry of Enterprise Development of Malaysia * Non-governmental organisation: Malaysia Chain Association 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Allocate 100 million MYR to develop 1,000 new chain stores. 2. The association provides a variety of education, training, exhibitions, and at the same time acts as a contact unit between domestic industries and other related organisations abroad. 3. 1998 The "Chain Act" was passed and implemented.
Japan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Civil organisations: Japan Chain Store Association, Japan Authorised Chain Store Association, Japan Retail Industry Association 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Franchise contract review 2. Maintain the domestic chain system 3. Provide counseling 4. Handle education and training 5. Handle domestic and foreign exchange activities
South Korea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Government unit: Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Energy of Korea * Civil organisations: Korea Franchise Business Cooperative Association, Korea Chain Store Association, Korea Franchise Association, Korea Supermarket Cooperative Association 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Train 3,000 professional franchisees each year, and the national treasury will bear 50% of the training costs. 2. Promote a three-year plan to normalise the franchise business. 3. Promote the recognition of the "Sunshine Village" brand products with low price and good quality and encourage purchase at franchise stores. 4. Promote and implement joint procurement, sales and facility utilization, etc.

Source from: Ministry of Economic Affairs, R.O.C. in Taiwan.

3.4.10 The type of Japanese franchise system

"Taiwan-Japanese rule" refers to the period when Taiwan was ruled by Japan from 1895 to 1945 (Yao, 2019). From 50 years of Japanese rule resulted in, leaving behind many Japanese cultures. And Japan is geographically very close to Taiwan. There are many business activities, and in the franchise system, most of them use the Japanese franchise type to operate (Lin, et al.,2020). In fact, there are many different types of "chain stores", and the definition of various types of chain stores mostly imitates the Japanese model. If the classification is based on the outline, the chain stores can be divided into four types:

1. Regular chain (RC). All sales points are funded by the headquarters, so the decision-making power, and management power are owned by the head office. The product mix of each branch is the same or similar, and the source of supply is determined by the head office. All decisions can be executed most thoroughly and with the highest degree of standardisation. The capital required by the headquarters is quite large and the relative risk is high. For example: Unified Supermarket Direct Store.

2. Voluntary chain (VC). Most of these stores already exist. The chain headquarters provides professional management assistance for franchisees and the use of CIS (Corporate Identification System). The franchisee pays franchise rights to the headquarters. The franchisee commits to purchase a certain percentage of products from the headquarters. This form of franchise and franchise owner have complete management rights and autonomy, so it is not easy to control the franchise owner. The franchisee voluntarily joins the head office chain system. Since the franchise stores existed before joining, they joined the chain system one by one for the sake of good image trademarks and low purchase costs.

3. Franchise chain (FC). Franchise chain is between the above two methods. Usually, the franchisee and the headquarters share the cost of setting up the store. The rent and decoration of the store are mostly the responsibility of the franchisee, and the headquarters is responsible for the production equipment. In this way, the franchisee also It needs to share profits with the headquarters, and the headquarters also has control over the franchisee, but because the franchisee has also paid a considerable fee, the profit is higher, and it also has some suggestions and powers to decide on the format of

the store. Most convenience store systems in Japan operate in this way.

Founded by the franchisee with funding, the headquarters provides the overall design including trademarks, commodities, business technology and symbolic headquarters. Ownership of the franchise store is independent of the right to operate, but the headquarter franchise fee, royalties, security deposit, start-up costs and signing fee, etc. must be paid. Headquarters must give continuous guidance and assistance to franchisees within the contract period, and franchisees are also obliged to abide by the regulations and restrictions of the headquarters. The headquarters of the open franchise must be very careful in control and supervision, otherwise it will easily lead to management defects, such as Dante Cafe, Doutor Cafe, etc.

4. Cooperate chain (CC). Most of the reasons for joining are to form against large chain stores. It is automatically initiated and jointly purchased by retailers to strive for preferential purchase prices. Each retailer is a shareholder and can participate in decision-making. A contract between the headquarters and franchise stores clearly defines rights and obligations.

5. Assign Chain (AC). These franchisers are willing to operate on behalf of the operators. The headquarters will provide old direct stores or new stores to franchisees, and help franchisees to pay for decoration, some equipment, and other expenses. The franchise owner of this franchise method not only has to pay the franchise and security deposit to the headquarters, but also the profits must be paid to the headquarters in accordance with the agreed ratio. The franchiser responsible for recruiting franchisees, store management and some management and marketing fees.

Table 9 Chain franchise types

	Regular chain	Voluntary chain	Franchise chain	Cooperate chain	Assign Chain
Sponsor	Manufacturers, retailers, wholesalers, and services	Manufacturer, wholesaler	Manufacturers, retailers, wholesalers, and services	Retailers	Manufacturers, retailers, wholesalers, and services
Funds	Headquarters	Franchisee	Franchisee	Franchisee	Both
Store ownership	Headquarters	Franchisee	Franchisee	Franchisee	Headquarters
Operating rights	Non- independent	Independent	independent	independent	Non- independent
Store operator	Headquarters appointment	Independent of the owner	Independent of the owner	Independent of the owner	Independent of the owner
Employment rights	Headquarters	Franchisee	Franchisee	Franchisee	Franchisee
Profits attributable	Headquarters	Franchisee	Partly paid to the head office	Franchisee	Partly paid to the head office
Price	Headquarters	Free	headquarters	Free	Headquarters
Commodity supply source	Headquarters	In principle, the head office will purchase the goods, but few commodities can be ordered by franchisee.	Purchased or recommended by the head office	In principle, the head office will purchase the goods, but few commodities can be ordered by franchisee.	Purchased or recommended by the head office
Store image appearance	Identical	Can be modified	Identical	Can be modified	Identical

Source from: author collation

Table 9 Chain franchise types- continue.

	Regular chain	Voluntary chain	Franchise chain	Cooperate chain	Assign Chain
Decision making	Headquarters	Based on franchise, the company views for reference only	Based on headquarter, but franchisee can advise	Franchisee shareholders	Headquarters
Franchise fee payment	None	Yes	Pay franchise and technical remuneration	Pay a certain amount of fees	Yes
Know-how/ training	Full training	Free use	Full training	None	Full training
Guide	Specialised staff tour guide	Free use	Specialised staff tour guide	None	Specialised staff tour guide
Means of competition	Not necessarily	price competition	Differentiation	price competition	Differentiation
Promotion	Headquarters unified implementation	Free	Headquarters unified implementation	Free	Headquarters unified implementation
Head office control	Fully control (The strongest)	Weak binding on franchise stores (weak)	Strong binding force on franchise stores (strong)	Headquarters are of a service nature (weakest)	Strong binding force on the franchise store (second strongest)
Relationship with head office	Fully integrated	Community of goods sources	Community of business ideas	Mutual aid community	Community of business ideas
Basis for cooperation	Relationship between headquarters and branches	Contract	Contract	Service-oriented, supplemented by contract	contract
Growth in the number of chain stores	Slower	Faster	Faster	Faster	Slower
Headquarters revenue source	Operating income	Wholesale trading income	Franchise fee, technical compensation, and business operating bonus	Service fee	Technical compensation and business operating bonus

Source from: author collation

3.4.11 Pros and Cons of chain types.

The table 10 shows the advantages and disadvantages of various chain types.

Table 10 Advantages and disadvantages of chain types

Chain types	Abbreviation	Advantages	disadvantages
Regular chain	RC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Centralisation of ownership and management rights makes it easy to exert economic scale benefits. 2. Purchase in large quantities and enjoy quantity discounts and low shipping costs. 3. Expand the scale of operation, could hire excellent management talents, and improve the operation efficiency. 4. Collective wholesale and retail functions. 5. The same advertisement can be used to share the advertising expenses together. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The investment amount is huge 2. High risk 3. Poor adaptability when external environment changes suddenly
Voluntary chain	VC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Less investment. 2. Risk diversification. 3. Unified procurement, expand the quantity of procurement to reduce costs. 4. Sovereignty belongs to each store, 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The chain headquarters has no absolute binding force on franchise stores, and it is easy to be reduced to their own development and lose their overall interests. 2. It is difficult to create a uniform and distinct contract image 3. The uneven quality of the store owner also affects the overall chain's business image
Franchise chain	FC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It has the advantages of regular chain and voluntary joining. 2. No need to bring your own funds when expanding. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The contract sanction is adopted. If the headquarters or franchise stores find legal loopholes in the contract, it will also easily affect the benefits of the department. 2. The continuous expansion of franchise stores may result in an oligopolistic or exclusive image
Cooperate chain	CC	At various levels of store operations, such as purchases, advertisements, or promotions, joint operations can be used to increase the efficiency of operations.	The lack of a strong and advantageous headquarters provides management technical guidance, so it is easy to cause differences of opinion, and the system and strategy are difficult to promote, which is the most difficult type of management.
Assign Chain	AC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No decoration and equipment fees required 2. the store be provided by headquarter. 3. the location has existing customers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. headquarter will charge percentage of the turnover. 2. only can sell the headquarter products.

Source from: author collation

3.5 Global current catering status of franchise & development

According to the International Franchise Association (IFA)'s "2015 Franchise Industry Economic Outlook Report", commissioned by the market regulator HIS Global insight, the rapid growth of the US franchise industry has exceeded the nation's GDP growth rate for five consecutive years. The franchised industry accounts for 3% of the nation's GDP, and economic output grew by about 5.4% to reach US \$ 889 billion. American fast-food catering is the overlord of the franchise industry. New job opportunities in the franchise industry were 248,000, an increase of 2.9% to 8,816,000 jobs, and the fastest growth in fast food restaurants and retail industry, of which 65% of the manpower was distributed in the food and catering industries; 29% was in the service industry; 6% in the real estate and automotive industry. The average investment for the first franchise is US \$ 250,000, the average monthly payment of franchise payment is about 3% -6% of the gross profit, most of the franchise stores are less than 100, and the average franchise contract period is 10 years. Within the fast-food restaurant industry, McDonald's is the nation's largest franchiser. (MOEA, 2015)

The franchise industry has changed a lot in the past five years. Many franchisees of regular franchise and regional developers have adopted high-tech tools to expand their marketing activities and have been operating cautiously in a downturn. The rise of multi-generation partnerships and the establishment of inter-generational connection architectures in business organisations, such as the NextGen project promoted by the IFA, is the combination of the passion, vitality, and familiarity of technology by millennials with the experience of baby boomers and a financial stability. To improve the relationship between franchiser and franchisees becoming the successful partnership business. Mobile networks are ubiquitous.

Due to the convenience and popularity of mobile networks, many companies have combined mobile communications with the company's marketing strategy. The franchise industry has actively developed mobile apps and used SMS marketing to win more customers. By paying attention to the community, social media has become a superior channel, and customers' opinions are given more attention, because the franchise owners and franchise stores need to establish their own communities to be able to immediately respond to customer opinions and provide more discounts for loyal customers. This connection also allows them to carry

out various types of online promotional discounts.

In April 2020, the British economy contracted by a record 20.4% due to the UK lockdown, causing irreparable damage to many families and businesses. Throughout the lockdown process, statistics also show that the economy is expected to decline by a quarter due to the general contraction of the entire economy (McGaun, 2020). The industry that was hit hardest during the COVID-19 recession was hospitality, whose growth rate reached a peak of minus 40%. John Gathergood, a professor of economics at the University of Nottingham, has an equally daunting view; he supposed that "By the end of the fiscal year 2020/2021, the government is most likely to owe debt for more than one year of all the value of its economy."

On June 23, 2020, the Ministry of Economic Affairs (MOEA) stated that Taiwan's food and beverage section grew at a monthly growth rate of 29% per month in May, the largest monthly increase in history (Wang & Mazzetta, 2020). According to data from MOEA, the sales of food and beverage suppliers in May increased by 29% to 61.9 billion New Taiwan dollars (2.1 billion U.S. dollars), although this figure was down 8.7% from the 67.9 billion New Taiwan dollars in the same month last year. Despite this, retail revenue fell by 5.8% from the NT\$319.5 billion in May 2019, mainly due to the slowdown in tourism. MOEA said that due to the weak global demand caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, exports suffered losses. Sales of the wholesale sector in May 2020 fell 6.8% from the same period last year to NT\$795.7 billion (Wang & Mazzetta, 2020).

3.5.1 The benefits of the franchise system

1. Shorten the exploration period of entrepreneurship.
2. Headquarters provides pre-employment education and training and assists in shop preparation.
3. No higher education or any professional skills required.
4. Entrepreneurship can be more civilian, without higher education, license, and experience, as long as you are willing and willing to learn, plus some management changes, transfer the headquarters of the management knowledge, step by step to internalise your skills, and join the chain store. Set up a Know-how system, and set up shop and business departments, greatly reducing the threshold for entry.

5. Allows entrepreneurs to concentrate on store operations.
6. In the face of personnel issues, restaurant chain operators simplified the in-field operations to be able to dine without a professional chef. The in-field lineup is strong and rotates frequently, and there is a store-to-store support mechanism, so it is not only a human problem to control management problems. Problems, such as new product development, promotional activities, logistics and distribution, store business information, etc., let entrepreneurs have no worries.
7. The power of franchise joint ventures outperforms singles, which reduces the chance of entrepreneurial failure.
8. Provides the trademark, goodwill and Know-How of the headquarters, possess the goodwill and popularity of the chain enterprises, and show the brand benefits.
9. The headquarters provides information about the company to facilitate the formulation of operating policies.
10. The head office performs site selection work to find a good place to open a store.
11. Headquarters provides Research & Design of commodities.
12. Headquarters assists in the purchase of commodities and raw materials.
13. Reduce store opening time and operating costs.

The operating cost of chain companies is 15-30% lower than the cost of a single store on average. The purchase cost is also 5 to 15% cheaper than that of a single store. Of course, some chain companies insist on the use of specified materials, so the reduced cost that is not seen must be reflected in the price. For instance: Hongye, insist that all decoration materials must use fireproof materials, which is based on safety considerations and is also a part of risk management control.

3.5.2 The weaknesses of the franchise system

Joining a franchise chain system, cannot be arbitrary, involves no choice in decorating the outlet, and it is compulsory to accept and cooperate with management activities. Some franchisees where business is quite good, pull back against the headquarters' promotional activities, do not want to cooperate with the headquarters' promotional activities; but prefer

their own innovations, which is the individualist approach. This may affect the store's operating income at a small level and the goodwill of the entire chain system, which is why many franchisees choose to leave the original franchise system. The reasons for limitation can be divided into the following five categories:

1. Lack of independence
2. It is unlikely to permit your own creativity.
3. Limited supply pipelines
4. No arbitrary transfer
5. There are many businesses restrictions.

3.5.3 Impact of franchise operation on industry, society, and economy

Any kind of industry, especially the comprehensive retail service industry that directly contacts consumers, will gradually adjust its business pattern as the economy develops and consumer habits change (Patwa, et al, 2021). As the pace of consumers' lives grows faster and faster, industries that demand "convenience" have developed rapidly, such as fast-food restaurants, fast printing shops, and convenience stores (Deloitte, 2018).

As society progresses, the finer the division of labour in the industry will appear. The basis is that it meets the "partial" needs of consumers. It is not easy to achieve an industry that wants to fully meet consumer demand in modern times (Kuokkanen & Sun, 2020). After all, consumers are changeable. Convenience stores competed with the grocery stores of the time and stood out (Deloitte, 2018). Not only did they achieve themselves, but they also forced the quality of the grocery stores to change from a crowded, dark, uncertain quality environment to a spacious, bright, fresh quality assurance business form. In the transformation, consumers are the biggest winners (Dzwigol, et al., 2019).

After all, the improvement of consumption environment and quality is the improvement of quality of life (Gatersleben, 2001). Although convenience stores have driven the subversion of the production and sales structure, consumers are the beneficiaries, because when consumers buy high-quality goods, international brands with huge advertising expenditures are no longer the only consideration (Hua, 2019). Cheap and good-quality private brands are

an optional item. And because of the introduction of convenience stores, consumers have another new shopping place in addition to department stores, supermarkets, or speciality stores such as stationery stores, bookstores, and grocery stores (Dissing, et al, 2010). Therefore, even if the market for integrated retail is highly competitive, consumers are still the biggest beneficiaries.

3.6 Crisis management capabilities

3.6.1 Coronavirus disease crisis

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Most people infected with the COVID-19 virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without special treatment. The elderly and people with underlying medical problems such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory diseases, and cancer are more likely to develop serious diseases (WHO, 2020). In the COVID-19 virus crisis in 2020, the Taiwanese government had to make difficult decisions under uncertainty and time constraints. These decisions had to be culturally appropriate and sensitive to the population; Taiwan had learned lessons from the previous SARS experience of 2003, and a public health response mechanism was established to take prompt action for the next crisis. Through early awareness of the crisis, daily briefings to the public and simple health information, the government were able to provide timely, accurate, and transparent information about epidemic, thereby reassuring the public. With the support of a team of well-trained and experienced officials, Taiwan quickly recognised the impending crisis and activated the emergency management agency to respond to the emerging epidemic (Wang, Ng & Brook, 2020).

In terms of sales in the catering industry, before the epidemic, the sales of the catering industry overall had a growth rate of more than 5%. However, due to the impact of the epidemic on the willingness to eat out, the sales growth of the catering industry slowed down in 2020. In 2021, due to the outbreak of the local epidemic and the implementation of the government epidemic plan and the tightening of restrictions on internal use, the sales of the catering industry dropped to 569 billion yuan; while as the number of restaurants in the overall catering industry continued to increase, the decline in turnover made it more difficult for catering operators to operate. However, 2022 has entered the post-epidemic era. With the

loosening of epidemic prevention policies, the public has set off a wave of retaliatory consumption, and with the intervention of various government revitalization measures, the sales of the catering industry have experienced huge growth, with turnover exceeding 600 billion. Exceeding pre-pandemic turnover performance.

Taiwan catering turnover 2018-2022

Source from: Fiscal information Agency

3.6.2 Redesign of business strategies

As the epidemic became more serious in 2021, during the epidemic alert period, due to strict control measures such as prohibiting internal use, the sales of the catering industry declined significantly during the epidemic. However, due to the reliance on delivery platforms during the epidemic, with these platform's high commission fees, coupled with the sharp fluctuations in original product prices during the epidemic, this seriously eroded the profits of the catering industry, leaving operators with meagre profits during the epidemic. Taiwan's franchised restaurant chains have successively announced September results in 2020. Wowprime (2727-TW) and Wacheng (2729-TW) both set new highs in September revenue. Wowprime's third-quarter revenue reached the second highest in a single quarter. The city hit a new single-season high, and the combined revenue of Gourmet (2723-TW) in September reached a single-month high this year, reflecting that most of the catering industry operations have bottomed out and continue to move toward recovery (Wang, 2020). Wowprime company explained that the Taiwan business group paid NT\$ 860 million in September, an annual

increase of 11.58%, and set a new high for the same period for the fifth consecutive month. The revenue in the first three quarters reached NT\$ 7.69 billion, an annual increase of 3.35%, freeing from the shadow of the epidemic; And the Chinese business group's September revenue was RMB¥ 460 million, and the RMB turnover increased by 0.31% annually, which has also returned to the pre-epidemic level (Wang, 2020).

The introduction of technology has changed the business profit model of catering operators, promoted the paradigm shift of the catering industry, and has become an opportunity for catering operators to expand their markets and move towards growth. During the epidemic, large chain catering operators have strengthened their APP membership mechanisms and combined them with online sales of products to better understand customer preferences and improve customer stickiness. They also relied on their brand appeal and influence to launch home delivery services of cooking kits and frozen meals. Or start an e-commerce platform.

3.7 Key points of theories of franchise

3.7.1 Main statements of theories

In the Chapter 2 and Chapter 3, in addition to the analysis of the definition of franchise, are discussed the historical franchise, it started from the USA, so the franchise system in the United States will be discussed, besides this study is in Taiwan, then the franchise system in Taiwan is also discussed. Agency theory and Brand resonance are important to consider in this study, what is more these two theories are often mentioned in many literatures. Other auxiliary theories include Transaction cost theory, social responsibility, Resource dependence and Resource Scarcity theory, Stewardship and Stakeholder theory, and Relational contract theory. It is also explained in Chapter 2 and Chapter 3 that the reason for choosing these auxiliary theories is that this article to study and discuss the variables related to ownership structure and management ownership, one needs to understand their role and purpose. The gaps in research have been identified, managerial ownership structure and company performance appraisal. The key success factors are to understand the process to achieve this goal. Collaboration of franchiser and franchisee from review above has been constructed the theoretical framework shows in the chapter 2.4.1 Theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee, so the next chapter this frame will be used in this research analysis. Moreover, chapter 3, figure 7 Conceptual Framework of Hypothesis shows the link

between company performance, ownership structure as well as the empirical model.

Branding is the only way to succeed in the Catering Industry. Taiwan's overall environment is actually quite friendly to catering entrepreneurship. A newly created catering brand or a regional restaurant can basically survive if it can serve friends or surrounding communities. However, in fact, the success rate of Taiwan's restaurant business is very low. The popular chain restaurant has created the illusion that the business is easy to succeed (Zheng, 2018). In this wave of chain restaurant trends, it can be found that Japanese restaurant brands are a relatively successful case. Taiwan has accepted Japanese colonization in the past and has been influenced by Japanese culture for a long time. The urban texture and eating habits are like Japan. Therefore, Taiwanese people have a higher acceptance of Japanese catering brands. A glimpse of the Japanese catering brands must be stationed in department stores. Carefully study the successful cases of these Japanese catering brands and pay attention to the cultural spirit of the staff plus high efficiency kitchen equipment and processes are important factors in establishing a high-quality catering brand (Zheng, 2018).

"Brand authorisation" means that the licensor allows the licensee to use the brand name, trademark or product features it owns, and may sell its brand or trademark to many domestic or foreign product manufacturers (Quelch, 1985). Brand authorisation is a common way to buy brand equity. By authorising brands to reduce consumers' cautiousness and distrust of new products and stand out in the same product category to expand product sales (Farquhar, 1989). Therefore, Quelch (1985) believes that through brand licensing, the licensee could develop into a national brand, quickly penetrate new markets, share investment risks, increase brand awareness, maximise the profitability of existing product lines, and rejuvenate mature brands. However, improper operation of brand licensing may cause risks, including lack of high-quality control of the brand's authorised products, which will result in damage to the authorised brand, or the authorised company's sale of products in cheap stores will also constitute a brand image. Damage to the authorisation, or failure to obtain the full commitment of the authorised person leads to the impact on the brand image or suspension of the brand authorisation partnership. Therefore, the continuity of brand authorisation is based on the authorised users' willingness to continue to use the brand to prolong profits under the brand authorisation effect (Tauber, 1988).

Brand authorisation is like a buying and selling relationship. If the authoriser and the

authorised person keep their promise to each other, it will help develop a stable relationship (Anderson & Weitz, 1992). Dywer, Schurr and Oh (1987) believe that the commitment in the buying and selling relationship should include three elements: (1) Input: Refers to the willingness of buyers and sellers to provide a considerable level of input. (2) Durability: The buyer and seller are willing to continue to maintain their relationship. (3) Consistency: Refers to the consistency of investment in the trading relationship. Kim and Frazier (1997) believe that the commitment is subject to (1) continuous commitment, that is, the willingness to maintain the relationship between the partners, (2) behavioural commitment, that is, when the partners need it, they can provide timely assistance, (3) emotional commitment, that is, the degree of rapport with each other, is affected by three factors.

Therefore, from the degree of commitment, it can be seen the tendency of relationship members to choose to stay or leave. For franchisees, when the franchise headquarters obtains the promise of the franchise owner, the franchise headquarters will have easier access to market intelligence, and at the same time, it can also obtain strong support from the franchise owner (Anderson, Lodish & Weitz, 1987). In other words, the franchisee obtains the authorisation of a certain brand, so that consumers will come to consume because the brand is familiar, and in the case of profit, the franchise will continue to use the brand to continue the benefits brought by this brand.

3.7.2 Firm performance approach strategy

Franchising helps reduce the risk of small businesses by leveraging the resources of the franchiser and the franchiser community operating under the same brand to provide a supportive environment. When the franchiser goes bankrupt, their franchisees will usually not survive because functions such as marketing, supply chain logistics, IT and other core activities that combine the networks may be revoked or completely stop. Again, the biggest risk for franchisees to fail is in newer, start-up franchisees, but even mature brands sometimes fail, such as Angus and Robertson in 2011, and Clay in 2008, and Kleinmed (Gehrke, 2016). In hospitality journals, several papers have looked at the correlation between managerial ownership (MO) and company performance (Chung, 2017; Park and Jang, 2010). Looking at results shown in financial and strategic management papers, these writings show that managerial ownership influences company results once an optimal level of managerial ownership exists. Interestingly, only one paper has demonstrated the influences of

managerial ownership on measures other than company performance. Paek, et al. (2013) show that managerial ownership adversely affects CSR responsibility directed at staff in American hospitality companies. To the best of my knowledge, no studies have explored links between managerial ownership and strategic risk-taking in the hospitality industry, although the outcomes of managerial ownership on company performance is often understood when looking at a company's risk-taking behaviour (Wright, et al., 1996).

Unlike company performance that is complicated, diverse, and directed by many other instruments (Hodak, 2005; Wright, et al., 1996), strategic risk-taking is a more typical path of managerial ownership, which directly determines a company's financial success and longevity (Wright, et al., 1996). So, by studying the result of equity ownership by corporate members on company risk-taking, it be built upon existing knowledge of the direct results of managerial ownership in the written hospitality papers. Our studies will offer the restaurant sector with new understandings of the role executive stock ownership exercises in encouraging managers to import working practices that are in the shareholders' best interests (Rhou, et al., 2019).

As the franchise system evolves, it is necessary for managers to assess how the system works and demonstrate system performance from the perspective of each partnership. For this assessment, franchisers can use criteria for assessing franchise performance for special transactions, such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and measurement of intangible assets (García-García, et al., 2016; Koh, et al., 2009; Sun and Li, 2013). In order to assess partnership performance, franchisers must use measures to measure the success or failure of franchise relationships and factors that determine franchise performance. Contracts can reduce inconsistencies and improve performance measurement (Sande and Haugland, 2015). This new model of international franchising allows partnerships to become a dynamic process. Standards must be evaluated based on financial and qualitative measures that require ongoing monitoring to Maintain trust, commitment, and ensure the viability of its performance (Rosado-Serrano & Paul, 2008).

3.8 Chapter Summary

From the review above it can be seen that the food industry is the most active industry in franchising; after all, it has established a track record of success, providing franchisees with

a wide range of opportunities to provide substantial support to businesses. For those looking for scalable business opportunities, the catering industry may also be an ideal choice. Successful franchisees usually develop from one ownership to multiple ownership. This option is particularly suitable for larger and faster-growing chain stores and can bring a very profitable future to those who meet the conditions (FranchiseDirect, 2020). The catering industry suffered severe setbacks during the epidemic. However, in the post-epidemic era, epidemic prevention policies have gradually withdrawn, life has gradually returned to normal, and the development of the catering industry has also shown signs of hope. During the epidemic, catering operators have continuously strengthened their physical fitness, developed new brands, invested in digital transformation, combined online and offline business models and many other efforts, and have laid a good foundation for the development of the catering industry. In the future, catering operators will continue to use data analysis, consumer insights and other tools to grasp the pulse of consumer demand, explore demand gaps and provide catering services that meet demand, enhance the consumption experience of the overall dining process, and thereby enhance the competitive advantage of the overall catering industry. Through the discussion in Chapter 3, the most important contribution is to find out how to improve the management capabilities of managers. And through the research on the ownership structure and the manager's shareholding degree, it can be discovered the company's management performance, especially the financial performance. This gap is tested by the research methodology in Chapter 4.

Chapter 4- Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This study mainly explores the correlation between corporate governance with ownership structure and operating performance in Taiwan's catering industry. Taking 28 listed domestic catering companies from 2016 to 2020 as a sample, the least square method is used to explore the possible effects of equity structure and financial factors on companies. The impact of business performance; in particular, the shareholding of directors and supervisors is negatively correlated with operating performance (Kao, Hodgkinson and Jaafar, 2019). On the one hand, it is revealed that the company's directors and supervisors do not seem to perform their due management and supervision functions to affect operating performance. On the other hand, this article also supports institutional investors' shareholdings and the correlation between stock or shareholding preference and business performance (Pare & Jang, 2010). Finally, the regression results also show the important relationship between financial ratios, such as financial leverage and earnings per share (Faisal, Khan, and Al-Abound, 2018). It also indirectly provides evidence that Taiwan's catering industry's operating performance is reflected in assets in recent years.

The analysis process of this research is divided into four parts. The first part is to examine the narrative statistics of each variable to observe the distribution characteristics; Manager (including director status) shareholding ratio, Manager (including family relative) shareholding ratio, director shareholding ratio, and Corporation shareholding ratio are used as explanatory variables. Referring to agency theory, stewardship theory and stakeholder theory show the company manager hold the degree of stock share. Also consider if their relative hold the company share degree. The second part is the Size (company size), Lev (debt ratio), MTB (Market price to Book price), Growth (sales growth rate), InvRate (Investment rate), FCF (Free Cash Flow), CapInt (Capital Intensity) and OMRate (Operating Margin Rate) as the regression equation Control variables to observe the relationship between different performance variables and explanatory variables. The third part is to transform the performance variable in the regression into the DOF variable of the joining rate and explore whether DOF will be affected by the explanatory variable. The fourth part is to explore whether the level of insider shareholding will disturb the outcomes of the regression analysis and implement the above two-part regression analysis. Referring to the chapter 2 theoretical

underpinning between franchiser and franchisee in franchisee side the performance management and employee dividend; franchiser side the authorised use and cost advantage has been considered while this research process.

This study uses secondary data for collation and analysis. The secondary data is mainly based on franchise restaurants-related statistical data published by Taiwan officials (TWSE, 2021). Through a systematic collection of time series data, the original data is further sorted, statistically analysed, and related literature is sorted and summarised (Pai-Vaidya, 2018). The detailed are time-series statistical analysis results of data to explore the development of franchised restaurants in the Taiwan market, to understand the market share of franchised restaurants in Taiwan, their market growth and changes, the restaurant chain type, and the study of direct management or franchise stores of franchised restaurants (Song, Park and Lee, 2019). Also covered are the number of stores, the distribution of stores by region, the main consumption situation, etc., and the management and policy development of the franchise system by Taiwan government.

The reliability and validity part, considering the reliability of the research data and the stability and consistency of the data source, mainly still rely on the official publicly released statistical data with high reliability (Pai-Vaidya, 2018). After the research has identified the research topic and conducted relevant literature research, the research method will be introduced. In the review and discussion part of the related literature in Chapter two and three, it can be sorted out different opinions about the relationship between the ownership structure, institutional corporation shareholding and the company's own operating performance. The following problems can be found in the literature:

1. The change in ownership structure and operating performance is not necessarily linear (Merendino and Melvile, 2019). The company's operating performance will follow the level of the internal manager's shareholding ratio, and to varying degrees of shareholding, it is in line with the theory of "Interest Convergence theory" (Lee, 2007) and "Benefit Prediction theory" (Vickers, et al., 2016). The shareholding ratio of corporations in professional investment institutions is indeed related to the efficiency of the company's own governance. Most studies have found that corporations in professional investment institutions tend to invest in companies with high future value, and because corporations have many professional talents, corporations' investment trends (funds flow) can indeed be used as a basis for general

investors, this is a relation to the social responsibility and brand resonance theory.

2. Regarding the relationship between the characteristics of the board of directors and operating performance, from the viewpoint of agency theory or corporate governance theory, there are opposite opinions, and the empirical relationship has not obtained a consistent result (Ali, et al., 2019).

3. Due to the varying degree of agency problems and the difference in the shareholding structure of each company, the company's dividend policy will vary due to differences in the shareholding ratio of internal managers, the characteristics of the board of directors, and the company's future growth opportunities and strategic considerations (Khan, Khidmat, Hares, Muhammad & Saleem, 2020).

4.2 Research Design

4.2.1 Research Design Flow Structure

This research first analyses the literature review, finds out the papers, journals, books and so on of the key factors for the succession of the company. Besides the research process of the nine research steps as shown in figure 6. In this research process, as of the figure 6 research design flow structure, shows research steps and directions, the first step is identifying research question, the directions if identify research question and confirm research direction object and scope. The second step is definition term which is explanation of proper nouns such as financial term and some abbreviations. The third step is literature review, in this part has literature discussion and related theories with franchise and ownership. The fourth step is methodological approach with quantitative data. The fifth step is hypothesis, are derivations from the literature and reasoning in the conceptual framework, to define assumptions, define hypotheses, based on previous literature hypotheses, and propose new hypotheses, tentative assertions subject to testing. The sixth step is data collection, in this step is collect and organize data from the statistics department of Taiwan, also it is greatly credible. The seventh step is data statistical description. The eighth step is empirical results, in this section shows the result and finding. The ninth step is analysing the empirical results, straighten the data from result, also using the statistics SPSS software to research hypothesis

and to verify. Final step is conclusions, according to the analysing empirical results, extending suggestions and summary.

Figure 6 Research Design Flow Structure

Research steps

Source from: author

4.2.2 The benefits of the quantitative approach

Quantitative approaches are designed to collect numerical data that can be used to measure variables. Quantitative data is structured and has statistical properties; its results are both objective and conclusive. It uses a grounded theory approach that relies on data collected through systematic analysis. To draw overall conclusions from the research and predict the results, this study uses quantitative approach to provide supporting evidence. Quantitative analysis refers to a method of analysis based on numerical and statistical data, which can help readers understand problems and phenomena more comprehensively and make more accurate decisions and predictions. Here are some benefits of quantitative analysis:

(1) Quantitative results are highly reliable: Quantitative analysis is based on numerical and statistical data, and rigorous methods can be used to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data, thereby making the analysis results more reliable.

(2) A more comprehensive understanding of the problem: Through quantitative analysis, readers can have a more comprehensive understanding of the problem and phenomenon. Because quantitative analysis collects large amounts of data and conducts systematic analysis, it can provide more comprehensive information than qualitative analysis.

(3) More accurate decisions and predictions: Through quantitative analysis, users can make more accurate decisions and predictions. Because quantitative analysis can provide more and more accurate data and information, it can help users better evaluate the pros and cons of different solutions and choose the best solution.

(4) Strong repeatability and comparability: Quantitative analysis methods are usually relatively standardized and standardized, so they can ensure the repeatability and comparability of analysis results, and users can easily compare and evaluate different data.

In short, quantitative analysis is a very effective analysis method that can help readers or users understand problems and phenomena more comprehensively and accurately and make more reliable decisions and predictions.

4.3 Hypothesis Development

4.3.1 Introduction

Franchising management as a risk decrease strategy for the catering business. Since franchising is regarded as a risk decrease strategy, it is believed that there is a negative correlation between MO and the DOF (Song, Park and Lee, 2019). Management ownership reduces the risk aversion to management risk by encouraging strategic decision-making, thereby increasing Research and Design spending, and reducing irrelevant corporate diversification (Brinkerink and Bammens, 2018). Because the view of managers, franchising decreases business risks, and business risks in turn generate personal gains by reducing the risk of managerial hires and management remuneration (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019).

When the management ownership rate is down, managers are more expected to use franchising to reduce company risk, and when MO rate is high, managers are more expected to decrease DOF to increase company risk (Siebert, 2015). From the perspective of shareholders, although franchising stabilises the company's income and reduces capital investment, it also obtains income from sales increase and fix assets appreciation through the units owned by the company, thus abandoning potential profit maximisation.

4.3.2 Research Hypotheses

In this study, the hypothesis are derivations from the literature and reasoning in the conceptual framework. research hypotheses are based on research of motive, purpose, and then based on the results of empirical research Rhou, Li, and Singal (2019) and other scholars, the study hypothesis 1 to hypothesis 8:

Ownership structure: The shareholding ratio of directors, managers and corporations affects company performance.

(1) Shareholding ratio of managers (including relatives) with ROA and EPS.

Alessandri & Seth (2014) takes the international diversification strategy as a risk-raising strategy, controls other incentive mechanisms, and there is a negative correlation between MO and international diversification. It supports the position that MO raises the risk of forcing

managers to reduce the risky tendency of managers to add value from the perspective of shareholders. Although management ownership has an incentive effect between company leaders and stockholders, it likewise causes risks from the shareholder to manager-related costs referring to transaction cost theory, stakeholder theory and stewardship theory (Alessandri & Seth, 2014). Different from neutral shareholders with diversified investments, managers with a higher management shareholding avoid risk because their human capital and wealth portfolio are concentrated in the international capital (Wright, et.al., 2007). Put another way, the risk-taking attributes of MO may result in high managerial ownership.

The company's agency problem will have different solutions depending on the internal manager's shareholding ratio. To a certain extent, the agency problem will decrease as the internal manager's shareholding ratio increases, but when the internal manager's shareholding exceeds at a certain critical point, agency problems will increase as the shareholding ratio of internal managers increases. This is based on Morck, Shleifer and Vishny (1988) and McConnell and Servaes (1990) mentioned that there is a Nonlinear Relation between management's shareholding ratio and the company's market value to analyse the impact of internal manager's share ratio on company's operating performance (Martine-Ferrero, et al., 2021).

This study will observe Taiwan's capital market where information asymmetry is more serious than that of developed countries, and mainly based on Chen et al (2005). It is different from the previous observation of only internal managers' shareholding ratios but uses internal managers to compare with the shareholding ratios of its family relationship (second-class relative) and its related companies (subsidiaries under the manager's name), it can be explored the Nonlinear Relation with the company's operating performance (ROA, EPS) (Bettinelli, 2012). Therefore, the hypothesises has been recommended following below.

Hypothesis 1: Under different managerial family levels of shareholding with a Nonlinear relationship, that the increase in shareholding ratio has significantly different impacts on company performance.

(2) Managers also hold shares as directors with ROA and EPS.

When the direct monitoring is higher, the degree of management freedom is lower, and if the scope of management discretion of different companies is different, the level of management ownership will also be different. This is because when the direct supervision of the board of directors and shareholders is weak, management ownership is adopted as the corporate governance mechanism. So far, our analysis has focused on the impact of MO on franchise decisions (Himmelberg, et al., 1999). Therefore, the relationship between our proposed MO and the DOF may be confused by the impact of management discretion correlated with each company (Bettinelli, 2012). Even if a considerable section of the difference in MO cross-section is not observed it is explained by the heterogeneity of the company and the scope of management discretion (Himmelberg, et al., 1999).

The director is the decision-making group of the board of directors. The position and power in the enterprise are greater than that of the shareholders (Merendino and Melville, 2019). They must lead the board of directors to perform a supervisory role. If the manager also serves as the director, then the manager has two identities, both the executive and the executive decision-making supervisors may be so prone to guarding and stealing, hindering the function of the board of directors, and making potential investors and shareholders doubt the objective and impartiality of the board of directors overseeing the management authority.

When a manager is also a director, as described by Patton and Baker (1987), he may dictate the board of directors and control the agenda for his own benefit, making the board of directors unable to play a good supervisory role and reducing company performance (Merendino and Melville, 2019). On the other hand, if a person assumes the roles of director and manager at the same time, two problems may arise: one is a conflict of interest, that is, individuals make decisions that are unfavourable to the company through the convenience of their positions and harm the interests of shareholders; the other is that the performance of the management authority cannot be evaluated independently, because the governed board loses its autonomy (Merendino and Melville, 2019). Based on the above, put forward the hypothesis 2 and hypothesis 3 in this research

Hypothesis 2: There is a negative relationship between the director status of a manager and the company's operating performance.

Hypothesis 3: The manager's ratio of shareholding has a positive impact on company performance.

(3) Shareholding ratio of corporation with ROA and EPS.

In recent years, the shareholding ratio of institutional investors in the stock market has continued to increase. Although it is still not as good as the shareholding ratio of retail investors, the role of institutional investors is of profound significance; according to Pound (1988), "efficiency monitoring hypothesis", based on its own risk considerations, institutional corporations will have stricter requirements for the supervision of the board of directors, and by concentrating equity and their professional capabilities and technologies, they will have more supervision capabilities than the general investment public (Chaharmahali & Tavakolnia, 2019). Moreover, referring to brand resonance theory if institutional shareholder in the franchise, public investors and customers understand the institution with good present brand resonance, that affects the market price drive leading and more confidence the franchisee business as well as the company performance will improved. McConnell and Servaes (1990) found that Tobin's Q has a positive relationship with the shareholding ratio of institutional investors, mainly because institutional investors have better professional capabilities and information advantages, and their positions are relatively independent, so they can bring strong supervisory ability. Therefore, if there are many corporation's shareholding shares, their operating performance after listing will not drop significantly, so the hypothesis of this research is proposed.

Hypothesis 4 : The corporation's shareholding ratio has a positive impact on company performance.

Ownership structure: The shareholding ratio of directors, managers and corporations affects DOF.

(1) Shareholding ratio of internal managers (including relatives) with DOF.

Referring to chapter 2 theoretical underpinning between franchiser and franchisee in franchisee side show employee dividend and performance management, the theories base on managerial owner ship which are stewardship theory and stakeholder theory. For example, after the establishment of Wow prime Company in 1993, to accelerate the brand

growth, the core director of the Central Standing Committee will act as the "Lion King" to develop new brands. For every new brand and every store opened, the chairman will invest 26% and create the brand. The "Lion King" invested 20%, the store manager held 11%, and the chef held 7%. If the store makes profit, dividends are also distributed according to the proportion of shares held, so that the store manager and chef can treat each store as their own business and work hard for themselves (Yang, 2019). The manager's shareholding ratio plus the manager's relatives' shareholding ratio are included in the independent variables of this hypothesis. Correspondingly find out whether the DOF will increase due to the increase in the shareholding ratio (Rhou, LI & Singal, 2019).

Hypothesis 5: Under different managerial family shareholding degrees, with a Nonlinear relationship, an increase in the shareholding ratio has significant differences in the impact of the company's franchise degree.

(2) Managers also hold shares as directors with DOF.

In Asian countries, many franchise business as family business to start with, so once they set up the business and doing a manager position referring to stakeholder theory, most of directors are family members, such parents, and siblings; it has managerial ownership problems referring to stewardship theory, due to if the managers with director status, they may be selfish motives and the company's performance may not present the best way. As Lafond and Roychowdhury (2008) pointed out, management ownership is partly due to stock accumulation during the manager 's term of office, the manager 's founder status and/ or manager's divestment decision. By divestment to rebalance their individual investment portfolios, managers can generate equity that differs from that expected in management discretion. Managers may also have high ownership because they are the company's founders or members of the founding family. In the choice of succession candidates, integrity and corporate mission are more important than gender and ranking. (Chrisman, et al., 1998) This is due to the Chinese culture's emphasis on the family, which makes the business owners more cautious about the inheritance of the family business (Shen, 2018).

The manager may also have the status of director, whether it affects the degree of franchise. As mentioned in the previous literature, the proportion of shares held by the company's internal managers affects the company's performance. If DOF (Degree of Franchise) is included as one of the company's performance evaluations, it may also have a positive

impact. Evaluation whether it is listed as one of the company's performances also depends on the company's governance policy. Making franchise taxes more sensitive to shareholder value will give shareholders more weight than managers (Barzuza, 2010). Based on the above, put forward the hypothesis 6 and hypothesis 7 of this research

Hypothesis 6: There is a positive relationship between manager (including director status) and franchise degree.

Hypothesis 7: Manager's shareholding ratio has a positive impact on the degree of franchise.

(3) Shareholding ratio of corporation (include corporate) with DOF.

According to the research on Taiwan's shareholding ratio and company performance (Zhang, 2004; Shen, 2003), it is found that the shareholding ratio of corporations is positively correlated with the company's operating performance (Chueh, Hsu and Chen, 2014) referring to chapter 2 brand resonance theory and social responsibility basic. Under the price model, the value of government shareholding has a bearing on the value of equity have a significant positive relationship (Lin and Jeng, 2006). In this study, the degree of franchise is a part of the company's business expansion and operating performance, and it is predicted that the high proportion of corporation shareholdings is positively related to the degree of franchise.

Hypothesis 8: The corporation' shareholding ratio of has a positive impact on the company's franchise degree.

Table 11 A summary table of empirical research issue`s and hypotheses

	Research topics	Explain the variables	The relationship between expected variables and company performance ROA & EPS
Corporate Variables	shareholding structure	MRHD MO MHD CHD	Positive Correlation Negative Correlation Positive Correlation Positive Correlation
	Research topics	Explain the variables	The relationship between expected variables and DOF.
governance	shareholding structure	MRHD	Positive Correlation
		MO	Positive Correlation
		MHD	Positive Correlation
		CHD	Positive Correlation

Source from: author

4.3.3 Conceptual Framework of Hypothesis

The theoretical model framework and research propositions developed by this research, as well as the research hypotheses derived, are hereby constructed to construct an empirical framework. The figure 7 conceptual framework of hypothesis shows the dependent variables which are company performance, the independent variables which are ownership constructure and the control variables has showed about company financial valuation metric, which are investment rate, leverage, market value to book value, capital investment, sales growth rate, operating margin rate and firm size. Moreover, it has shown in this figure are the different variables for the hypothesized development paths and empirical models that are the unique formula for this study, the control variables bring to this research model 3 and model 4 formula. In MO model which is model 3 formula are included the control variables in MTB, CapInt, IntRate and Lev; in DOF model which is model 4 formula are included the control variables in MTB, CapInt and Growth. From this diagram, it can be clearly showed the relationship and development path between assumptions and variables which are Dependent variables (DV), Independent variables (IV) and Control variables (CV).

Figure 7 Conceptual Framework of Hypothesis

Source from: author

4.4 Variables Definition

4.4.1 Research variable definition

Dependent Variables in Detection Models

Operational performance measurement index value. This study plans to take Taiwan listed companies as a sample group, use different performance indicators, and add internal managers and affiliated companies' shareholding to explore the relationship between manager's shareholding rate and company's operating performance. This is related to figure 3 Franchisee side performance management and agency theory.

The theoretical calculation method is as follows:

(1) Return on Assets (ROA)

According to the research of Chen et al (2005), ROA (EBIT / TA), EPS, etc. are used for basic analysis from the perspective of accounting statements and the company's future value in measuring the company's operating performance. Among them, ROA (Return on Assets) refers to the profit ratio that the company can create by using funds and loans during a certain period. It can also be said to be the total return on the company's assets.

ROA = Earnings Before Interest and Tax /Average Total Assets *100%

$$= \frac{EBIT_{i,t}}{TA_{i,t}}$$

(2) Earnings per share (EPS)

Earnings per share (EPS) is an important indicator of company earnings. It is calculated by dividing the total profit generated in a period by the number of shares the company has listed on the stock market. Earnings per share is used to determine the added value of each company's outstanding shares. In an exchange, the amount of profits a company earns, and

the number of shares listed may vary, so earnings per share provide a way to evaluate various businesses on a per capita basis.

EPS = (Net Income - Preferred Dividends) / average outstanding common shares

$$= \frac{(NI-PD)_{i,t}}{AOS_{i,t}}$$

(3) Degree of Franchise (DOF)

The dependent variable in this study is the degree of franchise (DOF), which is obtained by dividing the number of franchise stores by the total number of stores. The value of DOF ranges from 0 to 100, where 0 % signifies firm wholly owned by the company, and 100 signifies a fully franchise company (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019).

DOF = The number of franchise units / The total number of units

$$= \frac{TFU_{i,t}}{TU_{i,t}}$$

Independent Variables in Detection Models

Most listed companies in Taiwan tend to be family businesses, and family members serve as directors, supervisors, and important high-level managers, making it difficult to solve agency problems (Shen, 2018). Previous research only focused on the shares in the manager's name, but this research focused on the shares in the company that has the right to decide or represent the manager and related persons (second-class relatives) (Bettinelli, 2012). In short, it is internal the manager's family shareholding ratio. According to Morck et al. (1988), there is a Nonlinear Relation between insider shareholding and performance, and domestic regulations require companies to prepare consolidated financial statements when they hold more than 50% of the shares of other companies or have substantial control rights. However, as to what proportion of the shareholding ratio must be considered to have the right control right, it depends on the company's shareholding distribution status, so in terms of the shareholding ratio with absolute control. This is related to figure 3 Franchisee side employee

dividend and agency theory, also the stewardship theory and stakeholder theory are both related to ownership structure.

Most scholars such as Chaganti, Mahajan and Sharma (1985), Selton and Kedner (1987), and Jensen (1993) believe that if the general manager is the chairman or director, it is like a player in the hands of the general manager, the impartiality and objectivity of the board of directors were affected, and the board of directors could not perform its functions, resulting in poor performance of the company.

Institutional investors who are corporation shareholding (CHO) have more complete information than non-institutional investors, which puts supervision pressure on managers and can exert stronger checks and balances. Therefore, institutional investors' shareholding has a positive impact on the company's operating performance. Therefore, this research also discusses the influence of corporate shareholding ratio interest rate on company performance.

(1) Managers held share degree include director status (MO)

= The Number of shares held of Manager with director status/Total number of shares*100%

$$= \frac{(MHD+DHD)_{i,t}}{TS_{i,t}}$$

(2) Managers held share degree include relative family held degree (MRHD)

= The Number of shares held of Manager plus family relative share held /Total number of shares*100%

$$= \frac{MRHD_{i,t}}{TS_{i,t}}$$

(3) Director held share degree (DHD)

= The Number of shares held of director /Total number of shares*100%

$$= \frac{DHD_{i,t}}{TS_{i,t}}$$

(4) Managers held share degree (MHD)

= The Number of shares held of Manager only/Total number of shares*100%

$$= \frac{MHD_{i,t}}{TS_{i,t}}$$

(5) Corporate held share degree (include legal person) CHD

= The Number of shares held of corporate include legal person/Total number of shares*100%

$$= \frac{CHD_{i,t}}{TS_{i,t}}$$

Control Variables in Detection Models

(1) SIZE

Jensen (1985) and Lipton and Lorsch (1992) argue that the size of a company will affect corporate governance and operating performance. This study uses the natural logarithm of total assets as a representative indicator of the size of the company. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019) Moreover, the number of owners and total assets are the variables with the greatest explanatory power (Dalbor, Kim and Upneja, 2004).

= The natural logarithm of Total Asset, as a standard to measure the size of the enterprise.

$$= \log(\text{Total Assets})_{i,t}$$

(2) Debt ratio (Lev.)

There are still divergent opinions on the impact of capital structure on the company's operating performance. This study will use the ratio of total liabilities to total assets as the debt ratio to eliminate the interference of capital structure on performance.

= Total debt /Total assets *100%

$$= \frac{TD_{i,t}}{TA_{i,t}}$$

(3) Growth Rate (Growth)

Short and Keasey (1999) pointed out that the company's growth rate is an important part of determining the company's operating performance. Sales growth rate refers to the ratio between the company's sales growth in the current period and the previous period's sales. It reflects the increase or decrease in sales. Also, it is an important indicator for evaluating the company's growth status and development capabilities.

= (Net operating income- Net operating income in the previous period) /Net operating income *100%

$$= \frac{(NOI_{i,t} - NOI_{i-1,t})}{NOI_{i,t}}$$

(4) Market to Book Ratio (MTB)

The Market-to-Book ratio (also known as the Price to Book ratio) is a financial valuation indicator used to evaluate the percentage of a company's current market price to the book price. The market value is the current share price of all outstanding shares, the price at which the market considers the company to be valued (CFI, 2021). One of the representative variables of performance, the ratio of market price to book value is put into the control variable.

MTB = Market Capitalization / Total net book value *100%

$$= \frac{MP_{i,t}}{(TA-TD)_{i,t}}$$

Note: Total net book value= Total Assets – Total Liabilities

(5) Capital Intensity Ratio (CapInt.)

A company's capital intensity ratio is a measure of the amount of capital required per dollar of revenue. It is calculated by dividing the company's total assets by sales. It is the reciprocal of total asset turnover (Xplained, 2021). Capital expenditures (CapEx) are funds used by companies to acquire, upgrade, and maintain physical assets (such as property, plant, buildings, technology, or equipment) (FERNANDO, 2021)

= Total Assets / Net Revenues *100%

$$= \frac{TA_{i,t}}{Sale_{i,t}}$$

(6) Investment rate (InvRate.)

Investment rate is the ratio of total tangible investment to value added. (Insee, 2019) InvRate is the rate of Capital Expenditures (CapEx) to the stock of PPE. (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019)

= The Capital expenditures / the stock of PPE *100%

$$= \frac{CapEx_{i,t}}{PPE_{i,t}}$$

Note: Capital Expenditures= PPE= property, plant, and equipment (FERNANDO, 2021)

(7) Free Cash Flow (FCF)

Free cash flow (FCF) refers to the cash generated by a company after considering cash outflows to support operations and maintain its capital assets. Unlike earnings or net income, free cash flow is a measure of profitability. It does not include non-cash expenditures in the income statement, including equipment and asset expenditures, and changes in working capital in the balance sheet (FERNANDO, 2021).

= Cash from Operations - Capital Expenditures.

$$= CFO_{i,t} - CapEx_{i,t}$$

(8) Operating Margin Rate (OMRate)

Net profit margin (also known as "profit margin" or "net profit margin ratio") is a financial ratio used to calculate the percentage of profit a company generates from its total revenue. It measures the amount of net profit a company receives for every dollar of revenue. The net profit margin is equal to the net profit (also called Net Income) divided by the total income, expressed as a percentage. (CFI, 2021)

= Net income / sales * 100%

$$= \frac{NI_{i,t}}{Sale_{i,t}}$$

After previous research (Lafond, et al., 2008), the agents of management option include company size (size), Market value to book value ratio (MTB), leverage rate (lev), Free cash flow (FCF), capital intensity (CapInt) and Investment rate (InvRate), The detailed formula has been discussed above.

Owing to managers are unlikely to own a huge percentage of shareholding in big companies, it be supposed Size to be inversely related to MO. The study expect that Lev is negatively correlated to MO, in line with Jensen (1986), debt reduces the agency cost of FCF by decreasing the cash flow at the discretion of managers, thereby decreasing the need for

higher levels of MO. It be anticipated that there will be a negative correlation between CapInt and MO, because the observability of fixed assets mitigates agency issues, resulting in a decline in management equity (Roh, et al.,2019). As for free cash flow correlated to the tendency to dominate, it be assumed its correlation with MO to be positive. Likewise, using InvRate as an agent of disposable expenditure, it be assumed a positive correlation between the InvRate and the MO. (Rhou, et al., 2019)

Based on earlier research, it be included a few control variables that might impact the company's franchise level. First, it be controlled by the size of the company. Since it has been recommended that franchising can be used as a tool for expansion by small companies that usually lack sufficient funds to establish all the company's business, it have been found from previous studies that there is a negative correlation between scale and freedom (Roh, 2002). Second, it be controlled by the company's MTB ratio. In franchise research, the MTB ratio is usually used as a representative of corporate brand capital (Roh, 2002). Although franchiser provide franchisees with the right to use their brand in trade a certain profit sharing (Combs, et al., 2011), a company with strong brand capital are more expected to invite franchisees and thus the brand stronger. With the concession's stable cash flow (Koh, et al., 2018), companies with less fluctuations in operating cash flow are correlated with higher degree of franchising. Constant with previous research (Roh, 2002), it be expected a negative correlation between risk and degrees of freedom. Finally, it be monitored the sales growth ratio in year t relative to the previous year. Since previous study has shown that rapid growth hotel companies are more possible to use franchising to decrease agency costs related with checking new employees in new departments (Roh, 2002), it has been definite a positive correlation between sales-growing and freedom relationship.

COVID-19, Coronavirus disease is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus from end of year 2019. (WHO, 2020) Covid-19 affects the operations of many companies, the most serious one is the catering industry. Most restaurants are difficult to meet the social distance prescribed by the government, and many countries have implemented lockdown to restrict people's activities at home to avoid the spread of the virus; therefore, many restaurants cannot run the business so decide to close business.

Table 12 Definition of Variables

Variables	Abbreviation	Definition
Managerial ownership	MO	The ratio of the company's shareholding by the top directors and managers. (Himmelberg, et al., 1999) (Jensen & Meckling, 1976)
Degree of franchising	DOF	The number of franchised stores by the total stores. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Company Size	Size	Firm Size is measured as the natural logarithm of total assets. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Leverage	Lev	Leverage is the debt-to-asset ratio. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Market to book	MTB	The percentage of a company's market value to the book value. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Capital intensity	CapInt	CapInt as the percentage of PPE to sales. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Free cash flow	FCF	Free cash flow (FCF) refers to the cash generated by a company after considering cash outflows to support operations and maintain its capital assets. (FERNANDO, 2021)
Investment rate	InvRate	The capital expenditures to the PPE. (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019)
Return on Asset	ROA	Return on Asset (ROA) is calculated by dividing a company's net income by total assets, showing how profitable a company is relative to its total assets.

Source from: author collation

4.4.2 The sign of variables

Table 13 The sign of variables

Variables	Name	Authors (Year)	sign
MO	Managerial Ownership	(Jensen, 1986), (Seo and Sharma, 2018), (Lafond, and Roychowdhury, 2008), (Jensen and Meckling, 1976)	+
DOF	Degree of Franchising	(Roh, 2002), (Seo and Sharma, 2018), (Lafond, et al., 2008), (Roh, 2002)	+
Size	Firm Size	(Lafond, et al., 2008), (Roh, 2002)	+
Lev	Leverage	(Himmelberg, et al., 1999; Lafond, et al., 2008)	-
MTB	Market-To-Book	(Himmelberg, et al., 1999; Lafond, et al., 2008), (Roh, 2002)	+
CapInt	Capital Intensity	(Himmelberg, et al., 1999; Lafond, et al., 2008)	-
FCF	Free Cash Flow	(Lafond, et al., 2008), (Koh, et al., 2018; Sohnetal.,2014)	+
InvRate	Investment Rate	(Lafond, et al., 2008 cited in Rhou, et al., 2019)	+
Growth	Sales Growth	(Roh, 2002) (Rhou, et al., 2019)	+
ROA	Return on Assets	(Rhou, et al., 2019)	+
EPS	Earing per share	(Rhou, et al., 2019)	+

Source from: author

4.5 Data Collection & Sample Selection

4.5.1 Research period and research samples

This chapter describes the collection of research data required to test these hypotheses, and describes the methods used in preparing the data for the empirical study reported in this thesis. As the reliability of all empirical research in accountings is ultimately achieved through the quality of the accounting data on which is based, this aspect of the research study is described in detail below. This research mainly analyses the shareholding of insiders. If there is a change in operating rights, this sample will not be considered. In this study, it is decided to take 5 years as the observation sample period, and the research period is from 2016 to

2020, sample size is 466, and the catering companies listed on the Taiwan Stock Exchange are the research objects. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of research showed that below table 14.

Table 14 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria of research

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The companies set up in Taiwan. ➤ The companies must have more than one of below business codes, Drink section (F501030), Pub section (F501050), Restaurant section (501060) and Other catering section (501990) ➤ The companies have more than 2 branch in Taiwan. ➤ The companies are in Taiwan stock exchange. ➤ The companies submit their annual report by Accountant's signature. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The company's main office is not setup in Taiwan. ➤ The companies are not in Taiwan stock exchange or have been removed from the stock market. ➤ The companies have not more than two branch in Taiwan. ➤ Inconsistent qualifications, the companies were only a small part of the income comes from catering income or no actual catering business. ➤ Missing information, such as lack of year financial report for interruption of trading.

Source from: author

4.5.2 Data source

The research variables covered by this research include company shareholding structure, ROA, EPS, etc. Mainly taken from the database of Taiwan Economic News (TEJ) (TEJ, 2021). Use the public information observatory of the Taiwan Stock Exchange to reveal the latest annual statements and public offering prospectuses of the sampled companies (TWSE, 2021). Refer to the company registration system established by the Commercial Department of the Ministry of Economic Affairs to check whether the investment company is owned by the family of internal managers (DGBAS, 2021). The above information is calculated and confirmed one by one, and finally typed in and another verification is done to ensure the correctness of the input data.

Figure 8 The process of collecting data from different sources.

Source from: author

Firstly, In the “Goodinfo!” website, there are four part of stock relative catering industry, which are Tourism business (44 companies), Sightseeing-International Catering (12 companies), Sightseeing-Michelin restaurant (7 companies) and Sightseeing- Hotels and shopping centres (2 companies) (Goodinfo, 2021). Secondly, from the “Goodinfo” filtering, delete the repeat and missing data, sum up as 28 companies, according to their stock code to find their

public financial report and accounting subject's data from 2016-2020 every season from TEJ database system. TEJ (Taiwan Economic Journal) is Taiwan Economic News Database company. Also, TEJ is a finance and Economics Database company (TEJ, 2021), after the filtering data process, as result total 466 of firm-quarter-years. Thirdly, in the TEJ database does not offer the Market capital price, so it can be found from TWSE. TWSE is Taiwan stock exchange (TWSE, 2021). The historical market capital price has been found that end of March, end of June, end of September and end of December from 2016-2020. One of variables MTB (Market capital value to Book value) is needed the figure to calculate. Fourthly, after the filtering data, the 28 companies have been confirmed in this study. The company's annual report from 2016-2020 has been found their company official website. The number of franchise branches can find from the annual report and to figure out the variables DOF (Degree of Franchise) which is needed in the regression analysis. Finally, according to the Ministry of Economic Affairs, R.O.C. "Retrieval System for Company Bank Number and Limited Partnership Business Item Code List", the catering industry divided into four business code, which are Drink section (F501030), Pub section (F501050), Restaurant section (F501060) and Others catering industry (F501990) (MOEA, 2021). In this study I will compare the different industry codes and their correlation coefficient analysis to find out whether it is significant.

Taking into account the degree of disclosure of company information in the market, companies that are listed on the OTC are also deleted; at the same time, the manager with director status shareholding ratio, manager shareholding ratio, director shareholding ratio, manager shareholding ratio (include manager's relative) In the case that complete information is required for the shareholding ratio of corporations, and after deducting the sample companies for the conversion of operating rights during the study period and incomplete information, a total of 28, total 466 firm-quarter-year listed companies in Taiwan were obtained as empirical samples. This research takes the listed and OTC (Over-the counter) catering companies on the Taiwan Stock Exchange as the research object and selects 28 companies where the following table including.

Table 15 Sample companies Market capitalisation and number of branches

NO.	Name of company	Abbreviation	Stock Code	Industry section	Market capitalisation NT\$	Number of Branches (2021)
1	Ten Ren Tea Co., Ltd.	Tenren	1233	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	32.25	2
2	AN-SHIN FOOD SERVICES CO., LTD.	MOS Burger	1259	Drink section (F501030) Pub section (F501050) Restaurant section (F501060)	70.20	275
3	Namchow Shareholdings Co., Ltd.	Namchow	1702	Other catering section (F501990)	48.65	11
4	THE AMBASSADOR HOTEL, LTD.	AMBASSADOR	2704	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	29.00	3
5	FORMOSA INTERNATIONAL HOTELS CORPORATION	Silks	2707	Drink section (F501030) Pub section (F501050) Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	146.00	4
6	Gourmet Master Co. Ltd.	85 Degree	2723	Drink section (F501030)	141.00	455
7	Yummy Town (Cayman) Shareholdings Corporation	Yummy Town	2726	Other catering section (F501990)	40.20	960
8	WOWPRIME CORP.	Wowprime	2727	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	151.50	283
9	TTFB COMPANY LIMITED	THAI TOWN	2729	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	241.50	138
10	La Kaffa International Co., LTD.	LAKAFFA	2732	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	105.00	530

NO.	Name of company	Abbreviation	Stock Code	Industry section	Market capitalisation NT\$	Number of Branches (2021)
11	My Humble House Hospitality Management Consulting.	HUMBLE HOUSE	2739	Drink section (F501030) Pub section (F501050) Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	22.85	4
12	Mr. Onion International Co., Ltd	Mr. Onion	2740	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	19.95	23
13	FDC International Hotels Corporation	Fleur de Chine	2748	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	41.65	5
14	PRESIDENT CHAIN STORE CORPORATION	President	2912	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	280.00	6210
15	The Landis Taipei Hotel Co., Ltd	The Landis	5703	Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	24.90	11
16	New Palace International Co., Ltd.	New Palace	8940	Restaurant section (F501060)	14.20	8
17	Hi-Lai Foods Co., Ltd	HI-LAI	1268	Restaurant section (F501060)	120.50	39
18	HOTEL HOLIDAY GARDEN	Holiday Garden	2702	Other catering section (F501990)	25.20	2
19	LEOFOO DEVELOPMENT CO., LTD.	LEOFOO	2705	Restaurant section (F501060)	18.05	9
20	Chateau International Development Co.,Ltd.	Chateau	2722	Restaurant section (F501060)	33.35	3

NO.	Name of company	Abbreviation	Stock Code	Industry section	Market capitalisation NT\$	Number of Branches (2021)
21	FX HOTELS GROUP INC.	FX HOTEL	2724	Other catering section (F501990)	5.45	83
22	HOYA Resort Hotel Group	HOYA	2736	Restaurant section (F501060)	16.90	5
23	Tofu Restaurant Co., Ltd.	TOFU	2752	Drink section (F501030) Pub section (F501050) Restaurant section (F501060)	154.00	69
24	KURA SUSHI ASIA CO., LTD.	KURA SHHSHI	2754	Restaurant section (F501060)	75.90	29
25	YoungQin International Co., Ltd.	Youngqin	2755	Restaurant section (F501060) Other catering section (F501990)	58.20	835
26	LEALEA HOTELS & RESORTS CO., LTD.	LEALEA	5364	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	18.55	9
27	Green World Hotels Co., Ltd.	Green World Hotel	8077	Drink section (F501030) Restaurant section (F501060)	10.70	11
28	HOLIDAY ENTERTAINMENT CO., LTD	Holiday KTV	9943	Pub section (F501050) Restaurant section (F501060)	61.00	53

Source from: author

4.5.3 About the IFRSs

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs), Refers to companies that have adopted IFRSs to prepare financial reports in accordance with the provisions of the FSC since 2013, including listed, OTC, new OTC companies and the financial industry under the supervision of the FSC (TWSE, 2021). Consolidated financial report is a financial report that expresses the financial status and financial performance of the parent company and its subsidiaries after the merger. According to the regulations of the competent authority, the enterprise must submit this financial report to the outside world (TWSE, 2021).

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). Disclosure and Transparency is one of the corporate governances' principles of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC). Market forces drive the company to attach importance to the interests of shareholders and creditors (TWSE, 2021). The company should ensure timely and truthfully disclose all the company's material information. Among the information that companies regularly disclose, financial statements are usually an important tool for investors or shareholders to make decisions. Accounting standards are the main language of financial reporting. There are more than 115 in the world. The adoption of IFRSs is mandatory or permitted in several countries. (TWSE, 2021).

Table 16 IFRSs historical name and abbreviation

Abbreviation	Full Name
IFRSs	International Financial Reporting Standards
IFRICs	International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee
IASs	International Accounting Standards
SICs	Standing Interpretations Committee

Source from: IFRSs historical name and abbreviation (TWSE, 2021).

The globalisation of the capital market has become an unstoppable trend. Since many large domestic listed (counter) companies have gone to foreign exchanges for listing. Or issue convertible corporate bonds abroad to raise funds, the compilation and disclosure of relevant financial information must comply with local regulations. And considering the increasing frequency of international commercial transactions. It is also becoming common for domestic companies to set up overseas subsidiaries (TWSE, 2021). The accounting information of domestic companies is consistent with international regulations, which will save companies the cost of preparing related statements. Conducive to the internationalisation of enterprises and is conducive to attract foreign investment in domestic enterprises, so to enhance global

competitiveness. Taiwan is committed to building an information disclosure system in line with international standards and promoting accounting standards in line with international standards (TWSE, 2021).

Table 17 Other countries practice with IFRSs.

Country	IFRSs Practice
European Union	Requires its domestic listed companies to prepare financial reports in accordance with IFRSs since 2005.
USA	The SEC issued a statement on February 24, 2010: 1. Encourage the convergence plan between US accounting standards and IFRSs to reduce differences in accounting standards. 2. It has a work plan to evaluate the impact of US companies adopting IFRSs on the US securities market and stated that if the US decides to adopt IFRSs in 2011, US companies expect to apply IFRSs as early as 2015.
Canada	IFRSs has been fully agreed since 2011.
Japan	The Financial Services Agency of Japan announced the Japanese financial reporting structure in December 2009: 1. Listed companies that meet certain conditions can choose to use IFRSs to prepare consolidated statements from the beginning of the fiscal year on April 1 (2009) 2. It will be decided in 2012 whether to compel all listed companies to adopt IFRSs in 2015 or 2016.
China	The Ministry of Finance of the Mainland has issued No. 38 Accounting Standards for Business Enterprises in consideration of IFRSs and required listed companies to prepare financial statements based on this since 2007.
South Korea	Since 2011, IFRSs have been fully approved.
Hongkong	IFRSs have been adopted.
Singapore	IFRSs have been adopted.

Source from: International Financial Reporting Standards

Table 18 Data definitions and code -IFRSs

Variable Name	Explanation	IFRSs
Total Debt (TD)	= Current liabilities + non-current liabilities Total Debt is calculated by combining up a company's liabilities, or debts, which are classified as short -term and long-term debt. (Indeed, 2021)	1000
Total Assets (TA)	= Current assets + non-current assets Refers to the resources formed by past transactions or other matters of the enterprise, owned, or controlled by the enterprise, and expected to bring economic benefits to the enterprise. Represents the sum of total current assets, long-term receivables, investments in unconsolidated subsidiaries, other investments, net property, plant and equipment, and other assets. (Entrepreneur, 2021)	0010
Leverage (Debt ratio)	=Total Debt / Total Assets Using this indicator, analysts can compare the leverage of a company with the leverage of other companies in the same industry. This information can reflect the company's financial stability. The higher the ratio, the higher the degree of leverage (DoL), and therefore, the higher the risk of investing in that ratio (HAYES, 2021)	R505
PPE	Property, Plant, and Equipment (PP&E), Real estate, plant, and equipment (PP&E) are long-term assets that are critical to business operations and cannot be easily converted into cash. Real estate, plant and equipment are tangible assets, which means they are tangible or tangible in nature. (MURPHY, 2021)	0401
Sales	Represents gross sales and other operating revenue less discounts, returns and allowances.	3105
FCF	Free Cash Flow (D)= Consolidated total profit and loss + depreciation + amortization + purchase of real property, plant, and equipment + (working capital at the beginning of the period-working capital at the end of the period) =Net operating profit after taxes- CapEx	F69B
CapEx	Capital expenditures (CapEx) are funds used by companies to acquire, upgrade, and maintain physical assets (such as property, plant, buildings, technology, or equipment). Capital expenditures are usually used to undertake new projects or investments in the company (FERNANDO, 2021).	0320
ROA	Return on Assets = Total comprehensive profit and loss of the current period / [(Total assets of the current period + Total assets of the previous period) /2] *100 %	R11V
EPS	<i>Earnings Per Share</i> Income before extraordinary items + Preferred dividends, divided by the number of shares in issue. Refers to the earnings per share brought to investors/shareholders in the open market. It is a profit indicator for the company	R535
Growth	= (Net operating income-net operating income in the same period last year) / ABS (net operating income in the same period last year) * 100%	R401
OMRate	Operating Margin Rate = Operating profit/net operating income *100 (%)	R106

Source from: Variable's definitions and code -IFRSs

4.5.4 Data procedures

4.5.4.1 Business code

The company and limited partnership business item code table retrieval system from Ministry of Economic Affairs, R.O.C (MOEA,2021) Notice the corresponding business code and explanation. Table 19 shows that business code and business detail which are Beverage section (F501030), Pub section (F501050), Restaurant section (F501060) and Other catering section (F501990).

Table 19 Business Code

No.	Business code	Name	Business detail
1	F501030	Beverage section	An industry engaged in non-alcoholic beverage services. Such as tea, coffee, cold drinks, fruits, and other industries that serve customers after ordering, including tea art houses, coffee shops, ice fruit shops, cold drinks shops, etc.
2	F501050	Pub section	It is engaged in the catering service of alcoholic beverages but is not an industry that provides escorts. Including beer houses, drinking hotels, etc.
3	F501060	Restaurant section	Engaged in the industry where all kinds of Chinese and Western food supply points are ordered, and they are eaten on the spot immediately. Such as Chinese and Western restaurants, Japanese restaurants, Thai restaurants, Vietnamese restaurants, Indian restaurants, teppanyaki restaurants, Korean barbecue restaurants, restaurants, canteens, snack bars, etc. Includes box meals.
4	F501990	Other catering section	It is engaged in other food and beverage supply industries other than F501030 to F501060. Such as food package making, table setting, etc.

Source from: Ministry of Economic Affairs, R.O.C

4.5.4.2 Data source of concept stock

Filter out concept stocks of listed companies from Goodinfo Taiwan stock information (Goodinfo, 2021)

Table 20 Data collection from Goodinfo

No.	The Concept stock	Companies and Stock code	Total Numbers	2016-2020 Quarter-year companies
1	Tourism business	Mos Burger (1259), LAKAFFA (2732), JANFUSUN (5701), HILAI(1268), Ezfly (2734), The Landis (5703), Wanhwa(2701), HOYA (2736), Chihpen Royal (5704), Holiday Garden (2702),HUMBLE HOUSE (2739) PHX TOUR (5706), AMBASSADOR (2704), Mr. Onion (2740), Green World Hotels (8077), LEOFOO (2705), Richmond (2743), Power Wind (8462), First hotel(2706),Life travel (2745), New Palace(8940), Skills (2707), Fleur de Chine (2748), Holiday KTV (9943), Far Glory Hotel (2712), Tofu (2752), PH (2718), 8 Way (2753), Star travel (2719), KURA SHSHI (2754), Chateau (2722), Youngqin(2755), 85Degree (2723), Red Horse (2928), FX HOTEL(2724), HAWAN(3252), Yummy Town (2726), TOPLUS (3522), Wowprime (2727), Da Lue(4804), THAI TOWN (2729), CJW (5301), Lion (2731), LEALEA(5364)	44	880
2	Sightseeing-International Catering	Tenren (1233), Sunjuice (1256), TEHMAG1264), TECO (1504), SINMAG (1580), Namchow (1702), 85Degree(2723), Yummy Town (2726), Wowprime (2727),LAKAFFA(2729), LAKAFFA (2732), President (2912)	12	240
3	Sightseeing-Michelin restaurant	AMBASSADOR (2704), Silks hotel (2707), Yummy Town (2726), Wowprime (2727), Humble House (2739), Fleur de Chine (2748), The Landis (5703)	7	140
4	Sightseeing- Hotels and shopping centres	RICH (5512) and Founding (5533)	2	40
		Total	65	1300

Source from: author

4.5.4.2 Data filtering

For the company information found above, carefully screened, deleted duplicate information, inconsistent qualifications, missing information, etc. Explain and record the screening process in detail.

Table 21 Data filtering after in total

No.	Reason for deletion	Number of deletes
	The total number of collecting data in the first time without filtering.	1300
1	Delete duplicate data from Sightseeing-Michelin restaurant section, there are Yummy town (2726) and Wowprime (2727)	-40
2	Delete duplicate data from Tourism business section. The Landis (5703), HUMBLE HOUSE (2739), AMBASSADOR (2704), New palace (8940), Silks Hotel (2707), Fleur de Chine (2748), Holiday KTV (9943), 85 Degree (2723), Yummy town(2726), Wowprime (2727),THAI TOWN (2729).	-220
3	Most of the business projects are in the construction industry, and their income from the catering industry accounts for a very small part, delete form Sightseeing- Hotels and shopping centres section, RICH (5512), Founding (5533), HAEWAN (3252)	-60
4	Most of the operating income comes from home appliance manufacturing, and only a small part of the income comes from catering income, TECO (1504)	-20
5	These are no actual chain restaurants, and the main business is to supply materials to chain franchise restaurants or chain supermarkets. Sunjuice (1256), TEHMAG (1264), SIINMAG (1580),	-60
6	The main business project of Wanhwa (2701) is the rental of commercial buildings and the operation of movie theaters and mobile entertainment venues.	-20
7	These companies currently have only one store and no other branches, First Hotel (2706), Far Glory Hotel (2712), PH (2718), Chihpen Royal (5704)	-80
8	The main business of these companies is travel agency, non-catering income. Star travel (2719), Lion (2731), Ezfly (2734), Richmond (2743), Life travel (2745), PHX TOUR. (5706)	-120
9	Red Horse (2928) is a multinational management consulting company, but it has no actual catering business.	-20
10	TOPLUS (3522) and Da Lue (4804) is a food network platform and wedding consultant planning company	-40

No.	Reason for deletion	Number of deletes
11	CJW (5301) It is a jewellery company, and only one side occupation is the restaurant industry. The financial information may not be based on catering income, so it is cut off in this screening process.	-20
12	Janfusun (5701), Their main business of the amusement park.	-20
13	Power Wind (8462) is a gym centre, they do not offer restaurants service, so delete all of them.	-20
14	HILAI (1268), there are six seasons without market price from 2016 to 2017, so it would not consider.	-6
15	FX HOTELS (2724), there is no trade in September 2017, so no market price to collect.	-1
16	Tofu (2752), there is no market price from June 2017 to June 2019, also the financial report information incomplete from 2016 to 2017. Therefore, the Tofu company only 6 seasons data has been collected.	-14
17	8 Way (2754), the company has the market price since 2021, but our data collect from 2016-2020, so would not consider it in this study.	-20
18	KURA SHSHI (2754), there is only one season has market price in September 2019, but the interruption of trading will not have a market price until September 2020.	-17
19	Youngqin (2755), there is only a closing price in September 2019, but the interruption of trading will not have a market price until December 2020.	-18
20	The sample of deletions due to the data being incorrect by SPSS.	-18
	Total number of firm-quarter-years excluded	<u>-834</u>
	Total number of firm-quarter-years sample in this study.	<u>466</u>

Source from: author

4.6 Research Approach

The statistical methods used in the analysis of this study include narrative statistical analysis, multiple regression analysis models, and T test and F test methods. The following describes the analysis steps of the empirical study:

4.6.1 The descriptive analysis

This part makes a narrative statistical analysis on the research variables of different topics, presenting the characteristics and distribution of each research variable, including the ownership structure explanatory variables, control variables, and performance indicators. A general description can be used to describe each variable. Have a basic understanding of the characteristics and distribution situation.

In this study, narrative statistical analysis and correlation coefficient analysis of the research variables are firstly conducted, and then the multiple regression analysis is carried out after obtaining a preliminary understanding.

(1) Descriptive statistical analysis: First, conduct a preliminary descriptive statistical analysis of the collected data to understand the basic characteristics of the data and the distribution of the samples.

(2) Correlation coefficient analysis: Use correlation analysis to measure the direction and strength of the correlation between two variables. If the value of the correlation coefficient is very close to zero, it implies that there is no obvious linear relationship between X and Y. According to the general principle of quantity, the correlation coefficient of two independent variables above 0.8 has a high degree of linear correlation, and the problem of collinearity is very likely.

4.6.2 The multiple regression model

According to the literature discussion in Chapter two and the research hypothesis put forward in this article, the relationship between ownership structure variables and operating performance is explored, and the regression coefficients are estimated by the Ordinary Least

Squares Method (OLS) (Hult, et al., 2018). Before performing multiple regression analysis, it is necessary to establish the premises and assumptions that conform to the regression model to reduce research bias (Li, 2021). In addition, the explanatory variable in the multiple regression model must have a linear relationship with the explained variable, although in the previous literature the above pointed out that there is no linear relationship between insider's shareholding ratio and company performance (Kyere and Ausloos, 2021). However, this study consider Managerial Ownership stock hold degree divided into MRHD, DHD, MHD and CHD to observe the performance variables and shareholdings under each different shareholding ratio. The correlation between the stock ratio variables is still a kind of linear relationship and meets the restriction conditions of the regression model. Incorporating it into the multiple regression model for related analysis steps will not cause serious errors (Martinez-Ferreo and Lozano, 2021).

The purpose of the research is to explore the influence of the company's internal shareholdings, directors' shareholdings, managers (including director status) shareholdings, corporation shareholdings, and other factors into consideration on the company's operating performance and franchise degree. The regression analysis mode uses the least square method (ordinary least square, OLS) to estimate the regression coefficient and determine the significance (Hult, et al., 2018). In addition, to avoid the problem of collinearity or self-correlation among residuals caused by the high correlation between independent variables when conducting research on various issues, the accuracy of regression analysis must be affected. And the residual items perform the following verification steps:

Step 1: Collinearity verification of research variables

When the correlation between the operating variables is too high to cause the phenomenon of linear coincidence, which is the so-called collinearity problem, the variables with a high degree of correlation will cause serious mutual interference, and it is difficult for researchers to clearly distinguish between the independent variables and the corresponding variables (Tsai and Li, 2020). To improve the accuracy of the regression model of this study, it is an indispensable step to verify the existence of collinearity problems before performing regression analysis.

This study decided to use two verification methods such as Pearson Correlation analysis and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to cross-detect whether the variables have a high degree of linear overlap (Li, 2021). If the Pearson correlation coefficient value between the operating variables is less than 0.8, it is an acceptable range; and when the VIF value exceeds 10, it is necessary to further consider whether there is a problem of collinearity.

When the respective variables are highly linearly correlated, it will be difficult to distinguish the effects of the respective variables on the dependent variables, making the regression results biased. Therefore, to prevent the explanatory power of the respective variables from being affected by collinearity, certain variables must be discarded before the model is established. Some variables with high collinearity (Li, 2021). This study intends to use two verification methods, Correlation analysis and Variance Inflation Factor, to detect whether there is a high degree of linear coincidence between independent variables.

Correlation Coefficient, according to the general principle of quantity, the correlation coefficient between two independent variables is above 0.8, which means that there is a serious linear coincidence problem between the two variables (Maeenuddina, Hussain, Hafeez, Khan & Wahid, 2020).

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF), defined as $VIF = 1/(1-R_i^2)$, the R_i^2 refers to the coefficient of determination value obtained by regression analysis with the *i*-th independent variable as the dependent variable, and its value is between 0 and 1. From this definition, when the *i*-th independent variable has a high linear coincidence problem with other independent variables, the resulting R_i^2 will be very close to 1, and the VIF value will become very high (Li, 2021). The higher the VIF value, it means the problem of linear overlap between the independent variable and other independent variables becomes more serious, and when the VIF value is greater than 10, the independent variable may have a high degree of linear overlap with other independent variables, indicating the existence of collinearity (Li, 2021).

Step 2: Independence test of residual items

Using regression models for empirical research, the analysis results obtained are to reduce the prerequisite for the occurrence of bias, that is, hope that the residual items are uncorrelated or non-self-correlated, otherwise the research results will be distorted by the

influence of the correlation of the residual items. Therefore, this study will use Durbin Watson statistics for verification, that is, the DW value is used as the criterion for verifying whether the residual items are correlated (Ayunitha, et al., 2020). The closer the DW value is to 2, it can be judged that there is no self-correlation phenomenon; the closer it is to 0, it means that there is a positive self-correlation; the closer it is to 4, it means that there is a negative self, shows the correlation exists (Ayunitha, et al., 2020).

Step 3: Multiple regression analysis

After the sample of the empirical study has undergone the above two steps of verification and analysis, it is confirmed that there is no collinearity problem among the operating variables, and the residual items are also independent and will not cause any bias to the accuracy of the regression model. Multiple regression analysis (Li, 2021). This research explores the relationship between the equity structure of listed companies (manager shareholding, director shareholding and corporation shareholding) and the company's operating performance. And establish a multiple regression model. The establishment of the regression model, based on the literature discussion and the research hypotheses proposed in this article, establishes a model of the ownership structure variables and control variables for business performance and franchise degree, and verifies them (Al-Najjar, et al., 2017).

The empirical model is as follows:

Hypothesis 1~Hypothesis 4 examine the correlation between variables related to shareholding structure and company performance which are ROA and EPS (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019).

$$MO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Size_{it} + \beta_2 Size_{it}^2 + \beta_3 Lev_{it} + \beta_4 MTB_{it} + \beta_5 CapInt_{it} + \beta_6 CapInt_{it}^2 + \beta_7 FCF_{it} + \beta_8 InvRate_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Size: Firm Size

Size²: Square of Firm Size

Lev: Debt Rate

MTB: Market Capitalisation to Book value.

CapInt: Capital Intensity.

CapInt²: Square of Capital intensity.

FCF: Free Cash Flow

InvRate: Investment Rate.

The subscripts i: individual restaurant firm.

The subscripts t: quarter-year.

ε_{it} : The residual term of the regression (signifies an error term).

Hypothesis 5~Hypothesis 8 Test the correlation between the variables related to the ownership structure and the degree of franchise (DOF). Degree of the franchise where the squared term of CapInt is included to test the correlation between MO and DOF. (Rhou, Li, Singal, 2019).

$$DOF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MO_{it} + \beta_2 MO^2_{it} + \beta_3 Size_{it} + \beta_4 Risk_{it} + \beta_5 MTB_{it} + \beta_6 Growth_{it} + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

MO: Managerial ownership

MO²: Square of Managerial ownership

Size: Firm Size

Risk: Firm Risk

MTB: Market Capitalisation to Book value.

Growth: Sales Growth rate.

α : signifies firm fixed-effects.

λ : signifies year fixed-effects.

The subscripts i: individual restaurant firm.

The subscripts t: quarter-year.

ε_{it} : The residual term of the regression (signifies an error term).

$$MO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OMRate_{it} + \beta_2 Lev_{it} + \beta_3 MTB_{it} + \beta_4 CapInt_{it} + \beta_5 CapInt_{it}^2 + \beta_6 FCF_{it} + \beta_7 InvRate_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

OMRate: Operating Margin Rate

Lev: Debt Rate

MTB: Market Capitalisation to Book value.

CapInt: Capital Intensity.

CapInt²: Square of Capital intensity.

FCF: Free Cash Flow

InvRate: Investment Rate.

The subscripts i: individual restaurant firm.

The subscripts t: quarter-year.

ε_{it} : The residual term of the regression (signifies an error term).

$$DOF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DHD_{it} + \beta_2 MRHD_{it} + \beta_3 CHD_{it} + \beta_4 Size_{it} + \beta_5 Risk_{it} + \beta_6 MTB_{it} + \beta_7 Growth_{it} + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

DHD: Director hold degree

MRHD: Manager's relative hold degree

CHD: Corporation hold degree

Size: Firm Size

Risk: Firm Risk

MTB: Market Capitalisation to Book value.

Growth: Sales Growth rate.

α : signifies firm fixed-effects.

λ : signifies year fixed-effects.

The subscripts i: individual restaurant firm.

The subscripts t: quarter-year.

ε_{it} : The residual term of the regression (signifies an error term).

4.6.3 Validation of Regression models

After the regression model is established, the next step is to verify whether the regression model is effective. The regression verification methods used in this study are mainly F-test and t-test.

4.6.3.1 Regression validation, F-Test

The F test is a significant test that treats all operational variables to test whether there is a significant statistical relationship between the explained variable and all operational variables (StatisticsHowTo, 2021). Check whether the coefficients in the model are significantly different from zero to confirm whether the regression model is a valid regression model (MBASkooTeam, 2013). If the conclusion of the F test overturns the null hypothesis H_0 (regression coefficients of all operating variables are zero), it means that under a certain confidence level, there is a statistical linear relationship between the explained variable and the operating variable. On the contrary, if the conclusion of the F test cannot deny the null hypothesis, it means that the regression model has no explanatory power for the explained variables.

4.6.3.2 Regression validation, t-Test

The t test is also a significant test, which can test whether there is a significant linear relationship between a single operating variable and the explained variable. That is, check whether the coefficients in the model are significantly different from zero to confirm whether each operating variable has explanatory power for the explained variable. If the conclusion of the t test overturns the null hypothesis, it means that it is below a certain level of confidence. There is a statistical linear relationship between the explained variable and the single operating variable; on the contrary, if the conclusion of the t test cannot deny the null hypothesis, it means that the operating variable has no explanatory power for the explained variable, and there is no significant correlation between the two.

Chapter 5 Empirical analysis and results

5.1 Introduction

Based on the research method of Chapter 4, this chapter conducts an empirical study with a total of 466 firm-quarter-year samples from 28 listed companies on the Taiwan Stock Exchange from 2016 to 2020 (TWSE, 2021). First, the company's shareholding structure, franchise degree and its operating performance ratio are briefly summarised (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019). After the description, the Pearson correlation analysis of the relevant variables of the ownership structure will be carried out; then the multivariate regression analysis will be used to verify the hypothesis proposed in this study, and then to discuss the impact of the company's ownership structure on corporate performance (ROA and EPS) and the Degree of Franchise (DOF). Finally, use the Independent variables of MO, manager family shareholding ratio (MRHD), manager shareholding degree (MHD), and corporate shareholding ratio (CHD) to perform the above empirical analysis to test whether the regression analysis results will be due to the difference in shareholding ratio (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019). Resulting in changes in company performance and franchise degree.

This section is mainly divided into two parts. The first part first analyses the distribution of insider shareholding ratio during the sampling period, and then briefly introduces the characteristics of each variable in this study. The second part is to carry out the collinearity test and the independence test of the residual items mentioned in Chapter 4 among the explanatory variables.

5.2 Descriptive statistics

The research variables used in this research include Return on Assets (ROA), Earnings Per Share (EPS) that affect operating performance variables. In Ownership structure the study includes include the director sharing degree (DHD), manager with director status sharing degree (MO), manager sharing degree (MHD), corporation shareholding degree (CHD), and control variable include the asset scale (SIZE), Debt rate (Lev), Market value to book value (MTB), Capital Intensity (CapInt), Operating Margin Rate (OMRate), Investment Rate (InvRate) (Rhou, Li & Singal, 2019). It will be use in the initial statistical analysis. Use SPSS statistical software to perform model verification analysis on sample data (such as collinearity

verification, self-correlation verification, regression analysis, etc.) to understand the characteristics and distribution of the data, and to obtain the statistical relationship between various variables and business performance.

Descriptive statistical analysis. This table 22 has listed the minimum, maximum, average, and standard deviation of each variable in the sample company.

Table 22 Descriptive statistics of sample variables

Variables	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
MO	466	0.00	24.98	3.28	5.90
DHD	466	8.00	83.17	33.17	18.12
MRHD	466	0.00	39.40	2.04	4.37
CHD	466	0.00	83.48	39.56	24.68
MHD	466	0.00	11.92	1.18	1.91
Size	466	11.80	19.16	15.21	1.24
Risk	466	-717.60	408.63	-1.32	41.15
MTB	466	0.46	460.00	4.30	22.22
FCF	466	-886.10	289.85	-2.13	66.80
Lev.	466	9.90	99.91	52.94	21.16
Growth	466	-136.34	1,034.73	20.19	76.86
CapInt	466	-19.77	41.50	2.94	4.30
InvRate	466	-229.31	610.00	6.78	36.13
OMRate	466	-99.28	30.21	1.62	16.52
ROA	466	-1,340.00	723.00	4.83	180.05
EPS	466	-8.62	29.83	1.66	3.40
DOF	466	0.00	100.00	16.12	31.33

Source from: author

In terms of the shareholding structure of the sample companies, firstly, by observing the distribution of the shareholding ratio of managers with director status, it can be found that the sample MO ranges from 0.00% to 24.98%, and the standard deviation is as high as 5.90%, indicating that the MO situation is in each company There is a big difference between them, with an average of 3.28%. The corporation shareholding ratio (CHD) also ranges from 0.00% to 83.48%, with an average of 39.56%. The maximum value of DHD is 83.17%, and the minimum value is 8%. The maximum managerial shareholding ratio (MHD) is 11.92%, and the average is 1.18%, which is much lower than DHD and CHD, and is the lowest average among the variables of ownership structure.

From this result, it can be observed that the current shareholding structure of Taiwan's catering industry focuses on director shareholding ratio (DHD) and corporation shareholding ratio (CHD). The average numbers are high, so operations may be affected by director shareholding ratio (DHD) and corporation shareholding ratio (CHD). The corporation (legal person) shareholding ratio (CHD) has a considerable impact; as for the manager's shareholding ratio (MHD), the shareholding ratio of managers (including family relative) (MRHD), and the shareholding ratio of managers (including director status), they are obviously low, and the average number is below 5%, especially the manager's shareholding ratio (MHD) is less than 1.5%.

In the DOF variable, the highest 100 means a fully franchised firm, and the lowest 0 means a fully company-owned firm. The average value is 16.12% and the standard deviation is as high as 31.33%, indicating that there are big differences between companies. In the Growth variables, the highest is 1034.73, the lowest is -136.34, the standard deviation is 76.86%, and the average is 20.19%, indicating that there is a big difference in operating growth between different companies. Company scale (SIZE) is the lowest difference, the standard deviation is only 1.24, and the average is 15.21.

The Figures 9 and 10 present the changes in average Managerial Ownership (MO) and Degree of Franchise (DOF) during the 2016-2020 sample period. In the Figure 9 shows, MO is decreased 4.29% in 2016 season one to 2.72% in 2018 season four.

Figure 9 Managerial Ownership from 2016-2020.

From the figures 10, the DOF dropped slightly by about 2.63% from 2016 to 2018, consistent with the findings of prior research (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019). Since the end of 2018, Taiwan’s catering industry has started to take off. Many franchise system activities, from this chart, it can be known that the end of 2018 is 12.34%, and the number of franchised stores has increased by leaps and bounds. By the end of 2020, DOF has reached 25.54%.

This figure 9 shows that the lower the Managerial ownership (MO), the higher the Degree of Franchise (DOF) from the 2016-2020 period. However, the magnitude is not obvious, and may only have a slight impact. However, in the second quarter to the third quarter of 2019, the data showed that MO increased from 3.10% to 3.39%, while DOF increased significantly from 16.02% to 23.69%.

Figure 10 Degree of Franchise from 2016-2020

5.3 Multicollinearity Analysis

The so-called multicollinearity or linear coincidence refers to the possibility of a high linear correlation between two or more independent variables. When the linear coincidence of the independent variables in the regression model occurs, it is difficult to distinguish the effects of the respective variables on the variables, because the changes in these variables are highly correlated. Usually, it has been used correlation coefficient analysis and variance inflation factor (VIF) as the criteria for judging whether independent variables have collinearity (Li, 2021).

5.3.1 Correlation coefficient Analysis

As mentioned in Chapter 4, before conducting regression research on the relationship between variables, it is necessary to test whether the interaction between the explanatory variables is too close, which will affect the authenticity of the regression results. Moreover, this study is based on 28 listed companies as the sampling target, plus the sampling period is 5 years, 20 quarters, and there is a total of 466 sample points. Therefore, this study assumes that the sample is distributed under normal conditions, and the Pearson correlation coefficient test is performed. In addition, then use the VIF index to verify whether the correlation between the variables is consistent with the results of the Pearson correlation coefficient test. Moreover, the VIF indicators of the regression formula are all less than the critical value of 10, so there is no serious collinearity between the explanatory variables in the regression. From the Pearson's correlation Matrix table 23, it can be found that most of the variables have a degree of correlation with each other.

To further understand the relationship between variables, Pearson correlation coefficient analysis can generally be divided into three levels: a correlation coefficient less than 0.3 is a low linear correlation (StatisticsHowTo, 2021); a correlation coefficient between 0.3 and 0.7 is a medium linear correlation; a correlation between 0.7 and 1 The coefficient is highly linear. If there is a high degree of linear correlation between variables, collinearity is likely to occur (KENTON, 2021). Therefore, through correlation test analysis, check whether there is too high correlation between variables.

Table 23 shows the correlation between the independent variables. From Table 23, in terms of shareholding structure, the percentage of shares held by managers and the percentage of shares held by managers (including director status) are positively correlated at a significant level of $\alpha=0.01$. The possible reason is that directors tend to agree to the "interest convergence theory" (Maialeh, 2020). According to the view, that managers hold large shares, there are greater incentives to be an effective supervisor, reduce agency costs and increase operating performance, so they are more willing to invest in companies with a high proportion of directors (Chaharmahali & Tavakolnia, 2019).

Pearson correlation analysis is used to explore the linear correlation between two continuous variables (X, Y). If the absolute value of the correlation coefficient between the two variables is larger, it means that the degree of mutual covariation is greater (Makowski, et al.,2020). If the two variables are positively correlated, when X increases, Y will also increase; conversely, if the two variables are negatively correlated, when X increases, Y will decrease accordingly (StatisticsHowTo, 2021). Sen correlation analysis cannot accurately detect Nonlinear correlations.

The formula of Pearson's correlation coefficient is:

$$r(x, y) = \frac{COV(x, y)}{S_x S_y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Note: r is the correlation coefficient, COV is the covariate, \bar{x} is the average of x, \bar{y} is the average of y.

Table 23 Pearson's Correlation Matrix.

Variables	Test	MO	MRHD	DHD	CHD	Size	Lev	MTB	CapInt	FCF	Risk	InvRate	Growth	OMRate	ROA	EPS
MRHD	Pearson	.311**														
	Two-Tailed Test	.000														
DHD	Pearson	.068	-.213**													
	Two-Tailed Test	.129	.000													
CHD	Pearson	-.345**	-.228**	.087												
	Two-Tailed Test	.000	.000	.052												
Size	Pearson	.027	-.245**	.071	.040											
	Two-Tailed Test	.539	.000	.114	.370											
Lev	Pearson	-.134**	.019	.070	-.389**	.155**										
	Two-Tailed Test	.003	.678	.118	.000	.000										
MTB	Pearson	-.036	-.038	.129**	-.111*	-.053	.174**									
	Two-Tailed Test	.422	.394	.004	.013	.238	.000									
CapInt	Pearson	-.122**	-.032	-.095*	-.131**	-.022	.236**	-.013								
	Two-Tailed Test	.006	.474	.032	.003	.628	.000	.775								
FCF	Pearson	.004	-.031	.011	.070	.089*	-.077	-.084	-.142**							
	Two-Tailed Test	.931	.485	.805	.115	.046	.083	.059	.001							
Risk	Pearson	-.021	-.052	.015	-.027	.004	.016	.054	.013	-.010						
	Two-Tailed Test	.636	.241	.730	.540	.937	.721	.228	.773	.815						
InvRate	Pearson	.005	-.085	.077	-.046	-.014	.030	.244**	-.118**	-.408**	.000					
	Two-Tailed Test	.910	.056	.083	.300	.758	.506	.000	.008	.000	.992					
Growth	Pearson	.010	-.005	-.048	.012	.019	.021	-.028	-.140**	.037	.057	.013				
	Two-Tailed Test	.829	.902	.284	.785	.673	.638	.530	.002	.410	.203	.773				
OMRate	Pearson	.069	-.151**	-.029	.296**	.267**	-.466**	-.162**	-.408**	.256**	-.047	-.021	.105*			
	Two-Tailed Test	.123	.001	.511	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.291	.642	.019			
ROA	Pearson	-.033	-.023	-.126**	.361**	.031	-.406**	-.128**	-.256**	.153**	-.002	.046	.035	.531**		
	Two-Tailed Test	.463	.610	.005	.000	.482	.000	.004	.000	.001	.966	.300	.439	.000		
EPS	Pearson	.400**	-.142**	.153**	.024	.427**	-.152**	-.009	-.337**	.113*	-.006	.094*	.149**	.425**	.215**	
	Two-Tailed Test	.000	.001	.001	.589	.000	.001	.838	.000	.011	.886	.035	.001	.000	.000	
DOF	Pearson	.177**	.043	.137**	-.220**	.258**	.012	.024	-.285**	.011	-.070	.108*	.056	.155**	.047	.305**
	Two-Tailed Test	.000	.334	.002	.000	.000	.788	.597	.000	.808	.117	.015	.213	.000	.288	.000

Note: N=466, * $\alpha < 0.01$ (Two-Tailed Test), ** $\alpha < 0.05$ (Two-Tailed Test)

5.3.2 VIF (variance inflation factor) Analysis

Collinearity is defined as: $VIF_i = \frac{1}{1-R_i^2}$

The VIF values of the respective variables used in this study are listed in Table 24. It can be seen from Table 24 that the VIF values of all independent variables are less than 10. Therefore, based on this criterion, there is no problem of collinearity among independent variables.

Table 24 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 1

Variables	Collinearity statistics
	Model 1-VIF
Size	1.017
Risk	1.009
MTB	1.011
Growth	1.005
MO	11.201
MO ²	11.220

Note: $VIF_i > 10$ collinearity problem

Table 25 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 2

Variables	Collinearity statistics
	Model 2-VIF
Size	235.213
Size2	236.285
Lev.	1.192
MTB	1.109
CapInt	2.588
CapInt2	2.399
FCF	1.284
InvRate	1.327

Note: $VIF_i > 10$ collinearity problem

Table 26 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 3

Variables	Collinearity statistics
	Model 3-VIF
Size	1.070
Risk	1.010
MTB	1.042
Growth	1.007
DHD	1.071
MRHD	1.169
CHD	1.077

Note: $VIF_i > 10$ collinearity problem

Table 27 VIF statistics of sample independent variables on Model 4

Variables	Collinearity statistics
	Model 4-VIF
OMRate	1.551
Lev.	1.308
MTB	1.115
CapInt	2.582
CapInt2	2.375
FCF	1.322
InvRate	1.327

Note: $VIF_i > 10$ collinearity problem

5.3.3 Independence Test of Residuals

This study uses Durbin Watson's statistic test to detect whether the residual items tend to be self-correlated. The results show that regardless of ROA, EPS, or DOF as DV, the D-W value of this regression is not between 1.5 and 2. Therefore, it can be inferred that the residual items of this regression model are self-correlated with each other in different periods.

To prevent bias in the results produced by the regression model, the residual items in the regression model are required to be non-self-correlated and randomly distributed. In this study, the DW value is used as the criterion for determining whether there is self-correlation between variables. When the DW value is close to 2, it is judged that there is no self-correlation. The calculation method of DW value is:

$$DW = \frac{\sum_{t=2}^T (e_t - e_{t-1})^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T e_t^2}$$

From Table 28, the DW values of the regression type used in this study are as follows, so it is determined that the residuals are randomly distributed.

Table 28 Regression DW statistics on Model 3

Model 3	Regression ROA	Regression EPS	Regression DOF
DW-value	0.861	0.873	0.167

$$DOF_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DHD_{it} + \beta_2 MRHD_{it} + \beta_3 CHD_{it} + \beta_4 Size_{it} + \beta_5 Risk_{it} + \beta_6 MTB_{it} + \beta_7 Growth_{it} + \alpha_i + \lambda_t + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Table 29 Regression DW statistics on Model 4

Model 4	Regression ROA	Regression EPS	Regression DOF
DW-value	0.875	0.998	0.236

$$MO_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OMRate_{it} + \beta_2 Lev_{it} + \beta_3 MTB_{it} + \beta_4 CapInt_{it} + \beta_5 CapInt_{it}^2 + \beta_6 FCF_{it} + \beta_7 InvRate_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

5.4 Empirical Results-Regression Analysis

This section uses least squares (OLS) regression model analysis (Hult, et al., 2018) to explore operating performance, equity structure variables, and financial factors variables to further verify the research hypothesis of this article.

This section mainly discusses the influence of the ownership structure (MO, MHD, MRHD, DHD, CHD) on company performance ROA and EPS based on the regression model and its variable definitions established in Chapter 3. This section will be divided into three parts. The first part is the performance variable as the contingency number DV in the regression formula, which is ROA, EPS and DOF. Moreover, considering that the ownership structure and corporate governance have varying degrees of impact on the operating performance of companies of different sizes (such as inadequate disclosure of small company information). It not only adds the company's net sales growth as the controlling variable of company size in the regression formula. Bring in the regression formula to analyse, and then compare the results with the results obtained by using the full sample as the data to observe whether there will be any inconsistencies. The second part considers the company's own characteristics (fixed effects). Whether it will affect the results of the regression formula, so add the

company's fixed effect to the regression formula and check whether the addition of this variable will cause differences in the regression analysis results.

Based on the multiple regression model established in Chapter 4, this research examines the four independent variables IV of the three dimensions to understand the direction and significant correlation of changes in operating performance of the respective independent variables (IV) and analyses its empirical results. The regression analysis results are shown in Table 28-29.

The following is the order in which the research hypotheses are established to illustrate the letters of intent of the empirical results of this article.

5.4.1 Analysis of the correlation coefficient between the ownership structure and ROA and EPS

RH1: Under different managerial family levels of shareholding with a Nonlinear relationship, that the increase in shareholding ratio has significantly different impacts on company performance.

According to the research results in Table 34-35, overall, under the F test, the ownership structure and operating performance have a slight and significant impact. In addition, the study looks at the significant situation under different shareholding ratios individually. The result shows that the relationship between MRHD and ROA of manager (including family) shareholding ratio reaches a significant level with a p-value of 0.040 ($P < 0.05$), but the relationship between manager (including family relative) shareholding ratio (MRHD) and EPS is not significant. Under different operating performance evaluation standards, this would be significant.

Table 30 Hypothesis 1 result

Hypothesis	Result
H1a (MRHD on ROA)	Valid
H1b (MRHD on EPS)	Invalid

Source form: author

RH2: There is a negative relationship between the director status of a manager and the company's operating performance.

From the research results in Tables 34-35, it is known that the relationship between the shareholding ratio of managers with director status (MO) and ROA does not show a significant level, p-value is 0.051, but the manager also has director status (MO) with shareholding ratio to EPS It is exact significant ($P < 0.001$), and the p-value is 0.000.

Table 31 Hypothesis 2 result

Hypothesis	Result
H2a (MO on ROA)	Invalid
H2b (MO on EPS)	Valid

Source form: author

RH3 : The manager' s ratio of shareholding has a positive impact on company performance.

From the research results in Table 34-35, it is known that the shareholding ratio of managers (MHD) is very significant to ROA ($P < 0.001$), and the shareholding ratio of managers (MHD) is also very significant to EPS ($P < 0.001$).

Table 32 Hypothesis 3 result

Hypothesis	Result
H3a (MHD on ROA)	Valid
H3b (MHD on EPS)	Valid

Source form: author

RH4 : The corporation' s shareholding ratio has a positive impact on company performance.

According to the research results in Table 34-35, the shareholding ratio of corporation (CHD) is very significant to ROA ($P < 0.001$), and p-value is 0.000. But the corporation (CHD) shareholding ratio is significant to EPS, $P = 0.038$ ($P < 0.05$). It can be known that corporation shareholdings usually have a positive meaning for the general investment public, which in turn affects EPS. However, it has a very large impact on ROA and is relevant.

Table 33 Hypothesis 4 result

Hypothesis	Result
H4a (CHD on ROA)	Valid
H4b (CHD on EPS)	Valid

Source form: author

Table 34 Regression Analysis of Ownership structure and ROA

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	△R ²
MO	-2.877	-0.094		-1.959	.051			
MHD	19.175	0.197	18.107***	3.744	.000***	466	0.269	0.07
MRHD ²	-13.499	-0.094		-2.055	.040*			
CHD	1.863	0.256		5.345	.000***			

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

Table 35 Regression Analysis of Ownership structure and EPS

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	△R ²
MO	0.308	0.532		11.833	.000***			
MHD	-0.492	-0.267	27.526***	-5.424	.000***	466	0.359	0.206
MRHD ²	-0.189	-0.069		-1.625	0.105			
CHD	0.013	0.093		2.084	.038*			

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

5.4.2 Analysis of the correlation coefficient between ownership structure and DOF

RH5: Under different managerial family shareholding degrees, with a Nonlinear relationship, an increase in the shareholding ratio has significant differences in the impact of the company's franchise degree.

The research results from Table 36 show that the shareholding ratio of managers (including families) has a significant P=0.004 (P<0.01). This assumption is true. In terms of company management policies, expansion of franchise can be considered as a consideration for evaluating management capabilities, which may improve the company's overall performance and increase the number of franchise stores.

RH6: There is a positive relationship between manager (including director status) and franchise degree.

From the research results in Table 36, it is known that the shareholding ratio of managers with director status (MO) has no significant effect on the degree of franchise. This hypothesis is invalid.

RH7 : Manager' s shareholding ratio has a positive impact on the degree of franchise.

From the research results in Table 36, it is known that the proportion of MHD manager's shareholding has a positive relationship with the degree of franchise, $P=0.012$ ($P<0.05$). This hypothesis is valid.

RH8 : The corporation' shareholding ratio of has a positive impact on the company's franchise degree.

The research results from Table 36 show that the proportion of corporate shareholding is positively correlated with DOF, which is very significant, with a p-value of 0.000 ($P<0.001$). This hypothesis is valid.

Table 36 Regression Analysis of Ownership Structure and DOF

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	ΔR ²
MO	-0.041	-0.008		-0.152	0.879			
MHD	2.358	0.14	10.956***	2.517	.012*	466	0.182	0.076
MRHD ²	-3.437	-0.138		-2.861	.004**			
CHD	-0.287	-0.228		-4.499	.000***			

Note: Note: * $P<0.05$, ** $P<0.01$, *** $P<0.001$

5.4.3 Regression analysis of ROA performance under MO model

Under the MO model, the regression analysis of financial factors, only debt ratio (Lev.) has an incredibly significant effect on ROA performance $P<0.001$, and capital intensity (CapInt) has a significant effect on ROA performance.

Table 37 Regression analysis with ROA as the performance measure on MO

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	ΔR ²
Lev.	-2.345	-0.276		-6.098	.000***			
MTB	-0.507	-0.063		-1.543	0.124			
CapInt	-8.938	-0.214	18.107***	-3.504	.001**	466	0.269	0.07
CapInt ²	0.124	0.068		1.144	0.253			
InvRate	0.303	0.061		1.509	0.132			

Note: Note: * $P<0.05$, ** $P<0.01$, *** $P<0.001$

5.4.4 Regression analysis of EPS performance under MO model

Under the MO model, under the regression analysis of financial factors, the correlation coefficient analysis of capital intensity (CapInt.) on EPS is exceedingly significant p-value

<0.001. In addition, the correlation coefficient analysis of EPS and the square of capital intensity (p-value is 0.004) showed significant (P<0.01). The other variables are not significant. This MO model's regression analysis on EPS, it shows that only capital intensity is significant for EPS.

Table 38 Regression analysis with EPS on MO model

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	ΔR ²
Lev.	0.001	0.008		0.178	0.859			
MTB	-0.001	-0.004		-0.093	0.926			
CapInt	-0.294	-0.371	27.526***	-6.504	.000***	466	0.359	0.206
CapInt ²	0.006	0.162		2.888	.004**			
InvRate	0.004	0.042		1.123	0.262			

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

5.4.5 Regression analysis of DOF performance under the DOF model

Under the DOF model, the regression analysis of the ownership structure and financial factors shows that the shareholding ratio of corporations is significant (P<0.001), and the shareholding ratio of corporations (CHD) is extremely significant (P<0.001). The remaining variables are not significant. CHD is like the consumer public's brand impression of an organisation, so it is related to the brand awareness theory. Macdonald and Sharp (2000) also pointed out that brand awareness is very important to customers' consumption decisions. Brand awareness may enter the combination of brand product considerations, and it can also affect the brand's choice in these combinations. In the shareholder structure, the legal person's shareholding (CHD) and the capital intensity of financial factors CapInt both affect the degree of franchise and have a significant correlation.

Table 39 Regression analysis with DOF on DOF model

Variables	Coefficient	SE-BETA	F-value	t-value	p-value	N	R ²	ΔR ²
MO	-0.041	-0.008		-0.152	0.879			
CHD	-0.287	-0.228		-4.499	.000***			
MTB	-0.012	-0.009	10.956***	-0.2	0.842	466	0.182	0.076
CapInt.	-3.054	-0.422		-6.545	.000***			
CapInt.2	0.047	0.15		2.369	.018*			
Growth	0.009	0.021		0.509	0.611			

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

5.5 Regression Analysis with different business code and model summary

Among the 28 catering industry companies, according to the industry code of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, they can be subdivided into four categories, namely Drink section (F501030), Pub section (F501050), Restaurant section (501060) and other catering section (501990) (MOEA,2015). Some industries have multiple industry codes. For example, Humble House (2739) has four business codes (Drink, Pub, Restaurant and Others catering industry) (MOEA, 2021). Although some companies are repeated in different groups, they can still be analysed according to the four categories making a regression analysis description.

5.5.1 The four catering Type on ROA

For the four major categories of catering industries, the ROA regression analysis was performed, and it was found from the F test that they were all very significant. In the T test, in the model 3 regression analysis, Firm size (SIZE) variable on ROA in the Pub section was slightly significant, MTB, director shareholding degree (DHD) and Manager relative shareholding degree (MRHD) variables on ROA in pub section has and extremely negative correlation. Market to book price (MTB) variable on ROA in Drink section and Restaurant section are slightly significant. DHD variable on ROA in Restaurant section and Other catering section are both significant. The same principle can be proved, the results of these studies are consistent with the literature discussion in Chapter 2; the impact of shareholding ratio on company operating performance (Wang & Chiang, 2020). The franchise level associated with management ownership has reached an optimal level, which means that management shareholders can improve the company's operating performance by setting corporate goals and designing effective incentive contracts or bonus (Rhou, et. al., 2019). In the model 4 regression analysis of debt ratio (Lev.) to ROA, the Pub and Restaurant section industries show negative correlation, but the Drink section and other catering section's debt ratio (Lev.) are not significant. Free Cash Flow (FCF) and Investment rate (InvRate) variables on ROA in the Drink section show great importance. Operating profitability ratio (OmRate) variable on ROA in Restaurant and other catering sections shows favourable influence. In Capital Intensity (CapInt) regression analysis on ROA, the Pub section is slightly significant.

Table 40 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on ROA

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
SIZE	- 0.062	- 0.818	- 0.238	-2.374*	-0.094	- 1.685	0.126	1.643
RISK	0.021	0.363	0.072	1.145	0.016	0.358	0.018	0.258
MTB	0.144	2.034*	-0.807	-8.127***	0.119	2.194*	- 0.071	- 0.984
GROWTH	- 0.027	- 0.452	- 0.025	- 0.401	-0.041	-0.893	0.107	1.524
DHD	- 0.052	- 0.856	-1.088	- 11.543***	-0.127	- 2.685**	- 0.202	- 2.548*
MRHD	0.058	0.857	0.304	3.398***	- 0.016	-0.318	0.114	1.498
CHD	0.122	1.940	- 0.099	- 1.410	0.340	6.812***	0.208	2.649**
R ²	0.035		0.720		0.139		0.191	
ΔR ²	0.014		0.570		0.116		0.107	
F	1.432		28.598***		9.585***		5.828***	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

Table 41 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on ROA

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
OMRATE	0.202	2.958*	0.193	1.229	0.350	6.340***	0.473	6.294***
LEV	-0.109	-1.903	-0.443	-4.236***	-0.189	-3.827***	-0.117	-1.582
MTB	-0.008	-0.143	-0.168	-1.727	0.018	0.379	-0.050	-0.729
CAPINT	-0.167	-1.643	0.878	3.332**	-0.056	-0.900	-0.095	-0.686
CAP2	-0.078	-0.746	-0.690	-2.743*	-0.032	-0.511	0.116	0.900
FCF	0.232	4.150***	0.149	0.995	0.013	0.273	0.118	1.492
INVRATE	0.252	4.647***	0.307	2.669*	0.072	1.604	0.167	2.060*
R ²	0.316		0.600		0.276		0.336	
ΔR ²	0.316		0.600		0.276		0.336	
F	18.359***		16.746***		22.733***		12.525***	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

5.5.2 The catering industries on EPS

The regression analysis of EPS for the four categories shows that all of them are very relevant according to the F test. In addition, starting the t-test, in the model 3 regression analysis, In the regression analysis of Sales Growth (Growth) variable on EPS, all sections are not significant at all. In the regression analysis of MRHD on EPS, all sections are slight significant. In the Corporate shareholding Degree (CHD) regression analysis on EPS, the other catering section is invalid, and the remaining three industries are very significant. This result supports the "efficiency regulation hypothesis" proposed by Pound (1988), that is, institutional

investors have more professional talents, easier access to information and professional knowledge. Institutional investors are more professional than small investors and can effectively monitor the company and increase the company's value. The higher the shareholding ratio of institutional investors is within a company, means that institutional investors have confidence in the company's operating performance and future development. It is a worthy investment target and proves that the company is strong. Therefore, CHD has supervisory capabilities and plays a positive role in corporate governance.

In the model 4 regression analysis, the debt ratio (Lev) in the EPS regression analysis is not significant, only Other catering section has a slight correlation. In Capital intensity (CapInt) and Operating Margin Rate (OMRate) both variables in model 4 regression analysis on EPS, all sections are significant, but CapInt variable analysis show negative correlation. The results of this study confirm a previous study in the USA (Song, Park and Lee, 2019). The Investment Rate (InvRate) in model 4 regression analysis on EPS shows only the Restaurant section is slightly related. In the regression analysis of MTB on EPS, the results under a whole sample are not correlated, but under the model 3 and model 4 in the Drink section, Pub section and Restaurant section these three industries are very related.

Table 42 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on EPS

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
SIZE	0.226	3.535***	-0.177	-1.400	0.232	4.727***	0.566	8.383***
RISK	-0.015	-0.291	0.018	0.219	-0.012	-0.309	0.002	0.031
MTB	0.308	5.134***	0.471	3.756***	0.358	7.508***	0.057	0.899
GROWTH	0.071	1.408	0.220	2.744	0.072	1.767	0.151	2.434*
DHD	0.157	3.042*	-0.052	-0.434	0.126	3.022*	-0.203	-2.909*
MRHD	-0.134	-2.343*	-0.249	-2.209*	-0.099	-2.166*	-0.155	-2.321*
CHD	-0.202	-3.791***	-0.432	-4.852***	-0.136	-3.080*	-0.054	-0.785
R ²	0.313		0.554		0.329		0.375	
△R ²	0.055		0.208		0.030		0.036	
F	18.120***		13.830***		29.166***		14.844***	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

Table 43 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on EPS

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
OMRATE	0.342	5.270***	0.501	3.453**	0.297	5.718***	0.419	5.461***
LEV	-0.047	-0.871	0.061	0.625	-0.032	-0.687	0.199	2.646*
MTB	0.281	5.117***	0.494	5.497***	0.399	8.970***	0.047	0.674
CAPINT	-0.468	-4.844***	-1.363	-5.582***	-0.139	-2.355*	-0.653	-4.622***
CAP2	0.431	4.343***	0.733	3.144*	0.155	2.602*	0.482	3.652***
FCF	0.093	1.755	-0.033	-0.241	0.060	1.342	0.067	0.825
INVRATE	0.089	1.726	-0.102	-0.954	0.116	2.762*	0.027	0.330
R ²	0.385		0.657		0.357		0.309	
ΔR ²	0.385		0.657		0.357		0.309	
F	24.823***		21.375***		33.047***		11.050***	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$

5.5.3 The catering industries on DOF

The four categories show regression analysis on DOF, and it is found from the F test that all of them are fully relevant. Under the financial factors, In the MTB regression analysis of DOF, Drink section, Pub section and Restaurant section are related. In the regression analysis of capital intensity (CapInt) to DOF, Drink section and Pub section show a slight negative correlation. The Restaurant section is not relevant, but the Other catering section shows a highly negative correlation. In the regression analysis of the Growth rate (Growth) on DOF, all sections are significant. Under the ownership structure, the Pub section shows negative correlation in the regression analysis of DHD to franchise degree, but the Restaurant section has a positive correlation. In addition, in the Restaurant section, the shareholding ratio of managers (including families) is almost all significant in the DOF regression analysis, only the other catering section is not significant. Finally, in the regression analysis of CHD on DOF shows what all sections are significant, mentioning the literature on ownership and corporate performance in Chapter 3, Zhuang (2005) pointed out that the institutional legal person shareholding ratio was empirically analysed using Taiwan listed company data and found that the shareholding ratio was significantly negatively correlated with corporate performance.

Table 44 Model 3 Regression analysis the catering industries on DOF

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
SIZE	0.322	5.547***	0.077	3.827***	0.222	4.973***	0.296	3.667 ***
RISK	-0.090	-1.992*	0.018	1.396	-0.080	-2.197*	0.095	1.276
MTB	0.390	7.165***	-0.079	-3.978***	0.468	10.778***	-0.035	-0.460
GROWTH	-0.035	-0.773	0.003	0.266	-0.024	-0.637	0.071	0.955
DHD	0.086	1.836	-0.161	-8.476***	0.158	4.169***	-0.051	-0.611
MRHD	0.110	2.118*	1.032	57.439***	0.100	2.402*	0.003	0.038
CHD	-0.209	-4.328***	-0.074	-5.237***	-0.239	-5.950***	-0.254	-3.071*
R ²	0.434		0.989		0.445		0.105	
ΔR ²	0.067		0.509		0.086		0.051	
F	30.432***		970.931***		47.761***		2.903*	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

Table 45 Model 4 Regression analysis the catering industries on DOF

Variables	Drink section		Pub section		Restaurant section		Other catering section	
	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value	coefficient	t-Value
OMRATE	0.037	0.544	-0.170	-0.812	0.019	0.351	0.019	0.233
LEV	-0.052	-0.906	-0.388	-2.780	0.003	0.055	-0.062	-0.779
MTB	0.504	8.719***	0.365	2.823*	0.530	11.623***	-0.013	-0.179
CAPINT	-0.218	-2.144*	-0.412	-1.172*	-0.079	-1.305	-0.767	-5.095***
CAP2	0.153	1.465	0.199	0.593	0.024	0.394	0.536	3.812***
FCF	-0.001	-0.023	0.016	0.080	-0.011	-0.235	0.067	0.779
INVRATE	0.011	0.207	0.323	2.099*	0.049	1.127	0.096	1.094
R ²	0.317		0.289		0.322		0.216	
ΔR ²	0.317		0.289		0.322		0.216	
F	18.430***		4.522***		28.323***		6.806***	
N	285		85		424		180	

Note: *P<0.05 , **P<0.01 , ***P<0.001

5.6 Research Findings and Discussion

Corporate governance factors may be affected by institutional settings. It is worth noting that Asia's socioeconomic institutional settings and behavioural characteristics are different from those of Western economies (Sheikh, et al., 2018). In unique features of this study, the model 3 MO, and the model 4 DOF have been created the key unique contributions by this study. Using empirical models in order to gratify the development's principal goal for finding the level of franchising and managerial ownership in Taiwan restaurant industry performances. The model 1 MO and the model 2 DOF were from the research (Rhou, Li and Singal, 2019) analysis models, these two formulas first use the data of Taiwanese restaurants to perform

multiple regression analysis, besides use the model 3 and the model 4 to perform multiple regression analysis. Furthermore, the model 3 is the new MO model, the different between model 1 which is added the operating margin rate variables and remove the firm size variables. The model 4 is the new DOF model, the different between model 2 is added the director hold degree variables, manager's relative hold degree variables, corporation hold degree variables and removed the MO variables. Due to those new variables using in the model 3 and the model 4 is much appropriate to this study and it is necessary to investigate the managerial ownership within the level franchise Taiwan restaurant industry.

Additionally, there are many restaurants in Taiwan setting up their business from family members, subsequently there are family businesses. Some of businesses their directors are family members, it is important to extra consider that the director hold share degree, manager's relative hold share degree and corporation hold share degree in the DOF model to multiple regression analysis, of course keep the existing variables, firm size, firm risk, market capitalisation to book value variables and sales growth rate variables in the DOF model 4. Jiraporn & Davidson (2019) believes that building knowledge about a company takes a lot of time and requires fully understanding the company's affairs by attending board meetings where information is shared and discussed. If directors have too many board appointments, it will be difficult for them to focus on and remain involved in the company's affairs (Sheikh, et al., 2018).

It is known from the regression analysis of all the above samples and the regression analysis of the classification industry code. Debt ratio (Lev.) regression analysis on ROA, the pub and restaurant sections are valid, except the Drink section and other catering section. In the corresponding whole sample regression analysis, it shows significant measures. Moreover, in the regression analysis of MTB on ROA, most of the different types of industries are significant, and only other catering is not significant, especially, in the whole sample base, it is invalid. It may be that the amount of data is large, and the significance is diluted. CapInt on ROA regression analysis shows significant in whole samples base, but only the Pub section shows slight significant. The investment rate (InvRate) on ROA is not significant in restaurants section.

Under the ownership structure, regression analysis on ROA, DHD in individual sections, Pub, Restaurant and Other catering sections are significant; MRHD is significant for the whole

samples base, but in the individual section only pub section shows as significant. CHD is not significant in all sections, but for the whole samples is very significant, indicating that mass investors, in a nutshell, will evaluate their business performance by the number of shares held by public. When directors have large board appointments, they may become overcommitted, which can compromise their ability to provide advice and oversight to senior management on behalf of shareholders (Ferris, et al., cited in Latif, et al., 2023).

The regression analysis on EPS, in individual industries, the debt ratio (Lev) is significant only in other catering section, and the remaining three industries are not significant, but it shows not significant in the regression analysis of the whole catering industry. In the MTB regression analysis on DOF, only other catering is not significant, but it is not significant under a large sample (whole catering industry). On the contrary, in the regression analysis of capital intensity on DOF, only the Other catering section is not significant, but significant in a large sample (whole catering industry). The growth rate (Growth) is not significant in all sections. The investment rate (InvRate) is not significant in the Restaurant section, but it is significant in the whole catering industry. Under the ownership structure and EPS regression analysis, MO, MHD and CHD are significant in the catering industry; regression analysis of ownership structure and ROA, MHD, MRHD and CHD are significant in all sections (Li, 2021). However, the CHD is significant for all sections (Zhuang, 2005; Hult, et al., 2018). The regression analysis on DOF, CHD and CapInt are significant in all sections, CapInt is not significant in the restaurant section, the rest are significant, and the whole sample of catering sections are very significant. InvRate is slightly significant in the pub section. Hwang and Jung (2016) found that the corporate governance index has a significant positive relation on the market-to-book value ratio.

Under the shareholding structure, regression analysis on DOF, MO is only significant for Pub section, and the rest are not significant. MHD is not significant in drink and the Restaurant sections, other catering industries significant. The shareholding ratio of managers (including family relative) MRHD is not significant in other catering, and the others are significant. Although the significant inconsistency of individual industries is seen, it means that under the influence of the general environment, family-owned businesses still have a positive correlation with the expansion of franchise stores. The corporate shareholding ratio CHD returns on DOF. Except pub and other catering industries are irrelevant, the rest are related. The regression under the whole catering industry shows highly significant.

Chapter 6- Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

From this research, before 2018, franchise catering was not common. However, in Taiwan since 2018 there has been a significant increase in franchise system business activities. The catering industry is the largest. The catering industry is divided into four categories, including Drink section, Pub section, Restaurant section and Other catering section. From 2018 to 2020, the Taiwan's catering industry franchise rate has increased rapid by 106.97%.

6.2 Analysis conclusion

Clarify in response to this research questions, in research question 1, Analysis of the role of equity structure on financial performance and research question 2, Analysis of the role of the managerial ownership model affect the performance of the company. Financial performance is viewed using Return on assets (ROA) and Earnings Per Share (EPS). Looking at the impact of ownership structure on financial performance, both managerial shareholding and institutional shareholding have a positive effect on the company's financial performance. However, when the manager has a shareholding status as a director, although the performance in Return on assets (ROA) is futile, the performance in Earnings Per Share (EPS) is affirmative. In addition, when the manager's relatives hold shares, they are ineffective for EPS performance, but effective for ROA performance. From this result, when public investors have a positive view of whether a manager has director status, the Earnings Per Share (EPS) is effective. However, in practice, the person may have selfish purposes in operations business, and their director status can affect some of the company's important decisions, so their Return on assets (ROA) performance is no-good. In research question 3, Analysis of the role of the level of franchising and managerial ownership compare. The level of franchising is viewed using DOF, just mentioned that when a manager with director status, the Return on assets (ROA) performance is negative, and the DOF is the same. From the results, when engaging in the development of a franchise business, managers should avoid having director status, otherwise their development performance would be negative, it would be of no value. In addition, when the manager owns shares and the manager's relative's own shares from the company, the level of franchising shows positive. The DOF performance takes optimistic when institutional investors own shares of the company.

This study uses ROA and earnings per share (EPS) as performance indicators to explore the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms, including internal manager (with director status) shareholding ratio, manager shareholding ratio, and corporate operating performance. The empirical results of this research are summarised as follows.

Manager shareholding degree (MHD), the empirical results show that the level of manager's shareholding does have a specific impact on the company's performance. The reason may be that Taiwan's main tourism focus is food, and the manager's shareholding ratio is more than 1%. As shown in Table 25, managers shareholding ratio is 1.18%. In the regression analysis, it is significant for ROA, EPS or DOF. Therefore, this variable has a significant impact on the company's operating performance.

Manger with relative shareholding degree (MRHD), the MRHD has a collinearity problem ($VIF > 10$). After the deleting of this variable, the regression analysis is performed again. This labouratory uses the $MRHD^2$ to perform regression analysis on ROA. There is no collinearity problem ($VIF < 10$). $MRHD^2$ instead the MRHD variables. The regression analysis results have a significant impact on ROA and DOF, but there are not significant on EPS.

Manager with Director status shareholding degree (MO), the empirical results show that the shareholding ratio of managers with shareholder status has a specific and obvious impact on company performance, because the Restaurant section is a service industry, and shareholders with director status have also increased their contribution to the company. According to the research results, it is found that MO is related to ROA, MO is related to EPS, and MO is not related to DOF. Therefore, the expansion of franchise stores cannot be resolved through changes in the shareholding structure.

Corporate shareholding Degree (CHD), CHD is positively correlated with the company's operating performance, and at $p = 0.10$ level, it is at a significant level with ROA. This result supports the "efficiency monitoring hypothesis" put forward by Pound (1988), that is, institutional investors have more professional talents, it is easier to obtain information and have professional knowledge, so the cost of supervision is lower than that of ordinary shareholders. The market's value of the company's cash shareholdings is positive, and actual earnings management makes investors less consider the value of the company's cash shareholdings. It also confirms the effective surveillance hypothesis combining the interpersonal deception theory and the signal

theory (Chaharmahali & Tavakolnia, 2019). Institutional investors can supervise companies more professionally and more effectively than small investors and enhance the company's value. And when the shareholding ratio of institutional investors in a company is higher, it means that institutional investors are more certain of its business performance and future development, and it is a worthy investment target, which proves that the institutional corporation has more complete information and stronger supervisory capabilities. Corporate governance has a positive effect.

6.3 Managerial Implications

This study uses ordinary least squares regression model and segmented regression model to explore whether there is a significant correlation between the proportion of insiders' shareholding and the company's operating performance. Some scholars believe that the company's operating performance will also affect the shareholding ratio of insiders, that is, there is an endogenous problem between the two variables. On the other hand, since the catering industry is a very important industry in Taiwan, it has attracted a lot of attention in the capital market. Therefore, this research divides all samples into Drink, Pub, Restaurant, and Other catering section to examine the business codes of each category. Whether there is a significant difference in the correlation between the proportion of insider's shareholding and the company's operating performance.

Judging from the empirical results of the various models of all samples, the influence of insider's shareholding ratio on the company's operating performance is not a monotonous linear relationship, but an increasing but slowing relationship. Increasing the shareholding ratio of insiders can reduce agency costs and alleviate moral hazards, thereby improving the company's operating performance and protecting the rights and interests of external investors. As for the company's operating performance, it has no significant influence on the proportion of insiders' shareholding.

Based on the empirical results of various models of samples of Drink, Pub, Restaurant, and Other catering section, the correlation between insider shareholding ratio and company's operating performance is roughly consistent with the empirical results of all samples. It is worth mentioning that the empirical results of the electronics industry sample show that when the shareholding ratio of insiders exceeds 25%, the shareholding ratio of insiders has a negative influence on the company's operating performance. It seems to imply that there may

be problems raised by the job consolidation hypothesis. That is, when a director holds a considerable proportion of the company's equity, he has sufficient voting rights and influence on the board of directors. Based on the consideration of ensuring the safety of one's own position, the company will control the company's decision-making, oppose some proposals that are beneficial to shareholders, plunder the company's wealth to satisfy personal interests, and cause the company's performance to decline.

From the perspective of agency theory, the equity-based reward plan. The empirical results of this study suggest that the equity-based reward plan should have an incentive effect, that is, increase the centripetal force of employees and reduce agency costs. To alleviate the problem of moral crisis. The business community can refer to the relevant results of this research before implementing the equity-based reward plan, but the effectiveness of the equity-based reward plan needs further research and discussion.

6.4 Recommendation

Based on the empirical results and analysis, finally put forward some opinions and suggestions, as a reference for the catering industry owner, government agencies, and future investors in the relationship between corporate governance variables and operating performance. Suggestions are given as follows.

6.4.1 Catering industry owner

The empirical results of this research found that the proportion of managers shareholding shares is relatively low, and the agency problems that may arise should be paid attention to and be cautiously prevented. The prerequisite for formulating equity incentives is to have a clear and reasonable equity structure. This requires companies to handle the equity relationship between the "founders, investors and incentive targets" at the beginning to avoid unnecessary equity dispute in the future. Therefore, when building the equity structure, it needs to be decided according to the business model of the chain enterprise, which is mainly divided into the equity structure of the three business models of direct operation, franchise, and custodial joint operation. Different business models require different equity structures (Sina, 2021). Expected to give full play to the positive effects of corporate governance and improve the company's operating performance.

Franchise owner training and management should include, (1) Concept development: focus on establishing franchise owners' recognition and obedience to the headquarters. Therefore, it is necessary to confirm the consensus of both parties and give correct concepts. (2) Professional knowledge development: professional knowledge is the standards and details for performing work, at this stage, the focus is on absorbing knowledge and understanding principles. (3) Development of practical skills: professional knowledge must be combined with execution. It is mainly necessary to develop skills and fluency, and to demand accuracy and perfection. (4) Development of management skills: management of people, things, objects and moving lines, positioning, and standardization from the inside out to ensure smooth operations. The following guidance is required. (5) Acceptance assessment: Verify whether the relevant knowledge and skills learned can be flexibly applied in various aspects. (6) Regular assessment and care: assessment can be carried out from the following aspects. Through regular inspections and care, it has been building trust and smooth communication between the headquarters and franchisees and can be effectively track the operating status of the franchise group and provide timely assistance. (7) Convene franchise owner meetings: through regular meetings, communication between the headquarters and franchise owners of each store can be carried out, so that the franchise team can keep abreast of the latest developments and relevant implementation adjustments of the headquarters at any time. The use of relevant forms can more effectively control each meeting (RGANISM, 2021)..

6.4.2 Government agencies

Corporate governance involves a wide range of levels. In recent years, there have been many cases of asset emptying and fraud. Most of them have been defrauded by the management. In addition to the self-discipline spirit of the enterprise itself, the industry still needs the government to establish a corporate governance system that conforms to the international trend. It must provide complete laws and regulations as the backing, strengthen the company's concept and operation of corporate governance, and establish a set of effective and feasible disclosure standards to protect investors. The inside and outside complement each other and create a win-win situation. Fair Trade Commission's principles for handling business behaviour cases of franchise owners that is appropriate useful to protect the franchisees and customers (FTC, 2018).

Fair Trade Commission stand up for justice, report concerted action to the TFTC. Franchise performance bond. The purpose of the franchise deposit is mostly to protect the rights and interests of the franchise headquarters. It is agreed that the franchise store should fulfil its obligations in the franchise contract. Once the franchise chain violates the provisions of the franchise contract, the franchise headquarters can directly confiscate the franchise deposit in accordance with the franchise contract. The full name of the franchise bond is called the franchise performance bond. However, after some franchise systems receive the "franchise deposit", they will misappropriate the deposit paid by the franchisee and use it as a reinvestment business; once the franchise chain brand goes bankrupt due to poor management or failure to reinvest, the franchise chain brand headquarters will not be available at all. Franchisees will lose all their deposits easily. Therefore, the deposit collected by the franchise headquarters is handed over to the bank trust. When the franchise contract between the franchiser and the franchisees expires or the franchise contract is terminated in advance, the franchisee's deposit can be more securely received, even if the franchisee goes bankrupt., franchisees will also have the opportunity to get back the original franchise deposit been paid and to reduce their losses.

6.4.3 Future investors of franchise business

Based on the results of this research, when choosing a favoured brand and assessing whether the franchise fee is an amount can afford, after that, there are a few key points that need to be examined before deciding to be joining a franchise.

Observe nearby franchise stores of the same brand. If there is a franchise store of the same brand nearby, it can be observed its online and offline sales, and then use the passenger unit price to estimate whether the monthly turnover claimed by the head office is real or not. If possible, chat with other franchisees to understand their business conditions and cooperation with the headquarters. In addition, you can also go to the merchants with the worst reviews of the same brand on Google to observe and confirm whether the bad reviews are due to the store itself or the head office's quality control, and to think about whether the worst situation after opening your own store is the same as that of the other store. For example, McDonald has clearly standardized its product SOPs, had a clear division of labour, and had a low employee error rate. Therefore, even if McDonald's hires less qualified employees, it will not have a great impact on product quality.

Understand the headquarters' charging methods and business philosophy. Whether the franchise brand can make money, the most important thing is whether the headquarters is willing to give profits to the franchisees. Some headquarters charge very aggressive commissions. The franchisees are just working for the headquarters. The cost of raw materials and commissions provided by the headquarters to the franchisees, it is best to control it below 45%. If it is lower than 45%, then the franchisee has a large profit margin; if it is higher than 45%, it is considered too high, and if it is higher than 50%, there is almost no money to be made. Before joining, it is best to understand what kind of person the boss at the headquarters is, what business plans he has for the brand in the future, etc. If the boss of the headquarters is only seeking to earn franchise fees by expanding rapidly, then such a brand is also very dangerous. Usually the brand's popularity is short-lived, and if it dies quickly, franchisees may not even be able to earn back the money they originally invested.

Conditions of franchise contract. The franchise contract protects the future rights and interests of both parties, so the most important thing before joining is to read the contract in detail. If you are unfamiliar at reading contracts, you can also ask an experienced friend or contract lawyer to read them. If there are some unequal terms, do not sign it casually.

6.5 Research limitations

The coronavirus epidemic hit the catering industry very hard. According to statistics from the Ministry of Economic Affairs, the turnover of the catering industry in April this year was NT \$ 47.9 billion, not only the lowest since December 2014, but an annual decrease of 22.8%. According to data from the Ministry of Economic Affairs, the turnover of the catering industry has been decreasing for three consecutive months since February, and the rate of decline is increasing (CNA, 2020).

1. Taiwan's public catering companies are few, with only 28 companies consider, and the number of samples is of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), which may lead to statistical error. The number of samples is not large enough for a conclusive study, which may affect the results of the statistical analysis.

2. The business performance of a company is affected by many factors at the same time. This study mainly uses financial indicators to measure the business performance of the catering industry. Other non-financial factors (such as manager's integrity, morality, ability, employee centripetal force, and employee quality, etc.) are not included in this study. Which may cause the low coefficient of determination obtained after analysis. Therefore, it is recommended that follow-up researchers can use financial and non-financial factors as a measurement method, to highlight and clearly show the differences in overall operating performance.

6.6 Suggestions for future research directions

Since the research object of this study is a catering industry, the relationship between the related variables of corporate governance and operating performance is discussed. Therefore, it is impossible to conduct a more complete analysis and comparison of the relationship and difference between corporate governance and operating results of the overall industry. Future research is recommended to consider more comprehensive sample data, expand the scope of research, and conduct more complete research.

Further explore the factors that affect the shareholding ratio of corporations and then the motivations that affect business performance. Whether reinvestment in the catering industry can effectively improve operating performance.

The company's insider shareholding ratio, investment decisions, and debt decisions should have a time-delayed effect on the company's operating performance. This study did not consider the time-delayed effect in depth. Follow-up studies can further explore insider shareholding. Whether the impact of ratio, investment decision, and debt decision on the company's operating performance has a time-delayed effect.

Appendix

Appendix 1 Definition of Key Terms

Name	Definition of Key Terms
Capital market	Capital market is the part of a financial system concerned with raising capital by dealing in shares, bonds, and other long-term investments.
Managerial	Managerial is relating to management or managers, especially of a company or similar organisation.
Investors	Investor is a person or organisation that puts money into financial schemes, property, etc. with the expectation of achieving a profit.
Catering industry	Catering industry, the industry engaged in conditioning meals or beverages for immediate consumption or consumption (According to the definition of the 10th revision of the "Republic of China Industry Standard Classification" promulgated by the Executive council in 2016).

Source from: author

Appendix 2 Theories authors, method and finding list from 1996 to 2020.

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
H.G. Parsa	1996	-Power relationships -Satisfaction -Performance	This study employed a self-administered, structured questionnaire survey of a sample of QSR ⁴ franchisees in the USA. Of 752 questionnaires mailed to QSR unit managers, 141 completed, usable surveys were returned. The response rate of 18.8 % was considered acceptable in view of other studies reporting a response range of 6% to 37 %.	The balance of power in the relationship, as perceived by the franchisees, affects both the franchisees' satisfaction with the arrangement and their financial results. When franchisers have great economic power, franchisees may become dissatisfied and have lower revenues relative to their potential. On the other hand, when the franchisees perceive that their franchiser's power is noneconomic, the franchisees are more satisfied and able to achieve stronger margins.
Nerilee Hing	1996	-Marketing benefits -Financial benefits	The study was restricted to non-retail foodservice franchise systems and their franchisees owner-managers. The 27 franchise companies were contacted, only 9 later returned their completed questionnaires. This gave an effective response rate of 10.9%. The oldest system had been franchising in Australia for over 20 years and the youngest for 1 year. The franchise systems had a total of 229 franchisees who met the sampling criteria, with the largest system having 40 franchisees and the smallest having 7.	The findings indicate that, while many of the benefits for franchisees were empirically supported, considerable dissatisfaction was evident with various aspects relating to the financial costs and contractual controls imposed by franchisers and with the imbalance of power in franchise relationships. Most franchisees seem willing to accept these limitations as fair exchange for the substantial benefits they receive in choosing to purchase a franchised, rather than independent, business.
C.P. Himmelberg, R. G. Hubbard, D. Palia	1999	-Managerial ownership -Performance	The study data consists of firms from the Compustat universe over the three-year period 1982-1984., select 600 firms by random sampling, but the number of firms declines to 551 by 1985, and falls to a low of 330 by 1992. End up with managerial ownership information for about 70% of the Compustat firms.	A large fraction of the cross-sectional variation in managerial ownership is explained by unobserved firm heterogeneity. After controlling both for observed firm characteristics and firm fixed effects, this study cannot conclude (econometrically) that changes in managerial ownership affect firm performance.
V. L. Hoover, D. J. Ketchen & J. G. Combs Tracey & Jarvis	2003 2007	-Agency theory -More generally -Economic theory -Agency theory, -Resource	Examined 91 large, publicly held restaurant companies from 1989 to 1993, examined the accuracy of those two possible explanations for large restaurant companies. Case study of Aspire (social venture franchising) Examines the relevance of agency theory and resource	The decision to expand via franchising rather than by opening company-owned units stems from a desire to keep outlet-monitoring costs low combined with inexpensive access to capital. Findings include that the costs of selection are higher than in business format franchising as franchisees are assessed on

⁴ QSR: Quick-Service-Restaurant systems

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
Weaven & Frazer	2007	scarcity theory -Resource constraints theory, -Efficiency theory, Agency theory -Ownership, Allocation and Internalization (OLI) paradigm (see Dunning (2000))	scarcity theory for social venture franchising. Interviews (23 franchisers, service and retail sectors, Australia) Explores the strategic reasons justifying the recent emergence of multiple unit franchising arrangements within Australia from the perspective of the franchiser.	their ability to achieve social as well as commercial objectives and that the dual goals make goal alignment more complex and resource intensive than in business format franchising leading to higher agency costs. Franchisers encourage franchisee subsystem development because of strategic, operational and performance advantages (agency cost minimization, system-wide uniformity, brand value, reward strategies, subsystem intra-proximity, intra-system competition)
Dunning, Pak & Beldona	2007	-Agency theory, -Marketing channels theory, -Resource dependence theory	Survey (72 franchisers, several industries, U.S. & U.K.) Examines that foreign ownership choices of international franchisers and tests why a certain group of franchisers would like to own foreign outlets instead of franchising them.	Finds that international franchisers that enter foreign markets via an equity mode tend to have an exploration approach, while franchisers that enter via the franchising mode tend to have an exploitation intention.
Paik & Choi	2007	-Agency theory, -Marketing channels theory, -Resource dependence theory	Interviews (42 franchiser & franchisees, fast-food industry, U.S. & Europe) Examines the similarities and differences between domestic and international franchisees in the amount of control exerted by their U.S. franchisers and the degree of autonomy accorded to the franchisees.	Finds that international franchisees have more autonomy and that experienced international franchisees are less likely to demand autonomy, while experienced U.S. franchisees seek more autonomy. U.S. franchisers and international franchisees that experience difficulties tend to seek collaboration rather than compete for control or autonomy.
R. Lafond & S. Roychowdhury	2008	-Agency theory, -Managerial ownership	They obtain data on beginning-of-year managerial ownership from the Standard & Poor's(S&P) Execu Compdata base over the period 1994–2004. In addition, to requiring MO information were ask companies to have sufficient returns information on the Centre for Research in Security Prices (CRSP) and accounting data on Compustat to conduct our empirical analyses.	The results are consistent with equity stakeholders demanding greater conservatism as a means of addressing agency problems arising from greater separation between ownership and control. Conservatism arises as one potential mechanism to address the agency problems arising from limited liability and limited horizons. As managerial ownership declines, the severity of the agency problem increases, increasing the demand for conservatism.
S. Verbieren, M. Cools, & A. V.	2008	-Strategy -Performance	The study is based on an analysis of franchising articles published in 25 high-impact journals over the period 1996-2008. The literature is divided into 3 broad streams:	Several research gaps and avenues for future research are identified, especially towards a systematic study of management control issues in the context of franchising relationships.

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
Abbeele			1. Franchise initiation and subsequent propensity to franchise. 2. Franchise performance. 3. Control of franchising relationships.	
Bürkle & Posselt	2008	-Resource scarcity theory -Agency theory, -Signalling theory	Analytical. Examination of why franchising companies use a mixture of franchisee-owned and franchised-owned units.	Finds that the costs of risk and controlling franchised units explain the varying fraction of franchisee-owned to total selling units.
Dant, Perrigot & Cliquet	2008	-Agency theory, -Resource constraints theory, -Signalling theory	Archival (471 U.S. chains, 457 French chains, 468 Brazilian chains, service, and product & retail sector) Examination of the phenomenon of plural forms in franchising across the U.S., France and Brazil.	Findings indicate that the proportion of company-owned units within the network increases in the U.S. with company age and decrease with average total required investment Cash liquidity requirement increases in Brazil with total network size and decreases with incidence of internationalisation. For French model no statistically significant results.
Cochet & Garg	2008	-Learning theory	Archival (contract provisions of 3 chains, restaurant, food and retailing industries, Germany, range 8-18 years) & interviews (representatives of 3 chains, restaurant, food and retailing industries, Germany) Explores the evolution of formal contracts.	Finds that franchisers remain bounded rational: learning explains contract design capability better than foresight, a new management, and the pursuit of uniformity lead to contract changes and the presence of an active franchisee council promotes the efficiency of the contract change process.
Cochet, Dormann & Ehrmann	2008	Agency theory	Survey (208 franchisees from 11 chains, several industries, Germany) Tests the argument that chains counterbalance the loss in control inherent to autonomy with relational governance mechanisms.	Finds that the more relational governance becomes important the weaker agents' incentives are aligned with the interests of the entire network. Multi-unit ownership and franchisee success attenuated, and competition exacerbated the need for relational control, while age of the relationship and geographic distance did not emerge as significant moderator variables.
Y. Koh, S. Lee & S. Boo	2009	-Modern portfolio theory -Agency theory, -Resource-based view theory	Data collection from the Yahoo! Process. 75 companies were listed, but 50 companies out of the 75 were excluded because they are restaurants 100% owned or 100% franchised. The financial data for the 25 were collected from Compustat between the years 2000 and 2006.	Does not fully support the sigmoid relationship; rather a more quadratic or inverted U-shaped relationship was found.
B. Al-Najjar	2015	-Agency theory	It has two empirical stages to test our hypotheses. They employ a sample of publicly listed tourism firms in Jordan	The results show that institutional investors are self-opportunistic and negatively affect firm performance. Foreign

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
Y. Lee, Y. Nor, J. Choi, S. Kim, S. Han and J. Lee	2016	-FSR -CSR -Trust -Satisfaction	for the period spanning between 2005 and 2012, the 120 firm-year observations for 15 tourism publicly listed firms. Data was collected from foodservice franchisees located in South Korea in the spring of 2011. Out of the 420 completed responses, 204 responses were excluded from further analyses because they came from non-owners. They used a final sample of 216 for analyses. A qualitative research approach was conducted using semi structured interviews that were done face-to-face or over the phone. 27 interviews were conducted with chefs of various backgrounds and culinary focuses within the restaurant industry who held ranks in their restaurants from different parts of the world, such as the USA, Canada, Australia, England, and Hong Kong.	investors shareholding a minimum stake in a firm tend not to act as a monitoring device. The study finds that FSR and franchiser image are critical for building franchisees' trust in the franchiser, which affects franchisees' satisfaction and their long-term orientation.
W. Baldwin	2017	-Brand -Cultural		Chefs across the world are taking the traditions and flavours found in street food around Asia and applying that to restaurants and eateries while also bridging these cultures together.
A. Rosado-Serrano, J. Paul	2018	-Agency theory, -Resource-based view theory, -Transaction cost theory -Relationship theory, -Agency theory, -Resource-based view theory, -Transaction cost theory -Relationship theory, -Stakeholder theory, -Governance mode theory	Methodologies used in prior research. The research shows that international franchising has been mainly approached from 3 theoretical perspectives; agency, resource based, and transaction cost theories.	The new model has a robust and ample theoretical foundation and integrates moderating factors, which appear within franchise partnerships with those, which are used to moderate franchise performance.
A. Rosado-Serrano, J. Paul & D. Dikova	2018	-Transaction cost theory -Relationship theory, -Stakeholder theory, -Governance mode theory	Methodologies used in prior research; 8 articles followed a quantitative empirical methodology. Their review showed that international franchising research was mainly approached from three theoretical perspectives; agency, resource-based, and transaction cost theory.	They developed an overarching framework that integrates past approaches to studying international franchising with a more contemporary focus. They presented the ideas about new ways of integrating financial performance into a multi-level and dynamic analysis of international franchising.
K. Seo & A. Sharma	2018	-Prospect theory -Agency theory	Data for publicly traded U.S. restaurant firms were collected from Compustat, CRSP, and Execucomp, the final sample for this study included 659 firm year	The findings showed that overconfident CEOs, while shareholding equity-based compensation, tended to take on more strategically risky investments, and there was a

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
I. Hajdini & J. Windsperger	2019	-Risk Behaviours -Contract -Performance	observations of 45 U.S. restaurant firms from 1992 to 2013. Out of 1013 systems included in the database of German and Swiss Franchise Federations, the questionnaire was mailed to 667 franchise systems in Germany and Switzerland. Several franchisers in Austria participated in the final modification process, the system should have started franchising at least 2 years before the selection. The ANOVA test reveals no significant difference between the two respondent groups.	positive relation between franchising and risk-taking. The results of seemingly unrelated regression analyses based on data from the German and Swiss franchise sector provide support for most of the hypotheses.
K. Sun, S. Park & Z. He	2019	-Risk-sharing theory, -Agency theory,	The sample included 30 publicly traded U.S. restaurant firms categorised under Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code 5812 (eating places). 2000-2016 with cross-sectional and longitudinal dimensions.	Results generated from ordered logit regression and fixed effects OLS estimation suggest that the more involved in franchising a firm becomes, the higher bond ratings it can achieve. The positive influence of franchising on bond ratings is weakened by domestic geographic dispersion and internationalisation.
K. Sun & S. Lee	2019	-Agency theory, -Poter's model	Collecting data for the sample period of 1990 -2016 were retrieved from the COMPUSTAT database based on the standard industrial classification (SIC) code for the restaurant industry, 5812.	The findings suggest that as an interconnected governance structure, franchising offers benefits to franchisers by helping them develop competitive advantages and outperform their competitors in the market.
S. Jang & K. Park	2019	-Agency theory, -Signalling theory, -Transaction Costs theory -Social exchange theory, -Resource scarcity theory. -Property right theory	The primary objective of this study was to explain how healthy franchise systems are by proposing a model for a sustainable franchiser-franchisee relationship. This study is unique in the sense that the proposed model was constructed to reflect both franchisers and franchisees' perspectives, although more attention was paid to franchisees' benefits. To understand the foundation of franchising, this study began with a thorough review of franchise-related theories. Then, a theoretical framework for sustainable franchiser-franchisee relationships including both antecedents and consequences was suggested. Finally, this study also proposed propositions to form franchise theory that could help both franchisers and franchisees achieve a win-win situation, which is referred to later in this article as the 'franchise win-win theory.'	This study proposed a sustainable franchise-franchisee relationship model, suggesting that relationship quality is a vital part of a healthy relationship. Then, this study identified three core components of a sustainable franchiser-franchisee relationship (i.e., satisfaction, trust, and commitment) and the inter-relationships between these components. Furthermore, this study recognised the antecedents and consequences of the franchiser-franchisee relationship.

Authors	Year	Theories	Method	Finding
J. Gim & S. Jang	2019	-Agency theory, Signalling theory, -Dividend irrelevance theory, -Resource scarcity theory.	The data for this analysis was taken from the Compustate database of Wharton Research Data Services (SIC 5812). The 10-K annual reports for the sampled restaurant firms were used to determine whether firms are franchising businesses.	The findings further imply that franchise restaurants with higher free cash flows and the resulting information asymmetry closely follow agency theory and signalling theory, whereas non-franchise restaurants with insufficient internal cash strictly follow the pecking order theory.
S. Panda, A. K. Paswan & S. P. Mishra	2019	-B2B -Strategy	They randomly selected 100 franchisers listed in the Entrepreneur magazine operating in the USA. (Study I), Next, using data for 1234 US franchisers (Study II) The used an open inductive mechanism to code the data.	This study finds that both upfront fee and royalty rate are positively associated with network size, classroom, and on-the-job training, and negatively with franchising experience and support services. Internationalisation is positively associated with only royalty rate; and ownership percentage and franchisee net-worth are negatively associated with only upfront fees.
Y. Rhou, Y. Li and M. Singal	2019	-Managerial ownership -Agency theory -Risk-taking -Strategy	The sample of this study consists of publicly traded restaurant companies in the U.S. for the period of 1994 to 2006. Financial data are retrieved from Compustat using Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code 5812 for eating places. The final sample consists of 95 unique restaurant companies and 962 firm-year observations.	There is an optimal level of franchising associated with managerial ownership, implying that owners can influence their firms' risk-taking behaviour by setting target managerial ownership goals and designing effective incentive contracts.
W. E. Gillis, J. G. Combs & X. Yin	2020	-Prior theory, -Agency theory	Sample frame was the 2006 Bond's Franchise Guide (hereafter, BFG), an annual listing of approximately 1000 U.S. and Canadian franchisers in 45 industries. Survey design and scale development. Using a sample of 229 franchisers.	The findings that franchise management capabilities relate positively to franchiser performance among plural form franchisers. For 'turnkey' franchiser who franchise all, or almost all, outlets these capabilities relate indirectly to performance through lower opportunism and improved brand reputation.

Appendix 3 The sample companies and stock code

Tenren (1233)	MOS Burger (1259)	Namchow (1702)	AMBASSADOR (2704)
Silks (2707)	85Degree (2723)	Yummy Town (2726)	Wowprime (2727)
THAI TOWN (2729)	LAKAFFA (2732)	HUMBLE HOUSE (2739)	Fleur de Chine (2748)
President (2912)	THE LANDIS (5703)	New palace (8940)	Mr. Onion (2740)
HI-LAI (1268)	Holiday Garden (2702)	LEOFOO (2705)	Chateau (2722)
FX HOTEL (2724)	HOYA(2736)	TOFU (2752)	KURA SHSHI (2754)
Youngqin (2755)	LEALEA (5364)	Green World Hotels(8077)	Holiday KTV (9943)

Source from: author

Reference

Aaker, D. (1991) 'Brand equity', *La gestione del valore della marca*, Volume 347, p. 356.

Aaker, D. A. (1992) 'The value of brand equity', *Journal of business strategy*, 13(4), pp. 27-32.

Abdullah, H., & Valentine, B. (2009) 'Fundamental and ethics theories of corporate governance', *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*, 4(4), pp. 88-96.

ACFPT (2021) *About ACFPT*. Available at: <https://www.taiwanfranchise.org/index.php?lang=en> (Accessed 1 Mar. 2022).

Adnan, S. M., Hay, D., Staden, C. J. (2018) 'The influence of culture and corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure: A cross country analysis', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 198, pp. 820-832.

Aghekyan-Simonian, M., Forsythe, S., Kwon, W. S., & Chattaraman, V. (2012) 'The role of product brand image and online store image on perceived risks and online purchase intentions for apparel', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 19(3), pp. 325-331.

Alabdullah, T. T. Y. (2018) 'The relationship between ownership structure and firm financial performance: Evidence from Jordan', *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 25(1), pp. 319-333.

Ali, R., Sial, M. S., Brugni, T. V., Hwang, J., Khuong, N. V., & Khanh, T. H. T. (2019) 'Does CSR moderate the relationship between corporate governance and Chinese firm's financial performance?', *Sustainability*, 12(1), p. 149.

Al-Najjar, B., & Al-Najjar, D. (2017) 'The impact of external financing on firm value and a corporate governance index: SME evidence', *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24(2), pp. 41-423.

AMA (2017) *Definitions of Marketing*. Available at: <https://www.ama.org/the-definition-of-marketing-what-is-marketing/> (Accessed 30 Apr. 2022).

Anderson, R. C., & Reeb, D. M. (2003) 'Founding-family ownership and firm performance: evidence from the S&P 500', *The journal of finance*, 58(3), pp. 1301-1328.

- Anwar, G., & Abdullah, N. N. (2021) 'The impact of Human resource management practice on Organizational performance', *International journal of Engineering, Business and Management (IJEEM)*, p. 5.
- Aron, L. (2013) *A meeting of minds: Mutuality in psychoanalysis*. s.l.:Routledge.
- Arora, M., & Sharma, R. L. (2022) 'Artificial intelligence and big data: ontological and communicative perspectives in multi-sectoral scenarios of modern businesses', *foresight*, 25(1), pp. 126-143.
- Aulakh, P. S., Kotabe, M., & Sahay, A. (1996) 'Trust and performance in cross-border marketing partnerships: A behavioral approach', *Journal of international business studies*, Volume 27, pp. 1005-1032.
- Ayunitha, A., Sulastri, H. W., Fauzi, M. I., Sakti, M. A. P., & Nugraha, N. M (2020) 'Does the Good Corporate Governance Approach Affect Agency Cost', *Solid State Technology*, pp. 3760-3770.
- Badrinarayanan, V., Suh, T., & Kim, K. M. (2016) 'Brand resonance in franchising relationships: A franchisee-based perspective', *Journal of business research*, 69(10), pp. 3943-3950.
- Baena, V. (2012) 'Market conditions driving international franchising in emerging markets', *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 20 1, 7(1), pp. 49-71.
- Barich, H., & Kotler, P. (1991) 'A framework for marketing image management', *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 32(2), p. 94.
- Barthélemy, B., & Courrèges, P. (2011) *Gestion des risques: méthode d'optimisation globale*. s.l.:Editions Eyrolles.
- Barzuza, M. (2010) 'Does the Structure of the Franchise Tax Matter', *Va. L. Rev. Brief*, Volume 96, p. 27.
- Bencomo, R. Q. (2021) 'The Role of Independent Non-Executive Directors in Resolving Corporate Governance Disputes: A Framework of Conciliation for Effectively Addressing Controversies Within Shareholders, Stakeholders and the Board of Directors', *Trento Student Law Review*, 3(1), pp. 17-58.
- Berkowitz, A. D.(2004) *The social norms approach: Theory, research, and annotated bibliography*.. s.l.:s.n.

- Bettinelli, C. (2012) *The effectiveness of the board of directors in the family business*. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/37159140> *The effectiveness of the board of directors in the family business* (Accessed 15 Mar. 2022).
- Bewayo, E. D. (2009) 'Family Business In Africa: A Comparison With The ILS.-Western Model', *Journal of Global Business Issues*, 3(1), p. 171.
- Bhaumik, S. K., & Gregoriou, A. (2010) 'Family'ownership, tunnelling and earnings management: A review of the literature', *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 24(4), pp. 705-730.
- Borodzicz, E. P. (2019) *Ethnography as An Approach*, Portsmouth: Portsmouth Business School .
- Brean, D. J. S. (2021) *Corporate Governance: International Perspectives*. Available at: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781315204802-15/corporate-governance-international-perspectives-donald-brean> (Accessed 17 Mar. 2022).
- Brinkerink, J., & Bammens, Y. (2018) 'Family influence and R&D spending in Dutch manufacturing SMEs: the role of identity and socioemotional decision considerations', *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 35(4), pp. 588-608.
- Broccardo, L., Truant, E., & Zicari, A. (2019) 'Internal corporate sustainability drivers: What evidence from family firms? A literature review and research agenda', *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 26(1), pp. 1-18.
- Burhanuddin, S. F. (2021) *Franchise Agreement in Civil Law Perspective*. s.l., s.n., pp. 39-43.
- Byrd, J. W., & Hickman, K. A. (1992) 'Do outside directors monitor managers?: Evidence from tender offer bids', *Journal of financial economics*, 32(2), pp. 195-221.
- C. Wang, C. Ng, R. Brook (2020) 'Response to COVID-19 in Taiwan Big Data Analytics, New Technology, and Proactive Testing', *JAMA Network*, 33, p. 323.
- Çalışkan, O. (2013) 'Destinasyon rekabetçiliği ve seyahat motivasyonu bakımından', *Journal of Tourism & Gastronomy Studies*, 1(2), pp. 39-51.
- Castrogiovanni, G. J., Combs, J. G., & Justis, R. T. (2006) 'Shifting imperatives: An integrative view of resource scarcity and agency reasons for franchising', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(1), pp. 23-40.

- Ceasar, M. J. C. (2021) *anagement: A Win-Win Strategy for Organisational Effectiveness in the Changing Global Business Environment*. Available at: academia.edu (Accessed 10 Feb. 2022).
- Ceva, E., Testino, C., & Zuolo, F. (2015) 'The legitimacy of the supranational regulation of local systems of food production. A discussion whose time has come', *Journal of Social Philosophy*, *Forthcoming*.
- CFI (2021) *Market to Book Ratio (Price to Book) - Formula, Examples, Interpretation*. Available at: <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/knowledge/valuation/market-to-book-ratio-price-book/> (Accessed 5 Apr. 2022).
- Chaganti, R. S., Mahajan, V., & Sharma, S. (1985) 'Corporate board size, composition and corporate failures in retailing industry [1]', *Journal of management studies*, 22(4), pp. 400-417.
- Chakraborty, C. (2021) *The 'landmines' you may have bought in this market in hunt for a quick buck*. Available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/markets/stocks/news/the-landmines-you-may-have-bought-in-this-market-in-hunt-for-a-quick-buck/articleshow/80341294.cms?from=mdr> (Accessed 10 Feb. 2022).
- Chen, N. (2021) *In 2020, the global investment in catering technology will reach 22.3 billion! Catalyzed by the epidemic, how should Taiwan's catering industry catch up?*. Available at: <https://nommagazine.com/> (Accessed 05 Jan. 2022).
- Chen, W.(2020) *Research on the Brand Aging and Brand Rebuilding Process in the Catering Industry - Taking Yiqi as an Example*. 1 ed. Taiwan: National Taiwan Normal University.
- Chen, Z. (2017) *2017 Taiwan's top 20 international brands announced*. Available at: <https://www.chinatimes.com/newspapers/20171130000348-260511?chdtv> (Accessed 10 Dec. 2020).
- Chi, H. K., Yeh, H. R., & Yang, Y. T. (2009) 'The impact of brand awareness on consumer purchase intention: The mediating effect of perceived quality and brand loyalty', *The journal of international management studies*, 4(1), pp. 135-144.
- CHUANG, T. (2009) *The effects that the bonds between systems toward the operational performances of chain-like alliance system — Take the food and drinks industry of franchise system for example.*, Taiwan: Kainan University.
- Civitello, L. (2011) *uisine and culture: A history of food and people*. s.l.:John Wiley & Sons.

Clarkin, J. E., & Swavely, S. M. (2006) 'The importance of personal characteristics in franchisee selection', *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 13(2), pp. 133-142.

CAN (2020) *Catering industry turnover fell avalanche in April, annual decline rate hit the largest in 20 years*. Available at: <https://udn.com/news/story/7238/4589328> (Accessed 10 Jan. 2022).

COBUILD, C. (2021) *food preparation*. Available at: <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/food-preparation> (Accessed 12 Mar. 2022).

Colla, E., Ruiz-Molina, E., Chastenet De Gery, C., & Deparis, M. (2020) 'Franchisee's entrepreneurial orientation dimensions and performance. Evidence from France', *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 30(5), pp. 538-554.

Combs, J. G., & Ketchen Jr, D. J. (2003) 'Why do firms use franchising as an entrepreneurial strategy?: A meta-analysis' *Journal of management*, 29(3), pp. 443-465.

Combs, J. G., Ketchen Jr, D. J., & Short, J. C. (2011) 'Franchising research: Major milestones, new directions, and its future within entrepreneurship', *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(3), pp. 413-425.

Combs, J. G., Michael, S. C., & Castrogiovanni, G. J. (2004) 'Franchising: A review and avenues to greater theoretical diversity', *Journal of management*, 30(6), pp. 907-931.

Dalbor, M. C., Kim, A., & Upneja, A. (2004) 'An initial investigation of firm size and debt use by small restaurant firms', *The Journal of Hospitality Financial Management*, 12(1), pp. 41-48.

Dale, M., Shepherd, D., & Woods, C. (2008) 'Family models as a framework for employment relations in entrepreneurial family businesses', *New Zealand Journal of Employment Relations*, 33(1), p. 47.

Deloitte (2018) *Global Powers of Retailing 2017*. Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/tw/tc/pages/consumer-business/articles/powers-of-retailing2017.html> (Accessed 10 Dec. 2021).

DGBAS (2021) *Semi-annual settlement report*. Available at: <https://www.dgbas.gov.tw/mp.asp?mp=1> (Accessed 30 Dec. 2021).

- Dissing, C., Andersen, N., & Thrane-Møller, J (2010) *Retail Branding and Positioning*. s.l.:s.n.
- Durant, K. (2020) *Promotion Ideas for Catering*. Available at: <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/promotion-ideas-catering-23054.html> (Accessed 11 Mar. 2022).
- Dzwigol, H., Shcherbak, S., Semikina, M., Vinichenko, O., & Vasiuta, V. (2019) 'Formation of Strategic Change Management System at an Enterprise', *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, pp. 1-8.
- Ecourseonline (2020) *Catering management*. Available at: <http://ecourseonline.iasri.res.in/mod/page/view.php?id=110599> (Accessed 15 Dec. 2021).
- Einstein, M. (2012) *Compassion, Inc.* s.l.:University of California Press.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989) 'Agency theory: An assessment and review', *Academy of management review*, 14(1), pp. 57-74.
- Eisenhardt, K. M. (1989) 'Building theories from case study research', *Academy of management review*, 14(4), pp. 532-550.
- Entrepreneur (2021) *Balance Sheet*. Available at: <https://www.entrepreneur.com/encyclopedia/balance-sheet> (Accessed 15 Jan. 2022).
- e-volunteer (2021) *Chain franchise and catering chain development plan (109-112)*. Available at: <https://www.e-volunteer.org.tw/upload/newsfs51906084808135207.pdf> (Accessed 10 Feb. 2022).
- Executive-Yuan (2016) *Important policy*. Available at: <https://www.ey.gov.tw/Page/5A8A0CB5B41DA11E/86f143fa-8441-4914-8349-c474afe0d44e> (Accessed 10 May 2020).
- Faccio, M., & Lang, L. H. (2002) 'The ultimate ownership of Western European corporations', *Journal of financial economics*, 65(3), pp. 365-395.
- Faisal, K., Khan, A. K., & Al-Aboud, O. A. (2018) 'Study of Managerial Decision Making Linked to Operating and Financial Leverage', *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 7(1), pp. 139-143.
- Faith, D. O. (2018) 'A Review of the Effect of Pricing Strategies on the Purchase of Consumer Goods', *International Journal of Research in Management, Science & Technology*, Volume 2, pp. 2321-3264.

- FAO (2020) *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Available at: <http://www.fao.org/3/W5973E/w5973e02.htm> (Accessed 11 Mar. 2021).
- Felix, R. (2014) 'Multi-brand loyalty: when one brand is not enough', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 17(4), pp. 464-480.
- FERNANDO, J. (2021) *What Are Capital Expenditures (CapEx)?*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/capitalexpenditure.asp> (Accessed 14 Mar. 2022).
- Fox, R. (2007) 'Reinventing the Gastronomic Identity of Croatian Tourist Destinations', *International journal of hospitality management*, 26(3), pp. 546-559.
- Franchise Direct (2012) *Franchising and Corporate Social Responsibility*. Available at: <https://www.franchisedirect.co.uk/information/guidetobuyingafanchise/franchisingandcorporatesocialresponsibility/52/1480/> (Accessed 10 Dec. 2020).
- FranchiseDirect (2020) *Food Franchise opportunities: Fast Food & Restaurant Franchises for sale*. Available at: <https://www.franchisedirect.co.uk/foodfranchises/186> (Accessed 31 Dec. 2021).
- Frazer, L., Weaven, S., Giddings, J., & Grace, D. (2012) 'What went wrong? Franchisors and franchisees disclose the causes of conflict in franchising', *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 15(1), pp. 87-103.
- FTC (2018) *The Fair Trade Commission's principles for handling business behavior cases of franchise owners*. Available at: <https://www.ftc.gov.tw/internet/main/doc/docDetail.aspx?uid=167&docid=11795> (Accessed 11 Nov. 2023).
- FTC (2021) *Survey on the operation of chain retail stores (quantity supermarkets)*. Available at: <https://www.ftc.gov.tw/> (Accessed 15 Jan. 2022).
- Gärling, T., & Golledge, R. G. (2018) 'Cognitive mapping and spatial decision-making', *In Cognitive Mapping*, pp. 44-65.
- Gatersleben, B. (2001) 'Sustainable household consumption and quality of life: the acceptability of sustainable consumption patterns and consumer policy strategies', *International Journal of Environment and Pollution*, 15(2), pp. 200-216.

Gillis, W. E., Combs, J. G., & Yin, X. (2020) 'Franchise management capabilities and franchisor performance under alternative franchise ownership strategies', *Journal of business venturing*, 1(105899), p. 35.

Goodinfo (2021) *Goodinfo! Taiwan stock information website*. Available at: <https://goodinfo.tw/StockInfo/index.asp> (Accessed 16 Apr. 2022).

Gugler, K., Mueller, D. C., & Yurtoglu, B. B (2008) 'Insider ownership, ownership concentration and investment performance: An international comparison', *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 14(5), pp. 688-705.

Hallak, M., Berman, R. F., Irtenkau, S. M., Evans, M. I., & Cotton, D. B. (1992) 'Peripheral magnesium sulfate enters the brain and increases the threshold for hippocampal seizures in rats', *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*, 167(6), pp. 1605-1610.

Hao, G. (2022) *Research on the Agency Problem, Corporate Governance and Firm Value*. s.l., Atlantis Press, pp. 2917-2923.

HAYES, A. (2021) *Total-Debt-to-Total-Assets Ratio*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/totaldebttotalassets.asp> (Accessed 16 Jan. 2022).

Hennart, J. F., & Verbeke, A. (2022) 'Actionable and enduring implications of Oliver Williamson's transaction cost theory', *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(8), pp. 1557-1575.

Hillman, A. J., Cannella, A. A., & Paetzold, R. L. (2000) 'The resource dependence role of corporate directors: Strategic adaptation of board composition in response to environmental change', *Journal of Management studies*, 37(2), pp. 235-256.

Hizam-Hanafiah, M., Abdul Ghani, M. F., Mat Isa, R., & Abd Hamid, H. (2022) 'Critical Success Factors of Franchising Firms: A Study on Franchisors and Franchisees', *Administrative Sciences*, 13(1), p. 8.

Hsu, J. L. (2013) 'Key success factors in catering franchises', *International Journal of Organizational Innovation (Online)*, 5(3), p. 72.

Hu, W., Du, J., ZHANG, W. (2020) 'Corporate Social Responsibility Information Disclosure and Innovation Sustainability: Evidence from China', *Sustainability*, 12(1), p. 409.

Hua, H. (2019) *Mobile marketing management: Case studies from successful practices*. s.l.:CRC Press.

Huang, W. (2021) *Statistics on the turnover of wholesale, retail and catering industry in August 2021*. Available at: https://www.moea.gov.tw/MNS/populace/news/News.aspx?kind=1&menu_id=40&news_id=96989 (Accessed 11 May 2022).

Hult, G. T. M., Hair Jr, J. F., Proksch, D., Sarstedt, M., Pinkwart, A., & Ringle, C. M (2018) 'Addressing endogeneity in international marketing applications of partial least squares structural equation modeling', *Journal of International Marketing*, 26(3), pp. 1-21.

IFA (2019) *THE HISTORY OF MODERN FRANCHISING*. Available at: <https://www.franchise.org/blog/the-history-of-modern-franchising> (Accessed 10 Oct. 2022).

Ilmi, M., Kustono, A. S., & Sayekti, Y. (2017) 'EFFECT OF GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY DISCLOSURE AND MANAGERIAL OWNERSHIP TO THE CORPORATE VALUE WITH FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AS INTERVENING VARIABLES: CASE ON INDONESIA STOCK EXCHANGE', *International Journal of Social Science and Business*, 1(2), pp. 75-88.

Indeed (2021) *How to Calculate Total Debt (With Example)*. Available at: <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/how-to-calculate-total-debt> (Accessed 15 Mar. 2022).

Insee (2019) *Investment rate (business statistics)*. Available at: <https://www.insee.fr/en/metadonnees/definition/c1262> (Accessed 11 May 2020).

Jang, S. S., & Park, K. (2019) 'A sustainable franchisor-franchisee relationship model: Toward the franchise win-win theory', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Volume 76, pp. 13-24.

Jayachandran, S., Kaufman, P., Kumar, V., & Hewett, K. (2013) 'Brand licensing: What drives royalty rates?', *Journal of Marketing*, 77(5), pp. 108-122.

Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1979) 'Rights and production functions: An application to labor-managed firms and codetermination', *Journal of business*, pp. 469-506.

Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (2019) 'Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure', *Corporate governance*, pp. 77-132.

Jha, C. K. (2022) *Business proposal for new fast-food chain restaurant in Taiwan*, Taiwan: National Taiwan University.

Johnson, N. (2009) *Simply complexity: A clear guide to complexity theory*. s.l.:Simon and Schuster.

Kao, M. F., Hodgkinson, L., & Jaafar, A. (2019) 'Ownership structure, board of directors and firm performance: evidence from Taiwan', *Corporate Governance: The international journal of business in society*, 19(1), pp. 189-216.

Katsikeas, C. S. (2003) 'Reflections on Czinkota and Ronkainen's international marketing manifesto: A perspective from Europe', *Journal of International Marketing*, 11(1), pp. 28-34.

Keller, K. L. (1993) 'Conceptualizing, measuring, and managing customer-based brand equity', *Journal of marketing*, 57(1), pp. 1-22.

KENTON, W. (2021) *Pearson Coefficient*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/pearsoncoefficient.asp> (Accessed 16 Jan. 2022).

Khan, M. K., Kaleem, A., He, Y., Akram, U. Akram, Z., Chen, Y. (2017) 'Research on implication of convergence of interest hypothesis: Evidence from listed firms', *Human Systems Management*, 36(3), pp. 187-195.

Khan, R., Khidmat, W. B., Hares, O. A., Muhammad, N., & Saleem, K. (2020) 'Corporate governance quality, ownership structure, agency costs and firm performance. Evidence from an emerging economy', *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(7), p. 154.

Kknews (2017) *There are three types of chain management models, and chain management companies should avoid these misunderstandings!*. Available at: <https://kknews.cc/career/l2mxkvb.html> (Accessed 10 Dec. 2020).

Kotler, P. (1991) 'Kotler on', *Management Decision*, 29(2).

Kuokkanen, H., & Sun, W(2020) 'Companies, meet ethical consumers: Strategic CSR management to impact consumer choice', *Journal of Business Ethics*, Volume 166, pp. 403-423.

Kurniati, S. (2019) 'Stock returns and financial performance as mediation variables in the influence of good corporate governance on corporate value', *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 19 11, 19(6), pp. 1289-1309.

Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M. (2021) 'Corporate governance and firms financial performance in the United Kingdom', *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), pp. 1871-1885.

- Lafontaine, F. (1992) 'Agency theory and franchising: some empirical results', *The rand journal of economics*, pp. 263-283.
- Laroche, M., Kim, C., & Zhou, L. (1996) 'Brand familiarity and confidence as determinants of purchase intention: An empirical test in a multiple brand context', *Journal of business Research*, 37(2), pp. 115-120.
- Lee, C. (2007) 'Cultural convergence: Interest convergence theory meets the cultural defense', *Ariz. L. Rev.*, Volume 49, p. 911.
- Leland, H. E., & Pyle, D. H. (1977) 'Informational asymmetries, financial structure, and financial intermediation', *The journal of Finance*, 32(2), pp. 371-387.
- Libava, J. (2020) *The History of Franchising As We Know It*. Available at: <https://articles.bplans.com/the-history-of-franchising-as-we-know-it/> (Accessed 1 3 2021).
- Li, L. (2017) *2017 Chain Store Yearbook, the number of chain brands increased by 5.4%*. Available at: <https://www.chinatimes.com/realtimenews/20170419005345-260410?chdtv> (Accessed 31 12 2020).
- Lin, L., & Mao, P. C. (2015) 'Food for memories and culture—A content analysis study of food specialties and souvenirs', *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, Volume 22, pp. 19-29.
- Lin, P. C., Lin, C. J., Shen, C. W., & Wang, J. (2020) 'The revenue and logistics costs of convenience store chains in Taiwan', *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 48(11), pp. 1255-1273.
- Li, T. (2021) *Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/v/variance-inflation-factor.asp> (Accessed 5 1 2022).
- Loewenstein, G., & Lerner, J. S. (2003) 'The role of affect in decision making', *Handbook of affective science*, 642(3), p. 619.
- Lumen (2020) *Franchising*. Available at: <https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-business/chapter/franchising/> (Accessed 1 5 2021).
- Luo, X., & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2006) 'Corporate social responsibility, customer satisfaction, and market value', *Journal of marketing*, 70(4), pp. 1-18.

- Maeenuddina, R. B., Hussain, A., Hafeez, M., Khan, M., & Wahi, N (2020) 'Economic Value Added Momentum & Traditional Profitability Measures (ROA, ROE & ROCE): A Comparative Study', *Test Engineering and Management*, 83(April), pp. 13762-13774.
- Maialeh, R. (2020) 'Growth Theories and Convergence Hypothesis'. In: Springer: Cham, pp. 39-65.
- Martínez-Ferrero, J., & Lozano, M. B. (2021) 'The Nonlinear Relation between Institutional Ownership and Environmental, Social and Governance Performance in Emerging Countries', *Sustainability*, 13(3), p. 1586.
- Matthes, J. M., Saini, A., & Dubey, V. K. (2021) 'Performance implications of marketing agreement, cooperation, and control in franchising', *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 29(3), pp. 387-408.
- MBASkooTeam (2013) *F-Test Meaning & Definition*. Available at: <https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/statistics/8633-f-test.html> (Accessed 3 12 2020).
- McGaun, L. (2020) *THE STATE OF THE UK ECONOMY DURING LOCKDOWN AND BEYOND*. Available at: <https://impactnottingham.com/2020/06/the-state-of-the-uk-economy-during-lockdown-and-beyond/> (Accessed 5 12 2021).
- McLaughlin, J., McLaughlin, J., & Elaydi, R. (2014) 'Ian Macneil and relational contract theory: evidence of impact', *Journal of Management History*, 20(1), pp. 44-61.
- Means, G. (2017) *The Modern Corporation and Private Property*. s.l.:Routledge.
- Merendino, A., & Melville, R. (2019) 'The board of directors and firm performance: empirical evidence from listed companies', *The international journal of business in society*, 19(3), pp. 508-551.
- Mherman (2021) *A BRIEF HISTORY OF FRANCHISING*. Available at: <https://www.franchise-law.com/franchise-law-overview/a-brief-history-of-franchising.shtml> (Accessed 1 3 2021).
- Miller, D., & Le Breton-Miller (2005) *Managing for the long run: Lessons in competitive advantage from great family businesses*. s.l.:Harvard Business Press.
- MIRAI BUSINESS (2020) *A picture analyzes the layout of Taiwan's top 10 chain restaurant groups. Which three models are used to expand their territory?*. Available at: <https://www.bnext.com.tw/article/58913/catering-taiwan-2020> (Accessed 10 7 2021).

MOEA (2015) *Franchise to earn international wealth*. Available at: www.trademag.org.tw (Accessed 1 Nov. 2020).

Moorman, C., Deshpande, R., & Zaltman, G. (1993) 'Factors affecting trust in market research relationships', *Journal of marketing*, 57(1), pp. 81-101.

Moro, M. (2020) *The Definition of a Catering Service*. Available at: <https://bizfluent.com/about-6597461-definition-catering-service.html>

(Accessed 30 Oct. 2021).

MOTC (2021) *Summary of Tourism Market Survey*. Available at: <https://admin.taiwan.net.tw/> (Accessed 2 Jan. 2022).

Muniz Jr, A. M., & O'guinn, T. C. (2001) 'Brand community', *Journal of consumer research*, 27(4), pp. 412-432.

MURPHY, C. B. (2021) *Property, Plant, and Equipment (PP&E)*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/p/ppe.asp> (Accessed 10 Jan 2022).

National-Statistics (2011) *National Statistics, R.O.C. (Taiwan)*. Available at: <https://www.stat.gov.tw/mp.asp?mp=4> (Accessed 12 Jan. 2022).

NBS (2021) *Natioal Bureau of Statistics*. Available at: <http://www.stats.gov.cn/tjsj/ndsj/> (Accessed 30 Jan. 2022).

NielsenIQ (2018) *The Warring States Period of Taiwan's Retail Channels*. Available at: <https://nielseniq.com/global/zh/insights/report/2018/taiwan-retail-landscape-report-2018/> (Accessed 11 Jan. 2022).

Nyadzayo, M. W., Matanda, M. J., & Ewing, M. T. (2011) 'Brand relationships and brand equity in franchising', *Industrial Marketing Management*, 40(7), pp. 1103-1115.

Nyadzayo, M. W., Matanda, M. J., & Rajaguru, R. (2018) 'The determinants of franchise brand loyalty in B2B markets: An emerging market perspective', *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 86, pp. 435-445.

O'Reilly, C. A., & Chatman, J. A. (1996) 'Culture as social control: Corporations, cults, and commitment. In B. M. Staw & L. L. Cummings (Eds.)', *Research in organizational behavior: An annual series of analytical essays and critical reviews*, Volume 18, pp. 157-200.

Pai-Vaidya, S. (2018) *Evaluation of Selected Franchise Business in the State of Goa-An Empirical Study*. s.l., Goa University.

- Panda, B., & Leepsa, N. M. (2017) 'Agency theory: Review of theory and evidence on problems and perspectives', *Indian journal of corporate governance*, 10(1), pp. 74-95.
- Park, K., & Jang, S. S. (2010) 'Insider ownership and firm performance: An examination of restaurant firms', *Journal of Hospitality Management*, 29(3), pp. 448-458.
- Patwa, N., Sivarajah, U., Seetharaman, A., Sarkar, S., Maiti, K., & Hingorani, K. (2021) 'Towards a circular economy: An emerging economies context', *Journal of business research*, Volume 122, pp. 725-735.
- Pwc (2018) *PwC 2018 Global Consumer Insights Survey*. Available at: <https://www.pwc.tw/zh/news/press-release/press-20180313.html> (Accessed 21 May 2021).
- PwC (2021) *Zicheng United Accounting Firm*. Available at: <https://www.pwc.tw/> (Accessed 10 Feb. 2022).
- Radder, L., & Huang, W. (2008) 'High-involvement and low-involvement products: A comparison of brand awareness among students at a South African university', *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 12(2), pp. 232-243.
- Ramírez-Hurtado, J. M., Quattrociocchi, B., & Berbel-Pineda, J. M. (2022) 'Factors affecting the decision and the degree of the internationalisation of franchises', *European Journal of International Management*, 17(4), p. 583-610.
- Ray, K. G.(2020) 'Hostile Takeover: Who Benefits from Virtual Business Combination?', *In Advances in Mergers and Acquisitions*, Volume 19, pp. 101-124.
- Reisch, L., Eberle, U., & Lorek, S. (2013) 'Sustainable food consumption: an overview of contemporary issues and policies', *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy*, 9(2), pp. 7-25.
- RGANISM (2021) *Franchisee training management*. Available at: <https://www.organism.com.tw/download/franchisee> (Accessed 20 Feb 2022).
- Rhou, Y., Li, Y., & Singal, M (2019) 'Does managerial ownership influence franchising in restaurant companies?', *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Volume 78, pp. 122-130.
- Rondán Cataluña, F. J. N. G. A. & D. d. C. E. C. (2007) 'Proposing new variables for the identification of strategic groups in franchising', *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, Volume 3, pp. 355-377.

- Rosado-Serrano, A., Paul, J., & Dikova, D. (2018) 'International franchising: A literature review and research agenda', *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 85, pp. 238-257.
- Ruback, R. S. (1983) 'Assessing competition in the market for corporate acquisitions', *Journal of Financial Economics*, 11(1-4), pp. 141-153.
- Rubin, D. B. (1978) 'Bayesian inference for causal effects: The role of randomization', *The Annals of statistics*, pp. 34-58.
- Samiee, S. (1994) 'Customer evaluation of products in a global market', *Journal of international business studies*, Volume 25, pp. 579-604.
- Sashi, C. M., & Brynildsen, G. (2022) 'Franchise network relationships and word of mouth communication in social media networks', *Industrial Marketing Management*, Volume 102, pp. 153-163.
- Schewe, C. D., Smith, R. M. (1983) *Marketing: concepts and applications*. s.l.:McGraw-Hill.
- Schooley, S. (2019) *Business News Daily*. Available at: <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/4679-corporate-social-responsibility.html> (Accessed 1 Nov. 2021).
- Scott, F. A. (1995) 'Franchising vs. company ownership as a decision variable of the firm', *Review of industrial organization*, Volume 10, pp. 69-81.
- Seo, K., & Sharma, A. (2018) 'CEO overconfidence and the effects of equity-based compensation on strategic risk-taking in the US restaurant industry', *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 42(2), pp. 224-259.
- Shahram Chaharmahali & Esmail Tavakolnia (2019) 'Real Earnings Management and Market Value of Cash Holdings: The Role of Efficient Monitoring Hypothesis and Combination of Interpersonal Deception Theory and Signaling Theory', *Journal of Management Accounting and Auditing Knowledge*, pp. 127-144.
- Shane, S. A. (1998) 'Making new franchise systems work', *Strategic Management Journal*, 19(7), pp. 697-707.
- Sharma, A. (1997) 'Professional as agent: Knowledge asymmetry in agency exchange', *Academy of Management review*, 22(3), pp. 758-798.

- Shen, N. (2018) 'Family business, transgenerational succession and diversification strategy: Implication from a dynamic socioemotional wealth model', *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, 25(4), pp. 628-641.
- Shevchuk, O. O. (2021) 'MODERN TRENDS IN THE FRANCHISE FORM OF TOURISM BUSINESS', *MINISTRY OF EDUCATION AND SCIENCE OF UKRAINE NATIONAL AVIATION UNIVERSITY*, p. 281.
- Siebert, M. (2015) *The 9 Advantages of Franchising*. Available at: <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/252591> (Accessed 10 Oct. 2020).
- Sina (2021) *Aide Quancheng ESOP: This is a recipe for chain brand enterprise equity incentive design!*. Available at: <https://news.sina.com.tw/article/20210813/39579040.html> (Accessed 12 Feb 2022).
- Smith, J. B., & Barclay, D. W. (1997) 'The effects of organizational differences and trust on the effectiveness of selling partner relationships', *Journal of marketing*, 61(1), pp. 3-21.
- Song, S., Park, S., & Lee, S. (2019) 'Does franchising reduce geographically diversified restaurant firms' risk?', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 31(1), pp. 161-179.
- StatisticsHowTo (2021) *Correlation Coefficient: Simple Definition, Formula, Easy Steps*. Available at: <https://www.statisticshowto.com/probability-and-statistics/correlation-coefficient-formula/> (Accessed 13 Jan. 2022).
- Stewart, A., & Hitt, M. A. (2012) 'Why can't a family business be more like a nonfamily business? Modes of professionalization in family firms', *Family Business Review*, 25(1), pp. 58-86.
- Stouten, J., Rousseau, D. M., & De Cremer, D. (2018) 'Successful organizational change: Integrating the management practice and scholarly literatures', *Academy of Management Annals*, 12(2), pp. 752-788.
- Stulz, R. (1988) 'Managerial control of voting rights: Financing policies and the market for corporate control', *Journal of financial Economics*, Volume 20, pp. 25-54.
- TEJ (2021) *Company Overview*. Available at: <https://www.tej.com.tw/about> (Accessed 15 Jan. 2022).

- Thakor, M. V., & Katsanis, L. P. (1997) 'A model of brand and country effects on quality dimensions: issues and implications', *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 9(3), pp. 79-100.
- Thomas, C. W. (1998) 'Maintaining and restoring public trust in government agencies and their employees', *Administration & society*, 30(2), pp. 166-193.
- Thomson, M., MacInnis, D. J., & Whan Park, C. (2005) 'The ties that bind: Measuring the strength of consumers' emotional attachments to brands', *Journal of consumer psychology*, 15(1), pp. 77-91.
- Tillotson, L. M. (1980) *Toward a contingency theory of organizational effectiveness*. s.l.:Iowa State University.
- Tsai, C. C., & Li, D. (2020) 'A Study of Influential Factors of Entrepreneurial Performance of Taiwan Small and Medium Enterprise', *In Education and Awareness of Sustainability: Proceedings of the 3rd Eurasian Conference on Educational Innovation 2020 (ECEI 2020)*, pp. 41-13.
- Tsai, W. H., Hung, J. H., Kuo, Y. C., & Kuo, L. (2006) 'CEO tenure in Taiwanese family and nonfamily firms: An agency theory perspective', *Family Business Review*, 19(1), pp. 11-28.
- TTR (2020) *Catering industry development trend*, Taipei: TTR Taiwan Trend Research Report.
- TWIN, A. (2020) *Marketing*. Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/marketing.asp> (Accessed 20 Dec. 2021).
- TWSE (2021) *International Financial Reporting Standards*. Available at: <https://www.twse.com.tw/IFRS/about> (Accessed 30 12 2021).
- Verbieren, S., Cools, M., & Van den Abbeele, A. (2008) 'Franchising: a literature review on management and control issues', *Review of Business and Economics*, 53(4), pp. 398-443.
- Vickers, A. J., Van Calster, B., & Steyerberg, E. W. (2016) 'Net benefit approaches to the evaluation of prediction models, molecular markers, and diagnostic tests', *bmj*, p. 352.
- Wang, S. & Mazzetta, M. (2020) *Taiwan's restaurant industry posts record 29% sales growth in May*. Available at: <https://focustaiwan.tw/business/202006230028> (Accessed 5 March 2021).

- Wang, W. (2020) *Catering industry out of the haze of the epidemic Wangpin, Wacheng Q3 revenue hits high*. Available at: <https://news.cnyes.com/news/id/4532825> (Accessed 5 March 2021).
- Watson, D., Naragon-Gainey, K. (2014) 'Personality, Emotions, and the Emotional Disorders', *Sage Journals*, 2(4), pp. 422-442.
- Webb, D., Webster, C., & Krepapa, A. (2000) 'An exploration of the meaning and outcomes of a customer-defined market orientation', *Journal of business research*, 48(2), pp. 101-112.
- WHO (2020) *Coronavirus*. Available at: https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_1 (Accessed 5 March 2021).
- Xplained (2021) *Capital Intensity Ratio*. Available at: <https://xplained.com/796295/capital-intensity-ratio> (Accessed 5 March 2021).
- Xu, S. (2023) *'2023 Services industry outlook report'*, Taipei: The General Chamber of Commerce of the R.O.C..
- Yang, Y. (2019) *"Finance and Economics Weekly-Cover Story-Failure" Remaining talents to start a business, many franchise stores fail to end*. Available at: <https://ec.ltn.com.tw/article/paper/1262832> (Accessed 5 March 2021).
- Yao, H., Haris, M., & Tariq, G (2018) Profitability determinants of financial institutions: evidence from banks in Pakistan. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 6(2), p. 53.
- Yao, M.-I. (2019) 'Creating and re-creating the nation of Taiwan: representations of the history of the Japanese colonial era in history textbooks and teachers' discourses', *ational Identities*, pp. 305-320.
- Zhao, Y. (2021) *Globalization and Its Impacts on Economic Development of Alibaba Company*, s.l.: s.n.
- Zheng, J. (2018) *[Brand Transformation] The past and future of Taiwanese restaurant brands*. Available at: <https://www.expbravo.com/> (Accessed 5 March 2021).
- Zhou, M. (2020) *WU-NAN CULTURE ENTERPRISE*. Available at: <http://www.wunan.com.tw/> (Accessed 5 March 2021).

